

VALKYRIES

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1. Executive Summary

This document describes the preparation, development, and analysis of the first demonstrator. It is the first and the largest scale of those planned, considering the number of victims and first responders participating. A full-scale multi-victim incident simulation was conducted on the Spain-Portugal border. It involved a forest fire, a traffic accident, and first responders from both countries.

A full-scale exercise simulates a real event as closely as possible and is designed to evaluate the operational capability of emergency management systems in a highly stressful environment, simulating current response conditions. The full scale should test and evaluate most functions of emergency plans and allow evaluation of procedures, systems functionality and tools to improve response capacity to new incidents. Typically involves multiple agencies and participants physically deployed in a field location.

Although at the beginning, the essential objective of the exercise was not to test the tools proposed by Valkyries, after several contacts, the Spanish and Portuguese authorities agreed to use the biannual exercise they carry out in the area for this purpose. The main objective, which was to reduce voice communications, using various digital tools, and thus reduce the time it takes for victims to be attended and transferred to a hospital, was successfully achieved.

This document describes all the opportunities that have been tested in the simulation, the pre-testing and running of the simulation, and the evaluation of the solutions provided by Valkyries.

Figure 1 - VALKYRIES Use Cases

2. Identification

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3. Introduction

The VALKYRIES project aims to analyse the current state of protocols, nomenclatures, technologies, and procedures implemented by European first responders. The project proposes a series of pre-standardization and harmonization actions that would enable them to operate jointly in cross-border incidents. These harmonization proposals are implemented on a platform as reference integration. The validity of these proposals was demonstrated in the use case 1 (UC#1).

3.1. Justification

During the first phase of the project, the gaps and needs of end-users in multi-victim incidents (MCI) were analysed and a set of requirements was formulated. Subsequently, different technological tools, systems and equipment were suggested, as well as operational procedures and common practices and also the training and education system. Subsequently, opportunities for harmonisation and standardisation were developed. The results of this process are subject to evaluation and validation also through demonstrations. The tools and opportunities tested are described in more detail in chapter 9.

3.2. Requirements compliance matrix

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_BASE_T7.5_1	P2	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8	D7.5 D7.3	REQUIRED	Implemented. Report of UC (D7.5). Minimum operation
REQ_BASE_T7.5_2	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8	D7.5	REQUIRED	Implemented. Report of UC (D7.5). Legislation & agreements
REQ_BASE_T7.5_3	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-8	D7.5	REQUIRED	Implemented. Good practice in research
REQ_BASE_T7.5_4	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4	D7.5	REQUIRED	Implemented. Report of UC (D7.5). Safety and legal aspects
REQ_BASE_T7.5_5	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-10	D7.5 D7.3	RECOMMENDED	Implemented. Report of UC (D7.5). WHO validated survey
REQ_BASE_T7.5_6	P1	VALK-OBJ-4	D7.5	RECOMMENDED	Implemented. Report of UC (D7.5). Funding
REQ_BASE_T7.5_7	P1	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D7.5	RECOMMENDED	Implemented. Report of UC (D7.5). Action plan
REQ_COM_T7.5_1	P2	VALK-OBJ-1	D7.5 D7.3	RECOMMENDED	Implemented. Report of UC (D7.5). Small drills conducted
REQ_COM_T7.5_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	D7.5 D7.3	RECOMMENDED	Partially implemented. Report of UC (D7.5). Common methodology and evaluation

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
		VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9			
REQ_COM_T7.5_3	P2	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8	D7.5	RECOMMENDED	Implemented. Report of UC (D7.5). Implemented. Usability & usefulness survey
REQ_COM_T7.5_4	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8	D7.5	RECOMMENDED	Implemented. Report of UC (D7.5). Real-time information
REQ_COM_T7.5_5	P1	VALK-OBJ-5	D7.5 D7.3	RECOMMENDED	Implemented. Report of UC (D7.5). Profiles
REQ_COM_T7.5_6	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D7.5	RECOMMENDED	Implemented. Report if UC (D7.5). Agreements
REQ_COM_T7.5_7	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D7.5	RECOMMENDED	Implemented. Report if UC (D7.5). European scheduled drill
REQ_COM_T7.5_8	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D7.5	RECOMMENDED	Implemented. Report if UC (D7.5). General information of the drill
REQ_COM_T7.5_9	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D7.5	RECOMMENDED	Implemented. Report if UC (D7.5). Coordination information
REQ_COM_T7.5_10	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D7.5	RECOMMENDED	Implemented. Report if UC (D7.5). Planning information
REQ_COM_T7.5_11	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3	D7.5	RECOMMENDED	Implemented. Report if UC (D7.5). Evaluation resources

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
		VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9			
REQ_COM_T7.5_12	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8	-	RECOMMENDED	Not implemented in UC1 as it was executed ahead of schedule. Implemented in UC2 and UC3.

Table 1 – Requirements compliance matrix T7.5

4. Demonstration specification^[1]

4.1. References

- Project VALKYRIES, Number: 101020676 — Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters (Description of Action).
- Deliverables:
 - D7.1 Test beds and evaluation methodology
 - D7.2 Dataset management and benchmarking
 - D7.4 Benchmark integration and lessons learned
 - D7.3 System validation and evaluation
 - D2.10 Harmonization and standardization reports M12
 - D2.7 Definition of system requirements and demonstration use cases M12
 - D4.6 Opportunities for harmonization in the technology landscape for first responder response in multi-casualty disasters
 - D5.1 Overview of new operational and procedural opportunities for first responder response to multi-casualty disasters

4.2. General data^[RL2]

FULL NAME:	Cross-Border emergency intervention (Forest fire) Spain-Portugal
NICKNAME:	“FIRE SURPRISE”
SERIAL NUMBER:	001
LEVEL:	TACTICAL AND OPERATIONAL ON THE GROUND
FORM:	LIVEX
TYPE:	FX
DATES:	04 May 2023
AREA:	Fronteira Marvão (Portugal - Spain), PORTUGAL (GPS: 39° 21' 7.887" N, 7° 18' 26.3844" O)
OFFICER SCHEDULING AND CONDUCTING THE EXERCISE	Navid Behzadi. Medical Doctor, Investigation Leader SUMMA112.
EXERCISE DIRECTOR:	Navid Behzadi. Medical Doctor, Investigation Leader SUMMA112. Maria Soledad Delgado. Subdirector Emergency Coordination Centre 112 Extremadura. Juan Carlos Rojo. Director Emergency Coordination Centre 112 Extremadura. José Ribeiro District Commander of Emergency and Civil Protection of Alentejo, National Authority PC.
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	Alentejo, National Authority PC. Jose Rodriguez Gomez. Medical Coordinator Centre 112 Extremadura.	
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EVALUATION DIRECTOR:	Meritxell Bassols Tayeda. INDRA	
HOST INSTITUTION:	112 Extremadura. Civil Protection Portugal	
PARTICIPANTS:		INDRA TASSICA PARTICLE AREU BDI USN

Table 2 – UC1 General Data

5. Overall requirements

5.1. General framework

The outcomes of technological, procedural and collaborative streams will converge in the VALKYRIES reference integrated platform (SIGRUN), evaluation and demonstration actions.

The exercise will demonstrate the influence of current technological means of sharing and data collection on the smooth and more reliable development of activities in the field of emergency. This data collection and comparison would not have been possible without the earlier standardization of the most important data to be shared. This task is undoubtedly a challenge for most countries and their institutions. But offering the possibility of a better and faster way of working, breaking language and even procedural barriers.

The fire pushes for rapid and coordinated decision-making between the two countries, for the most efficient use of resources in an event that always overwhelms the Emergency Services. This exercise involves hospital activity as part of the process in minimizing disaster damage. Demonstrating how the flow of information from patients who are transferred, prepares health centres for a better management of their resources and distribution of victims.

5.2. Relation to other demonstrations

This is the first demonstrator realised in the Valkyries Project. The simulation exercise between Spain and Portugal is carried out every two years because of an European agreement that came about after the forest fires that ravage the region year after year, without respecting borders. It is therefore not a drill that has been devised ad-hoc for the testing of Valkyries tools. It is about simulating and exercising situations that have been occurring very frequently in recent years.

While the fire was completely simulated, the traffic accident was carried out as realistically as possible. The actors who played the patients were made up and instructed to show the pathological findings that corresponded to them. They were placed in two real accident vehicles. And the emergency services were activated in real time. Each of the first responders who took part did so according to protocol, as if they were acting in a real case. This allowed us to have an extremely strong demonstrative support to be able to test each of the tools. And to have extremely valuable feedback from the first responders who work in these situations on a daily basis.

In relation to other demonstrators, less simulation tools have been used and the focus has been on an incident with a prevailing health response.

6. Demonstration aims and objectives

6.1. Demonstration aim

Demonstrate by means of an almost real exercise, the tools and protocols proposed by the Valkyries project.

6.2. Demonstration objective

- EO1: Organize a FSX exercise to perform field tests of different operational factors for coordinated response of first responders to scenario "Fire Surprise"
- EO2: Execute intervention action/response of First responders based on outcome of FSX
- EO3: Provide extensive presentation of VALKYRIES system to First responders.
- EO4: Evaluate the systems of taking and sharing data of the incident.
- EO5: Provide emergency systems with a multi-casualty incident management tool in a large-scale exercise.
- EO6: Provide related First responders with outcomes of VALKYRIES system. Organize, conduct and evaluate intervention action/response of First responders using the benefits of VALKYRIES system in order tackle the scenario Fire Surprise.
- EO7: Evaluate the added value of VALKYRIES system as the tool of improvements of End user capabilities

6.3. Testing objectives

- TO1: Evaluate the digitisation tools proposed by the Valkyries project in order to reduce the time spent on voice communications.
- TO2: Evaluate the accuracy of an application for digitalizing triage process to correctly classify casualties in order of the severity of their injuries.
- TO3: Compare the time and performance of an "analogue" versus a "digital" triage solution.
- TO4: Evaluate the impact on a command and control of a digital decision support solution.

7. Operational scenario description

Use case 1 refers to a Cross-Border emergency intervention that represent a forest wildfire involving Spain and Portugal. A series of fire outbreaks is observed in a secluded area of significant ecological value in the proximity of the Spanish and Portuguese borders. Weather conditions are conducive for a rapid fire spread, with strong winds, low humidity and high temperatures prevailing for a long period of time. Given the low visibility on the road due to the dense smoke produced by the fire, an accident between a bus and several cars occurs. There are many injured and some dead inside the bus, and some more injured in the cars. A large number of ambulances is required for the provision of first aid to the victims, as well as effective collaboration between the different types of first responders arriving at the scene.

The forest fire scenario was computer simulated, due to the risks involved and because it is a protected area. The traffic accident scenario was carried out very close to the old customs office on the border between Spain and Portugal, between the municipalities of Valencia de Alcántara (Spain) and Marvão (Portugal).

Figure 2 - 3D reconstruction of the area, with the simulation scenario marked in red

In the vicinity of the building, a bus and a car collide due to low visibility because of smoke. The bus is full of passengers and due to the high energy released, many people are injured, some even die. In the car some injured people are trapped and have to be rescued.

This requires the involvement of first responders from all areas. First of all, security forces are responsible for protecting the accident site from further collisions and the flow of other vehicles. Secondly, fire-fighting forces, who must stabilise the vehicles, carry out manoeuvres to extract the injured from the trapped car, and extract them without further injury. They must extinguish the fire affecting the vehicles and secure the area to allow the entry of the medical team. And finally, medical staff who are responsible for the first medical triage and the most urgent life-saving measures, and assist with their evacuation to the medical station where they will receive further medical care and await evacuation to the hospital.

8. Concept of the demonstration

8.1. Phase I – Preparation

8.1.1. Planning Phase

Pre-exercise phase

The main aim of the scoping phase is to discuss and agree on the exercise purpose, scope and specific objectives. Ideally it should also clarify the target audience, expected outcomes, simulation exercise scenario, resources required/available, project leadership (exercise directors), project timeline, and budget. The agreements are captured in a concept note and signed off by the key stakeholders.

We conducted though different meetings and online contacts in order to define the definitive Full-Scale Exercise / Drill

Directors of both Civil Protection, 112 Emergency Services of Extremadura and Portugal and SUMMA 112 agreed to carry out an emergency drill within the framework of the bilateral agreement that requires drills to be carried out in cross-border areas.

Once the exercise management team was formed, the exercise director defined the project plan and the tasks required to build and implement the exercise.

The entire methodology in the preparation and development of the drill would be guided by the recommendations of the World Health Organization published in its WHO Simulation Exercise Manual.

Finally, on a meeting in Merida, Extremadura, October 27th 2022, UC-1 was defined:

Date of celebration:

Although it was initially planned for the summer months, it was necessary to advance the drill to early May due to the mobilization of resources displaced for the forest fire prevention campaign, which would not facilitate the participation of these people in the Drill in the summer months due to the risk of fires.

Finally the date was accorded on 4th of May 2023.

Celebration place:

In the area of the former border between Spain and Portugal (Fronteira Marvão) in Portugal.

Figure 3 – Celebration place

After studying the suitability of several existing alternatives in the Alentejo Natural Park, the exercise management team decided that the most ideal place to hold the drill would be on the N-521 right at the border post between Spain and Portugal.

They described that in the month of July, a series of storms with significant electrical equipment develop in the areas of Valencia de Alcántara and the Portalegre District, causing several outbreaks of fires on both sides of the border line due to lightning strikes in the area.

Furthermore, during the course of the extinction efforts, near the border, a bus accident occurred in which several people were injured and trapped.

Figure 4 – Google maps location ¹

In the next step, the participants were identified, defined within their areas of competence, depending on the purpose, scope and objectives of the exercise. The participants were facilitated in two group, could be separated into smaller focus groups (within Spain and Portugal group).

Control/ Coordination	Emergency Service	Alert the population
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency early detection and early warning. • Control of fake news. • Early activation of local, state and supranational civil protection plans. • Establishment of an advanced command post. • Establishment of efficient and autonomous communications. • Incident mapping • Safety/Security • Logistics • Management of the flow of information and press 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous teams working synchronously. • Standardized and harmonized data collection • Primary and secondary triage • Initial and advanced stabilization of the incident and victims. • Effective and efficient evacuation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mass Media Communication • Detection and control of fake news

Table 3 – UC1 main groups

¹ <https://goo.gl/maps/q6vwlDqXEaeuuPVN7> Coord: 39°21'7.39"N 7°18'25.95"W

ORGANIZATION	SUMMA 112	EXTREMADURA EMERGENCY					PORTUGAL EMERGENCY				
		CIVIL DEFENCE	FIREMEN	Health Service	HOSPITAL	POLICE GUARDIA CIVIL	CIVIL DEFENCE	FIREMEN	Health Service	HOSPITAL EVORA	POLICE
LEADER	Yes	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PLANNING	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
SAFETY	-	-	-	-	-	Yes	-	-	-	-	Yes
HELP / SAFETY	-	Yes	Yes	-	-	-	Yes	Yes	-	-	-
HEALTHCARE	-	-	-	Yes	-	-	-	-	Yes	-	-
MEDICAL TRANSPORT	-	-	-	Yes	-	-	-	-	Yes	-	-
HOSPITAL ATTENTION	-	-	-	-	Yes	-	-	-	-	Yes	-

Table 4 – UC1 focus groups

SPAIN GROUP*INTERVENTION GROUP:*

FIRE SECTOR: (Risk recognition and evaluation, Fire attack)

INFOEX: 3 teams. CGIF Activation. 1 Regional Coordinator, 1 AMN (20 person, 2 trucks, 1 car, 1 Command Post) It was included fire helicopter INFOEX plan.

CPEI: 5 firefighter y 1 official firefight. A fire-truck.

SEPEI: 10 person (2 command and 8 firefighter). 2 rescue vehicles and a car.

Military Emergency Unit (UME): 1 unit team and 3 vehicles. UME is a Spain Military Unit specialized in emergency situations that operates through the national territory or at the request of International Assistance and Cooperation with extensive training and experience in emergency and disasters.

Fireman Chief: Regional Coordinator Plan INFOEX.

ACCIDENT AREA: Recognition and assessment of risks, research and rescue, establishment of intervention areas, relief and base

SEPEI y CPEI

Research and rescue team Chief: Head of Duty Fire and Rescue Department of Caceres Region.

SANITARY GROUP

FIRE SECTOR: (Preventive for responders. Assistance to injured people, triage, evacuation of injured people to hospital centres)

SES: Regional Health System. Professional Emergency medical system.

RED CROSS: Ambulance voluntaries system in coordination with Regional Health System

Coordinator of the health group in the fire: Head of Duty of Emergency Service

ACCIDENT SECTOR: (Evaluation, triage, assistance, evacuation of injured people to useful hospital centres.)

SES: Advance life support ambulances. Basic life support ambulances

RED CROSS: Basic life support ambulances. Advanced Health Post.

DYA: Basic life support ambulances

Coordinator of the health group in the accident: Head of Duty of Emergency Service

Group Leader: Health Sector Technician (Must be responsible for knowing the number of beds available in hospitals, number of ICU beds, control of triaged, assisted and transferred wounded). This responsibility is assumed by the Emergency Coordination Centre.

SECURITY GROUP:

FIRE SECTOR: (Access control, establishment of alternative routes, evacuation of populations)

CIVIL GUARD: Responsibility in Citizen Security and Traffic.

LOCAL and NATIONAL POLICE:

ACCIDENT SECTOR: (Access control, establishment of alternative routes, security in the intervention, relief and base areas). Incident Investigation

CIVIL GUARD: Citizen Security and Traffic. Incident Investigation

LOCAL AND NATIONAL POLICE:

Head of Group: Head of Operations of the Civil Guard of Extremadura or the highest-ranking officer on the spot.

LOGISTICS GROUP:

FIRE SECTOR: (Provisioning for those involved. Management of transport for evacuations. Search for shelter for evacuees. Assembly of shelters for evacuees. Accommodation forecast for those involved. Provisioning for evacuees.) Management of these actions in a simulated manner when evacuation is not carried out.

ACCIDENT SECTOR: (Search for a place to receive victims' families. Provisioning for relatives. Management of transportation to accompany relatives once the injured have been evacuated to hospitals)

CIVIL PROTECTION JUNTA DE EXTREMADURA SERVICE, RED CROSS and PC VOLUNTEER ASSOCIATIONS

Group Head: Head of Duty of the Civil Protection Service of the Government of Extremadura.

TECHNICAL SUPPORT GROUP:

FIRE SECTOR: (Contact with basic supply companies.)

ELECTRICAL COMPANIES: Iberdrola

TELECOMMUNICATIONS COMPANIES: Telefónica

ACCIDENT SECTOR: (Management of technical material that is required)

Group Leader: Technician of the Civil Protection Service of the Government of Extremadura.

PORTUGAL GROUP

After the declaration of the emergency, all the responsibility for acting on the Portuguese side falls on the Civil Protection system. The National Civil Protection Emergency Plan is an instrument to support civil protection operations in case of imminent or occurrence of a serious accident or catastrophe in Portugal Continental, with a view to enabling unity of direction for the actions to be developed, the technical and operational coordination of the resources to be committed and the adequacy of exceptional measures to be adopted. In accordance with what is defined in the Basic Law of Civil Protection, this Plan is classified as general, in terms of purpose, and as nationally, in terms of the geographic area of coverage. As a base structure, scalable throughout the occurrence, the PCNac is organized in the following cells:

- a) Command Cell (CECOM) – Responsible for assuming, through CONAC, the command of operations, in direct and permanent connection with the remaining PCNac cells, with civil protection and relief agents, with the area's reception or concentration of reinforcements and with those responsible for district-wide operations. CECOM is also responsible for providing the guardianship policy all operational information about the ongoing situation, namely through direct coordination with the person responsible for CCON. CECOM is headed by CONAC or its legal substitute and integrates the elements of direct support to it;
- b) Communications and Command Cell (CECOC) – It is responsible for ensuring the communications and the flow of operational information, functioning as the single point of entry and exit of information at PCNac level. It is cell is organized into distinct jobs, which are responsible communications (radio, telephone and others) and the dissemination of information by the remaining PCNac and CCON cells. CECOC is coordinated by a member of the ANPC and reports to CECOM;
- c) Planning and Operations Cell (CEPLO) – It is responsible for the permanent monitoring the operational situation, ensuring its analysis and corresponding presentation of action proposals. It is also up to CEPLO promote, in close coordination with CONAC, correct planning operational with a view to an adequate mobilization of national resources available to reinforce theaters of operations. CEPLO is coordinated by a member of the ANPC;
- d) Operational Response Cell (CEROP) – It is responsible for providing the operational support requested within the framework of response actions, being responsible for mobilising the necessary human and technical resources in the search and rescue domains, transport of victims, firefighting, intervention in chemical accidents and pre-hospital emergencies. CEROP is coordinated by an element of the ANPC. Depending on ongoing operations, other entities may be called into this Cell;
- e) Command Support Logistics Cell (CELAC). It is responsible for ensuring all logistical support to command structures. It must also ensure support logistics to the structures that make up the PCNac and CCON, namely in the regarding food, storage and furniture. CELAC is coordinated by an ANEPC member;
- f) Technological Resources Cell (CERTEC) – It is responsible for ensuring all support necessary for the proper functioning of emergency communications between the national, district and municipal levels, through the creation of networks dedicated communications and IT systems, always ensuring the necessary redundancy

In districts affected by the serious accident or catastrophe that determines the activation of the Plan, the constitution of a **District Command Post (PCDis)** is guaranteed, which ensures exclusive management of the district response to serious accidents or catastrophes and is responsible for managing all resources available in the district area and for management of reinforcement resources sent to it by the national

level. In this situation, the CDOS remain in operation to monitor remaining occurrences not directly resulting from the serious accident or catastrophe.

The PCDIs report operationally and permanently to the PCNac, constituting this sector. The PCDIs perform missions similar to those of the PCNac, but adapted to the reality and district size. They must also ensure the coordination with the respective CCOD and the Municipal Command Posts (PCMun).

The person responsible for coordinating the PCDIs is the District Operational Commander or their legal replacement.

In Our Drill this person was D. Jose Ribeiro, District Commander of Emergency and Civil Protection of Alentejo, National Authority PC.

In the Full Spain-Portugal drill they participated with the deployment of resources related to a disaster, deploying the District Command Post which included the participation of all the agents used in this area such as firefighters, police, emergency medical services and civil protection ambulances.

Figure 5 – Operational Command Post scheme²

² <https://prociv.gov.pt/pt/home/>

Entidade	Designação	Meios		
		CB / ANEPC / SMPC / APC / Entidade	Tipo meios	Operacionais
Autoridade Nacional Emergência e Proteção Civil	Estrutura Operacional	Comando Regional Alentejo	VCDT	2
		Comando Sub-regional Alto Alentejo	VCDT	2
		Comando Sub-regional Alentejo Central	VCDT	1
		Comando Sub-regional Alentejo Litoral	VCDT	1
	Apoyo Técnico	Chefe de Célula	VTPT	1
		Técnicos Superiores	VTPT	2
		Operadores de Telecomunicações	VCDC	4
Equipa combate a incêndios	Força Especial Proteção Civil	VLCI	5	
Análise e uso do fogo	Força Especial Proteção Civil	EAUF-02	2	
Corpos de Bombeiros	Equipa de Posto de Comando	CBV Portalegre	VCDT	1
		CBV Castelo de Vide	VCDT	2
		CBV Nisa	VCDT	1
		CBV Crato	VCDT	1
		CBV Arronches	VCDT	2
		CBV Monforte	VCDT	1
		CBV Marvão	VCDT	1
	Combate a incêndios rurais	CBV Portalegre	VFCI	5
		CBV Castelo de Vide	VFCI	5
		CBV Marvão	VFCI	5
	Salvamento e desencarceramento	CBV Portalegre	VSAE	6
		CBV Castelo de Vide	VSAT	6
		CBV Elvas	VCDT	2
	Ambulância de socorro	CBV Elvas	ABSC	2
		CBV Crato	ABSC	2
		CBV Arronches	ABSC	2
CBV Monforte		ABSC	2	
CBV Marvão		ABSC	2	
Guarda Nacional Republicana	Apoyo ao PCO / CCOS	Oficial Ligação CCOS	VTPT	1
	Segurança, controlo trânsito	Comando Territorial	VTPT	4
	Combate a incêndios rurais	Unidade Emergência de Proteção e Socorro	VLCI	4
INEM	Apoyo ao PCO / CCOS	Oficial Ligação CCOS	VTPT	1
	Emergência pré-hospitalar	Equipa INEM	VMER	2
Instituto Conservação Natureza e Florestas	Apoyo ao PCO / CCOS	EGFR - Oficial Ligação CCOS	VTPT	2
	Combate a incêndios rurais	Bombeiros Sapadores Florestais	VLCI	4
			VLCI	4
			VLCI	4
Máquina rastos e plataforma	Bombeiros Sapadores Florestais	MR + PLAT	2	
Cruz Vermelha Portuguesa	Apoyo ao PCO / CCOS	Oficial Ligação CCOS - Del. Portalegre	VTPT	1
	Ambulância de transporte	Delegação de Portalegre	VDTD	2
	Ambulância de transporte	Delegação de Portalegre	VDTD	2
Serviços Municipais de Proteção Civil	Coordenadores e Técnicos	SMPC Marvão	VTPT	2
	Coordenadores e Técnicos	SMPC Castelo Vide	VTPT	2
	Coordenadores e Técnicos	SMPC Arronches	VTPT	2
	Coordenadores e Técnicos	SMPC Portalegre	VTPT	2
	Coordenadores e Técnicos	SMPC Fronteira	VTPT	1
Outros Agentes de Proteção Civil e entidades com dever de cooperação	Apoyo ao PCO / CCOS, apoio diverso	ALTICE	VTPT	2
		Segurança Social	VTPT	2
		Infra-estruturas de Portugal	VTPT	2
		E-REDES	VTPT	2

Figure 6 – Participants in Portuguese side, according with Spain Groups

The representation of the Portugal National Health System was in the pre-hospital care with the INEM, which is the Medical Emergency System, and with health personnel from the Évora Hospital, who took charge of the entire hospital part of the drill, that is, the arrival of injured patients to the emergency room, hospital triage and initial care in the HOSPITAL PHASE.

8.1.2. Preliminary defining meeting

On April 17th, 2023, a meeting was held with all parties to finalize the assignment of roles and tasks, as well as the definition of victims, which were agreed upon to ensure that groups were homogeneous and that the injuries and findings had significance in subsequent studies.

Nº PACIENTE	PRIMER TRIAGE	SEGUNDO TRIAGE	SCORE TRTS	HALLAZGOS
1	1	1	11	QUEMADURAS DE 2º GRADO EN CARA, MUCOSA NASAL Y OROFARINGE.
2	1	1	9	QUEMADURAS DE 2º GRADO EN CUELLO, ABDOMEN Y AMBAS PIERNAS (> 25% SCTQ).
3	1	1	10	COLAPSO DEL HEMITÓRAX DERECHO EN LA INSPIRACIÓN. DEFORMIDAD DE MUSLO IZQUIERDO
4	1	1	11	ANISOCORIA (MIDRIASIS DERECHA). HERIDA CONTUSA EN ZONA FRONTAL
5	2	2	11	TAQUIPNEICA. ABRASIONES EN LAS MANOS.
6	2	1	10	SIGNOS DE TRAUMATISMO PÉLVICO, CON PELVIS INESTABLE
7	2	2	12	DEFORMIDAD DE LA PIERNA A NIVEL DEL DOLOR
8	2	2	12	QUEMADURAS DE 2º GRADO EN TÓRAX Y BRAZOS (ALREDEDOR DEL 18% SCTQ) IMPOTENCIA FUNCIONAL DEL TOBILLO DERECHO
9	2	2	12	DEFORMIDAD CON IMPOTENCIA FUNCIONAL DEL TERCIO MEDIO DEL MUSLO DERECHO
10	2	2	11	HERIDA EN MALEOLO PERONEAL CON IMPORTANTE DEFORMIDAD Y CREPITACIÓN
11	3	3	12	HERIDA CONTUSA SUPERFICIAL EN ZONA FRONTAL DERECHA
12	3	3	12	CONTUSIÓN Y EROSIONES EN AMBAS RODILLAS
13	3	3	12	EROSIONES EN CABEZA Y CARA, ALGUNAS CON PEQUEÑAS HEMORRAGIAS
14	3	3	12	HERIDA CONTUSA DE UNOS 4 CM EN LA CEJA IZQUIERDA
15	3	2	11	EROSIÓN Y HEMATOMA EN LA PARED COSTAL
16	3	3	12	EROSIONES EN CARA Y TÓRAX
17	3	3	12	EROSIÓN BRAZO IZQUIERDO
18	3	3	12	LACERACIÓN DE UNOS 10 CM EN EL BRAZO DERECHO
19	3	3	12	ABRASIONES DISPERSAS
20	3	3	12	HERIDA EN CUERO CABELLUDO (4 CM) Y EN BRAZO DERECHO (5 CM). ABRASIONES EN PIERNA.
21	0			
22	0			
23	0			
24	0			
25	0			

Figure 7 – Triage victims proposed

And finally, the participants were defined, and registered in records:

CÓD. VEHÍC. GEMMA	ORGANIZACIÓN	DUEÑO	ORIGEN	FUNCIONES / PAPEL QUE REPRESENTA	HORA SALIDA
HELI 5.1	SES	SES	MALPARTIDA DE CÁCERES	LAS SUYAS COMO HELICÓPTERO SANITARIO	10:20
UME 1.3 – SIMUL	SES	DYA	SAN VICENTE DE ALCÁNTARA	LAS DE LA UME 1.3 DE SAN VICENTE DE ALCÁNTARA	10:32
SVA 5.2 – SIMUL	SES	CRUZ ROJA	VALENCIA DE ALCÁNTARA	LAS DEL SVB 5.2 DE VALENCIA DE ALCÁNTARA	10:20
U 03 – SIMUL	SES	DYA	VALENCIA DE ALCÁNTARA	A1 DE URGENCIAS QUE RECOGE EQUIPO CS VALENCIA	10:20
U 04 – SIMUL	SES	DYA	VALENCIA DE ALCÁNTARA	A1 DE URGENCIAS	10:20
U 05 – SIMUL	SES	CRUZ ROJA	SAN VICENTE DE ALCÁNTARA	A1 DE URGENCIAS (¿CON EQUIPO CS SAN VICENTE?)	10:32
CRUZ ROJA SVA – 01	CRUZ ROJA	CRUZ ROJA	SAN VICENTE DE ALCÁNTARA	LAS DE UN SVA MEDICALIZADO	10:32
CRUZ ROJA SVA – 02	CRUZ ROJA	CRUZ ROJA	CÁCERES/BADAJOS/MONTIJO	SVA CON ENFERMERÍA	10:43
CRUZ ROJA SVB – 01	CRUZ ROJA	CRUZ ROJA	CÁCERES/BADAJOS/MONTIJO	SVB PARA EL INCENDIO (PODRÍAN IR AL ACC DESPUÉS)	09:45
CRUZ ROJA SVB – 02	CRUZ ROJA	CRUZ ROJA	CÁCERES/BADAJOS/MONTIJO	SVB 4X4 PARA EL INCENICIO (PODRÍA IR AL ACC DESPUÉS)	09:45
CRUZ ROJA SVB – 03	CRUZ ROJA	CRUZ ROJA	CÁCERES	LAS DE UN SVB	10:43
CRUZ ROJA SVB – 04	CRUZ ROJA	CRUZ ROJA	CÁCERES	LAS DE UN SVB	10:43

Cronas terrestres desde el lugar del simulacro a:

- HUB – Hospital Universitario de Badajoz, 94 km = **73 minutos**
- HUC – Hospital Universitario de Cáceres, 110 km = **82 minutos**
- HDM – Hospital de Mérida, 132 km = **95 minutos**

Tiempo de vuelo desde el lugar del simulacro a:

- HUB – Hospital Universitario de Badajoz, **15 minutos**
- HUC – Hospital Universitario de Cáceres, **19 minutos**
- HDM – Hospital de Mérida, **23 minutos**
- HDG – Hospital de Getafe (grandes quemados), **80 minutos**
- HDB – Hospital de Burgos (implante miembros amputados), **120 minutos**

Dotación de camas de cuidados intensivos	HUB – Hospital Universitario de Badajoz	3
	HUC – Hospital Universitario de Cáceres	3
	HDM – Hospital de Mérida	2

Figure 8 – Example of Emergency Sanitary record

And it was decided where to locate the resources

Figure 9 – Location of the assets

8.1.3. Final essays

In Final preparations, VALKYRIES conducted four preliminary Functional Exercise or Field Small Scale Exercise/Drill beforehand in order to ensure that all functionalities of the system are working in a proper manner and interoperability between the modules of the platform was achieved. The operational capacity of the overall system was thus tested and ensured.

The first two were contacts with the procedures and tools that continued to be improved and perfected. In these first exercises, what would be carried out in a large-scale simulation was tested on a small scale.

On March 28 and April 12, 2023, at the facilities of the Emergency Training Centre of the Community of Madrid (IFISE) with the organization of SUMMA112 professionals, the 2 small-scale drills were carried out, reproducing what would later be carried out in the border of Spain and Portugal emphasizing and taking into consideration:

- Evaluate the impact of the tool in decongesting telecommunications and optimizing the management of the chain of command in a multi-victim incident in cross-border countries.
- Develop, integrate and improve the immediate response to emergencies, particularly when it affects several countries.
- Integrate, record, distribute and share all essential basic information, the minimum set of data to optimize the management of multiple casualty incidents.

Previously, we defined the exercise tasks, in priority order, along with who is responsible and deadlines for completion. The two field Small Scale Exercise aim to develop, integrate and demonstrate capabilities that allow an improvement the command and control and the management of the incident. Traditionally, emergency teams in SUMMA112 from Spain use voice communication systems (through radios and mobile phones) and triage systems based on paper cards. The Valkyries solution has developed a computer tool that integrates and distributes all essential and basic information to the chain of command and control and develops the "Minimum Data Set" (MDS) to manage Multi Casualty Incident. This research within the exercise aims to evaluate the tool's impact on the relieve of telecommunications and

optimization of the management in MCI. An expert committee previously defined CMD. It included primary and secondary triage severity colour, age, sex, hemodynamic stability, type of pathology, assigned resources, and destination hospital. Two MCI drills were conducted with 50 emergency medical participants and six investigators. In each one, two groups were created: one that worked with the traditional system using voice communications and paper triage cards (analogue group) and one with the computer tool developed by the VP (digital group). The times of each communication were collected, as well as total incident management time, primary triage time, secondary triage time, and variables corresponding to MDS, taking into consideration the differences between the two groups. The Chain of Command and Control was established as follows: Triage Post (TP) - Advanced Sanitary Post (ASP) - Evacuation Post (EP) - Medical Command Post (MCP) - Incident Management Health Team (IMHT) of the Emergencies Coordinating Centre (ECC). Descriptive statistical analysis and hypothesis testing to compare variables between both groups. Valkyries project concluded that the digitization of information in MCI compared with analogic traditional system had the potential to provide essential information available in real-time, optimizing the management of the chain of command and control thanks to the reduction of communication congestion and total incident management time. The difference achieved in primary triage depends more on the severity of the injuries (severe and mild cases with red and green triage cards) than on the participant.

8.2. Phase II – Shaping – Technology and participants (intervention) preparation

Technology: 8 smartphones with the application for digitalizing triage process; Mobile phones and tetras for voice communications; Digital tools were used to perform C2 and global view of the demo.

Several simulation tools and scripting were developed, by the technological partners, to generate the digital scenarios to support the tests and simulacrum, including in the UC1. The simulation tools aimed to:

- Generate initial simulacrum scenarios (Actors, assets, users, entities, etc.)
- Simulation of tasks and actions;
- Simulation of victims;
- Simulation of asset;
- Simulation of actors (first responders);
- Simulation of ambulances and vehicles routes and victims' transportation.

Participants:

- *The Players*, who are practically the ones with active roles in exercise.

All have been mentioned in the previous section:

- a) Inhabitants of the area witnessing the fire and the accident.
- b) Injured in the road traffic accident (actors)
- c) Portuguese command and control
- d) Spanish command and control
- e) Portuguese Emergency Medical Services
- f) Spanish Emergency Medical Services
- g) Portuguese Fire Extinguishing Services
- h) Spanish Fire Extinguishing Services
- i) Portuguese Security Services
- j) Spanish Security Services

- k) Drill manager
- l) Persons responsible for timekeeping
- m) Logistics staff for all drill participants
- n) Medical staff for all drill participants
- o) Broadcaster
- *Solution providers* are technical or research providers of tools or methodologies who have the main responsibility of guaranteeing the smooth operation of tools and/or to confirm the relevance of the methodology/process with the scenario deployed. TASSICA, PARTICLE and INDRA had a relevance
- The *observers*, who spectate the exercise without being actively involved in the exercise and register information for our own purposes. SUMMA112, TASSICA, HUMU, BDI, ISEMI, AREU and USN.
- Other: Portuguese Authorities, Spanish Authorities, press and spectators.

8.3. Phase III – Conduct – LIVEX

8.3.1. Conducting the simulation exercise in the field

Around 400 individuals took part in the exercise. On the day of the drill, all participants involved gathered two hours prior to the start of the drill. The actors who were assigned to play the role of the victims were given makeup according to the provided script sheets. Additionally, they were provided with transparent envelopes containing vital sign indicators and details of the most important injuries.

<p>VÍCTIMA ESP-1 VARÓN de 61 AÑOS</p> <p>MUCOSA OROFARÍNGEA QUEMADA RESPIRACIÓN: 29 rpm SpO2: 90% aire ambiente TENSIÓN ART.: 180 / 70 mmHg FRECUENCIA CARDIACA: 120 lpm SCORE DE GLASGOW: 9 / 15</p> <p>HALLAZGOS: QUEMADURAS DE 2º GRADO EN CARA, MUCOSA NASAL Y OROFARINGE.</p> <p>(ET) TRIAJE SECUNDARIO</p>

Figure 10 – Example of a patient identification card with clinical findings

The computer equipment was successfully installed in the mobile command and control setup located near the designated accident simulation site. Subsequently, the communications equipment underwent thorough testing procedures. Specifically, the 4G mobile coverage was ensured to facilitate the seamless operation of the application for digitalization of triage process. To ensure effective communication, the

voice equipment underwent rigorous testing for both GSM and Tetra coverage. Furthermore, the batteries of all equipment were diligently inspected and verified to be in optimal working condition.

During the simulated emergency scenario, each triage and communications officer was assigned a dedicated timekeeper. The triage process involved the utilization of four triage officers, with two assigned to primary triage and two assigned to secondary triage. Specifically, one triage officer performed analogue triage, which entailed filling out the triage card and communicating the findings verbally via telephone or Tetra to the Coordinating Centre. The other triage officer conducted digital triage, utilizing a smartphone app to fill out and transmit the triage information.

To accurately capture and document the triage and network communication times, both the smartphone app and the Coordinating Centre app were equipped with automated recording capabilities. This ensured that every triage and communication activity was meticulously logged without the need for manual intervention.

The timekeepers were given explicit instructions regarding the specific times that needed to be recorded:

A) For both primary and secondary triage, the time recorded encompassed the duration from approaching the patient to the completion of writing the triage result on the triage card (for analogue triage) or sending the triage result via the application for digitalizing triage process.

B) In the case of communication activities, the recorded time spanned from the initiation of the conversation (including dialling the telephone number or pressing the Tetra push-to-talk button) to the conclusion of the conversation (such as hanging up or releasing the Tetra push-to-talk button).

C) For analogue triages, data collection was performed to capture information on the outcome of the triage process.

By adhering to these instructions and employing automated recording mechanisms, we were able to accurately document and analyse the triage and communication times throughout the emergency scenario.

Figure 12 –Diagram showing the distribution of timekeepers

In the conducted drill, a realistic accident scene was simulated using a bus from a scrapyards, along with two cars. To enhance the authenticity of the scenario, actors portraying the victims were strategically placed in each seat of the bus. The emergency response teams from Portugal were assigned to attend to the victims on one side of the scene, while the Spanish emergency services attended to those on the other side.

The simulation started at 9:30, beginning with the simulation of a forest fire and the initiation of emergency calls to alert the authorities. At 10:00, the accident itself was simulated, and in real-time, the emergency medical services were promptly notified to respond to the scene for the assessment and treatment of the victims.

The first ambulance arrived at 10:25, coinciding with the arrival of the first security service. Subsequently, a fire truck reached the scene at 10:30. Once the firefighters arrived, they swiftly initiated measures to secure the accident site. Meanwhile, the police services effectively managed access to the scene, ensuring the smooth flow of traffic for vehicles not involved in the drill.

The advanced life support ambulance teams immediately engaged in triage activities. Half of the team utilized their own usual triage cards, while the other half employed a triage application directly on the patients themselves. This enabled them to efficiently assess the patients in both the cars and the bus, performing primary triage. For those conducting analogue triage, communication of their findings, including the assigned colour code and triage card number for each patient, was facilitated through mobile phones or Tetra devices. This process was crucial for maintaining accurate patient traceability throughout the entire triage process.

Due to unforeseen weather conditions, the helicopter initially activated for victim assistance and evacuation was unable to reach the scene. However, an alternative mobile advanced life support unit was promptly activated at 10:25 and arrived at 10:47, ensuring the necessary medical support was available.

The collaborative efforts of the fire brigade and the incoming ambulances played a crucial role in establishing medical stations and providing assistance to the victims. With the assistance of additional ambulance staff and a logistics vehicle that arrived simultaneously, two field hospitals were set up. One field hospital catered to the less severe patients with green triage codes, while the other accommodated those with orange and red triage codes, forming the advanced medical post.

Subsequently, the injured individuals involved in the accident were evacuated from the vehicles and transported to the advanced medical post. Once a patient had undergone both digital and analogue triage assessments, they were identified for evacuation to the advanced medical station. Portable stretchers were utilized to move the patients from the accident site to the advanced medical post.

Upon arrival at the advanced medical post, health professionals adhered to the proposed protocol. At the entrance, the professionals verified the primary triage assignment given to each victim and allocated an appropriate stretcher within the advanced medical post. The responsible medical staff conducted a secondary assessment, providing initial care, which included ensuring the airway was clear and providing oxygenation if necessary. They also ensured the maintenance of proper circulation, performed neurological assessments, and evaluated injuries. Additionally, the necessary medication was administered as required.

Both the mobile application and the triage cards played a vital role in documenting the secondary triage and the care provided by the advanced medical post staff. Similar to the process in the car crash area, the professionals conducting analogue triage communicated the details of the care and the results of the

secondary triage to the coordinating centre through telephone or Tetra communication systems. These updates were simultaneously reflected on the triage cards themselves.

In accordance with secondary triage, evacuation priority was established, and according to this, as ambulances arrived, each patient was assigned according to priority. Essentially, serious patients should be evacuated earlier and less serious patients could be evacuated later. As soon as a patient boarded an ambulance, the triage application allowed the transfer to be recorded on the mobile terminal. Those performing the analogue process had to communicate via tetra or mobile phone and voice to the command and control the patient number, the ambulance and that the evacuation was proceeding.

Once the evacuation had been completed, the existing data at each of the stations was checked. It was found that in the analogue triage group there were some errors, the most serious of which was that 10 patients with a green classification (slight) had not been registered, and their data and injuries were lost for the whole process.

Figure 13 – Conducting the traffic accident simulation exercise

The mobile command and control post played a crucial role in centralizing information from both the victims and the fire-fighting and security forces. It consisted of different sections, each responsible for specific tasks.

Fire Brigade Section

The fire brigade section received information from personnel at the scene and relayed it to the command centre. This information helped the command centre make informed decisions and develop the best plan of action. If necessary, the fire brigade section would activate new personnel or redirect existing personnel to address the situation effectively.

Security and Civil Protection Section

The security and civil protection section was responsible for determining measures to warn the population and communicating them to the troops present in the area. These measures could include evacuating the population, advising them to stay in their homes, redirecting traffic, or identifying better access and evacuation routes for other emergency services. The section ensured that appropriate communication and coordination were maintained to protect and assist the affected population.

Health Section

The health commanders operated within the health section of the command-and-control centre. This section centralized all the information received, both through voice communication (analog triage system) and electronic means (digital triage process). By analysing this information, the health section could activate additional resources if needed and organize the evacuation of the injured based on their injuries and severity.

Evacuation Prioritization

A priority for evacuation was established from the advanced medical post. Later-arriving ambulances were dedicated to the evacuation process, transporting patients to hospitals based on the established priority. Each patient had a triage card indicating the required care, which accompanied them during the evacuation. The hospital receiving the patient would be contacted either by telephone or computer application to relay information about the patient's condition, injuries, and the time of initiation of evacuation.

The command and control post served as a central hub for coordinating efforts, analysing information, and making informed decisions to effectively respond to the emergency situation.

8.3.2. Incident Command and Control Post

After assessing the scene and initiating medical care, we established an incident command post which is a multi-sector control unit, comprised of representatives from all agencies responding to the scene.

In this location we accommodate all the Command and Control solutions, tools and communications related to the incident. It was established to coordinate various sectors involved in field management, link with supporting systems to provide all information and mobilize necessary resources, and supervise victim management.

There were two different sectors within the Command Post:

- **Incident Commander** (Command Post Coordinator), in this case, the Major of the Fire and Rescue Service, because the incident was an uncontrolled forest fire. The incident commander had overall responsibility for managing the incident. Established objectives, strategies and implemented tactics to control the fire. At first, he carried out the general coordination of field operations, received reports from the other commands of the post and coordinated between other sectors and with another Incident Command Post in Portugal.

Considering all the data received, because it had acquired large dimensions they decided to activate the Multiple Victim Plan (Extremadura Civil Protection Plan). Incident Commander Post was now called Operative Control Centre (CECOP). As it affects a cross-border, the cross-border plan was activated.

With the information obtained, resources were mobilized according to the scale of the disaster. Information on the resources estimated time of arrival is collected. Contact with the Portuguese CCOD District Command to alert. The Portuguese Coordination Centre received all the information related to the incident in the region bordering Spain and initiates the fire collaboration agreement (cross-border multi-casualty incident).

Really at this moment Command Post was established with a team leader from each of the intervening teams (fire brigade, security forces and medical personnel) and political representatives. It began to centralise the reception of information, taking operational decisions for each of the teams involved. All information by all teams is received in real-time.

- **Health Emergencies Coordination Centre:** Both in Spain and Portugal the Emergency System is operated through the single number 112. Fortunately, there is a cross-border agreement for the management of large incidents in the areas close to the border between the two countries. After the first data, the alert was provided to the two 112 coordination centres, which activated their resources according to the usual protocol.

When the resources arrived, they carried out the initial assessment, made the first decisions and began communications from the scene of the incident. The mobile Advanced Command Post was installed, in whose sector part of the health emergency personnel called the Incident management health team- IMHT, personal of Extremadura 112 Service, were incorporated. The main function of this work team was to centralize all the health information of the incident and the coordination of the intervening resources, as well as the coordination with the hospitals for the transfer of the injured patients. It also maintains direct communication with the Advanced Medical Post.

As previously mentioned, traditionally the emergency teams in Coordination Centres in Spain and Portugal use voice communication systems (via radios and telephones). The Valkyries solution has developed a software tool that integrates and distributes all essential and basic information to the chain of command and control, and develops the "Minimum Data Set" (MDS) to manage incidents with multiple victims. IMTH analogic team spent the entire incident working in the traditional way, as is done in their usual work, and another IMTH team, called digital or VALKYRIES team, used the tools and communications provided by VALKYRIES project.

The VALKYRIES solution and tools used cover all parts of the coordination process:

- Reception of initial information, with Methane Method
- Allocation of resources, mobilization and monitoring thereof.
- Information on the injured, after initial triage and evacuation triage.
- Assignment of evacuation resources
- Transfer of information to hospitals receiving injured people (hospital alert)
- Completion of the information process upon arrival at the hospital

In the conventional or traditional model, the Valkyries team did not perform any intervention. We recorded the model used in each emergency system (telephone/TETRA communication, yes/no triage cards, communication and monitoring of resources, etc.) and record the variables to be measured as individual and group triage time; speed of management of each patient and group; Traceability of patients by colour of Triage, time to assign the hospital.

In the Valkyries model, after receiving the basic information such as the call to 112, we start up all the tools such as an application for digitalizing triage process [AM3][CC4][MG5] to have a first situational awareness of the incident and carry out electronic triage; the GLOBAL COP gives us the dynamic situational awareness of the resources and perhaps the communication tool between the national / supranational command posts. iSafety helped us in the simulation of situations and casualties and perhaps in the communications tool and resource situation. Finally, we compared both systems having the variables initially defined as the individual / group triage time; speed of management of each patient / group of patients, time on phone calls/radio voice, time to assign the patient's receiving hospital.

On Extremadura side, another Post was deployed, where all the monitoring systems and tools were placed, to accommodate the authorities, people related to the project without a specific function, as well

as observers and Valkyries Technology Manager in this drill. From this position, surveillance and monitoring of the entire intervention could be carried out, mainly with SIGRUN tools.

Another of the most notable aspects of digitalization is the ability to share information at all levels of patient care in incidents with multiple victims, as well as their ge positioning, the injured person or the resource that transports them. Once the patient enters the system through a wearable device or through the application for digitalizing triage process, as in our case, and is tracked on command and control platforms, this shared information is available in real time, in all phases of medical care in a multiple casualty incident, even in the final phase of care which is the hospital. In this way, having the number of injured, severity and type of injuries, allows us to prepare for the reception and definitive management of patients, as well as logistical or personnel aspects and prepare material or operating rooms.

8.3.3. Hospital Phase. Hospital do Espírito Santo de Évora (HESE) activities and procedures

Alongside the actions taken and described in a) and b), HESE was in constant communication with the assigned authorities and in standby to receive information regarding the incident and victim information.

Regarding our response process, HESE had the following structure in place to harmonise proceedings:

- Crisis cabinet – in constant contact with on-site HESE healthcare professionals and Évora’s Civil Protection. This was the main point of contact for emergency response professionals, from which they received initial triage information and victim description;
- Urgent and Non-urgent units – HESE simulated emergency response units with two tents (see figures below) where victims were directed after primary and secondary triage from the corresponding teams. The goal was to simulate an emergency service receiving the victims during its normal workflow, to promote response under stress from the healthcare professionals involved. Among others, departments such as surgery block, psychology and psychiatry, imaging, blood bank, and ICU were involved in the Use Case execution;
- Communications Team and Board of Administration, to oversee the activity and to serve as response “back-up” in case more resources (equipment, outside help) were necessary.

Figure 14 – Non urgent care unit

Figure 15 –Urgent care unit

Regarding data collection and sharing, HESE conducted its triage processes with 3 solutions: HESE triage cards, commonly used and the most well-known by their healthcare professionals; TASSICA 3 Card, developed by the partner TASSICA and used with their agreement; and an application for digitalizing triage process, from which it was possible to extract digital data for further analysis.

Primary and secondary teams used the three triage solutions, where the main goal was to determine whether the proposed application simplified and saved time during the triage process. The overall feedback was positive.

After the exercise, all teams gathered and discussed the proceedings, shared feedback and proposed several ways to improve internal processes using the VALKYRIES exercise as baseline.

Figure 16 – Exercise wrap-up and feedback session

8.3.3.8.3.4. Closing the exercise

Each exercise ended with an immediate debrief also known as debriefing “hot wash”, which is a facilitated process conducted by the exercise manager. The focus of this first debrief is to allow everybody to decompress and to give participants the opportunity to provide their initial feedback on the exercise

The following day, on 5th May, a representative of the members of each participating group met to participate in a briefing on the main exercise or “cold debriefing”.

This debrief aims to review the exercise objectives with the participants, and capture feedback on achievements, challenges and critical gaps in plans, procedures, systems and training. The objectives and the methodology for the main debriefing would have been set in the planning phase, and the sessions included in the exercise agenda.

The debriefing captured what was learned by the participants and observed by the evaluators, and what can be brought forward as a recommendation to improve response capacity.

The exercise was closed at the end of the “cold debrief”. This was done formally as agreed with the partners. This session included a ceremony with authorities Portuguese in Castelo De Vide City Council.

8.4. Phase IV – Evaluation (Brief description of the approach (algorithm and methodology) for validation and testing of the VALKYRIES results

The Testbeds and Evaluation Methodology document (D7.1) describes the development and conceptual design of the testbed and system that was used in the four use cases of the Valkyries project, as well as the methodology for end-user validation of the harmonization opportunities, which were identified within the different work packages of the Valkyries project.

Additionally, document D7.3, System Validation and Evaluation, describes the effectiveness of VALKYRIES results according to the established validation and evaluation methodology.

9. VALKYRIES Integrated System

Valkyries project produced number of harmonization proposals and developed a platform as reference integration. Validity of selected ones was demonstrated in exercise based on Use Case 1. Brief description of tools used are described In [PSG6]D7.3 [3].

9.1. Global Technological Schema

This is the global schema for UC1 with the tools and command and Control configuration.

Figure 17 – Global schema for UC1

The tools used for UC1 were iSafety, SIGRUN, GLOBAL_COP, an application for digitalizing triage process, Tassica Triage Cards and Hybrid Twin Lab for simulation.

Two headquarters were deployed as command posts for VALKYRIES in both Spain and Portugal with global information provided by GLOBAL COP.

In the mobile command post, iSafety was deployed with a liaison command and control operator executing the manual actions of incident creation, mission creation and resource allocation and updating.

This command post received the global triage data (from both Spain and Portugal) through the GLOBAL COP casualty dashboard.

On the Portuguese side, mission creation and resource execution actions were simulated, but a command-and-control tool was not deployed.

The following elements were simulated in SIGRUN using the HTL simulation tool:

- Fire perimeter
- Vehicle geolocation (route simulation).
- Simulation of road closures (congestion).

For the traditional part, the available command and control tools were used and communications between the FRs were by radio and voice.

Figure 18 – C2 application used in UC1

In this figure we see more detail of the Command-and-Control applications that were used in UC1.

There is a part of information that is GLOBAL and shared and a part that is country specific.

Screenshots of the tools used during the UC1 for the execution of the exercise can be seen in Annex E.

10. Harmonization opportunities

10.1. WP4 harmonization opportunities

This section will provide an explanation of how the harmonisation of the opportunities assessed in UC1 has been carried out. A specific explanation of UC1 will be given.

The harmonization opportunities implemented for UC1 are the following

- **CO.WP4.15. Location of near/nearest vehicles**
- **CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges**
- **CO.WP4.21. Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms**

A detailed description is included in [PSG7]D7.3[3].

10.1.1. CO.WP4.15. Location of near/nearest vehicles [PSG8][Pe9]

This opportunity was harmonized to support the key functions of the system regarding the location of the actors within an MCI scenario.

This harmonized opportunity was validated in the UC1, addressing the following tests purposes:

- Validate the assets (vehicles) report of their location, its updating delay and the time elapsed from the reported position until the data is displayed.
- Validate the victims' report of their location, its updating delay and the time elapsed from the reported position until the data is displayed.
- Validate the First Responders reported location, its updating delay and the time elapsed from the reported position until the data is displayed.
- Record and display the assets, vehicle and victim historical track

Regarding the vehicles position two different demo scenarios were used, real data and simulated data. Real data was obtained from the mobile phones reporting its position through SIGRUN. With the assets and victims position displayed in the GLOBAL COP, decision-makers have a better situational awareness and can decide the transport allocation to each victim based, among other data, on the nearest assets.

In UC1 the First Responders and victims were tracked based on real-time data from mobile solution with GNSS capability. Their position was logged regularly in the SIGRUN system and displayed in the GLOBAL_COP and in the applications for digitalizing triage process.

For the simulated data, it was developed several tools to simulate:

- The ambulances and victims transport from the demo start point to the assigned destination.
- The vehicles route and its ETA;
- Vehicles transportation status

The real victims were assigned to vehicles (real or simulated) and transported to the destination, and all routes were recorded in the SIGRUN. The response and elapsed times were collected and recorded for validation against the defined KPI.

UC1 only involved land vehicles: fire brigades' vehicles, ambulances, water supply and Command truck. For a wider and a more complete stress test, several of the victims were simulated being transported to the HESE Hospital simultaneously at different time intervals and in an accelerated time clock (regular transportation would take around 2 hours). Once the simulated transported victim arrives at HESE, real

actors would take simulated victim role and the demo would continue. By performing this demo it was possible to validate the relevancy of an accurate vehicles ETA to the medical services in Hospital.

A simulation of a cross border victim transportation was also included in the demo, combining real and simulated data for the purpose of validating the SIGRUN.

All geographical data was stored and their historical data can be viewed in the GLOBL COP.

10.1.2. [CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges](#) [PSG10]

For UC1 the opportunity to reduce communication times was adjusted to the UC scenario. In the UC1 case, iSafety was deployed as a Command-and-Control (C2) tool in Spain in the mobile command post and from there the actions of incident creation, mission creation and vehicle status update were executed.

In parallel, the same actions were being executed with the conventional tools. In this case, radio and voice communications and Spain deployed his own command and control tool in parallel to Valkyries. No command-and-control tool was used in Portuguese side.

There was no integration with real systems and most elements were simulated. A liaison operator was used to enter manual data.

iSafety had a liaison operator in the Spanish side who was in contact with the operator who managed the resources with the traditional method, and they were introduced in SIGRUN through the iSafety interface in a manual manner.

The Command-and-Control application had no integration with the geolocation data of the vehicles and therefore no data was integrated in SIGRUN. In SIGRUN the data was simulated through the HLT tool (Hybrid Twin Labs). The status of the assets (on the way, on site, active) was introduced manually in SIGRUN.

In the Portuguese side all the tasks and assets update were created using a simulation tool.

In this case the interactions between FR/Field Operational Centre and HQ in terms of incident creation, mission creation, resource allocation was measured using the SIGRUN platform.

10.1.3. [CO.WP4.21. Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms](#) [PSG11]

This opportunity has an identical implementation and validation in the 3 UCs, therefore, it is described in [PG12]D7.3[3]

10.2. WP5 harmonization opportunities

In the context of WP5, this deliverable D7.5 includes the results of

- PRELIMINARY TESTS: designed and conducted to assess and verify that the proposed enabler works as designed and, in the judgement of the expert, is suitable for advancing the opportunity to which it relates.
- DEMONSTRATIONS CONDUCTED AT UC1: A set of selected procedures and solutions will be harmonised and deployed in the UC1 in the context of a cross-border disaster, where the results will be demonstrated.

All enablers derived from the work in WP5 have been pre-tested, and the following were also demonstrated in the UC1:

- **CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans: EU structured repository of emergency response plans**
- **CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response**
- **CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response**

The assessment of the enablers in the UC1 demonstrator was carried out through the collection of the information necessary to evaluate the MEs (mission success measures) and to determine whether or not the established KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) were met. These records were made:

- Manually: for those exercises developed outside the SIGRUN federated system, through a network of VALKYRIES' own evaluators.
- Automatically: for those exercises developed using the SIGRUN federated system, from the data stored in it.

A detailed description is included in [PSG13]D7.3[3]

10.3. WP6 harmonization opportunities

The selected opportunities were implemented in UC1

- **CO.WP6.2. Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data**

This opportunity has an identical implementation and validation in the 3 UCs. A detailed description is included in D7.3 [3][PSG14]

11. Validation and testing results – Analysis of results

The results of the tests carried out for each opportunity are detailed below. Both the preliminary tests and the tests performed at the time of the exercise are described. The detailed description of each test performed is described in the verification and validation document D7.3 [3] and the methodology in D7.1 [5].

In this section, the summary of the results obtained is reported and the analysis of these data is performed.

Annex F. WP4 Results, Annex G.WP5 Results, Annex H.WP6 Results reflect the results sheets and the evidence for the test performed for each WP.

11.1. Preliminary tests

Prior to the implementation of the UC, preliminary tests were carried out with the tools in the SIGRUN integration environment in the IFISE facilities on 28th March.

SUMMA 112's services portfolio includes attention to situations of multiple victims and catastrophes, with the direction of the medical command in the event that the incident involves the deployment of municipal and regional resources. For this reason, it regularly carries out small-scale (less than 20 simulated casualties) simulations of multiple-casualty incidents throughout the year to train its medical staff.

Figure 19 – Previous small drills conducted by SUMMA 112 prior to UC1

Four of the small-scale drills were conducted in preparation for the Use Case 1 drill. The primary objective was to test the analogue and digital triage system as it would later be used in UC1. Secondary objectives were to evaluate the difficulties of deploying the computer and technical equipment needed to set up the SIGRUN platform, to evaluate the time needed to train medical staff in the application for digitalizing triage process, to develop and evaluate the system for capturing the time and accuracy of each of the triages using timekeepers and observers, and to find the strengths and weaknesses of the system, and to find the strengths and areas for improvement of the eventual deployment to be developed during UC#1 to test Valkyries' tools and finally to present the project to the health authorities in order to involve them in the preparation and development of UC1.

For this purpose, several mobile phone and terminals with the application for digitalizing triage process were deployed for each of the interveners who were to handle primary and secondary triage at the health post. A computer was also deployed to simulate the computer installed in the command and control system, which would receive all the information, alongside the operators who would receive the same information by voice. They were selected from among the partners and the data collection system was taught. On the one hand, the times of each of the voice communications they made to the command and control were recorded. On the other hand, the patient tables filled in by the triage officers and those of command and control were collected to see communication failures, counting each of the errors in each of the patients attended. The errors were also classified as critical or minor.

As a result of the four small-scale simulations, data began to be collected on time and accuracy variables, as well as many strengths of using digital triage to reduce voice communications. The data collected was analysed and a series of conclusions were drawn from these pre-tests:

- a. Voice communications were dramatically reduced. In these situations, every triage result made by the health teams present in the disaster area must be communicated to command and control verbally. This involves a considerable number of calls (at least 1 for each casualty present, over 1 minute) with a non-negligible error rate (in fact, it requires the person receiving the call to confirm the data). In total, digital triage saved more than half an hour of verbal communication of information, with milliseconds used by the application to communicate and transmit the information to the existing computer station in command and control.
- b. The accuracy of the information increased considerably. Despite the fact that with every verbal information (by phone or tetra) must be confirmed with the receiver, there is a considerable error rate. In other words, the "picture" at each of the posts did not match 100%, and several critical errors were found.
- c. As a sum of the two above, there was a very significant improvement in the times of the officers who performed digital triage, compared to those who performed analogue triage. This allowed them to finish the simulation (i.e. complete the transfer of all patients to the corresponding hospitals) almost half an hour earlier than their colleagues who used the usual way (analogue triage and verbal communications).

The application for digitalizing triage process proved to be a very important strength in helping the intervening healthcare teams to improve the accuracy and time to care for the victims. Some difficulties were also found in the interface that would be solved for the UC1 simulation.

In conclusion, the small-scale simulations conducted by SUMMA 112 in preparation for the Use Case 1 drill yielded valuable insights and conclusions regarding the implementation of the digital triage system. The primary objective of testing the analogue and digital triage system was successfully achieved, along with several secondary objectives.

11.2. WP4 Results

11.2.1. CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles

11.2.1.1. Preliminary tests results

The preliminary tests were designed and performed prior to the Project demonstrators (UCs) to evaluate and verify that VALKYRIES solution provides the location data of the vehicles and supports their updating

position while simultaneously distribute it to the different users that require such info, namely the GLOBAL_COP. The actual position of the victims and personnel was provided by the mobile phones, as well as the vehicles equipped with a mobile application.

This deliverable D7.5 (Use case report 1: Spain-Portugal) includes the results of the preliminary tests carried out before the UC1.

The functions were tested firstly in test environment (remotely with simulating tools) and after in small drills performed such as SUMMA112. In these tests and drills the location functions were successfully tested.

Figure 20 – Example of the location of an ambulance during simulated remote tests

The drill in SUMMA 112, a mix between real and simulated entities was used (assets / vehicles / victims), and their location was either simulated or real. The first were generated through simulation tools, the second through the use of GPS coordinated collected from a mobile phone application.

In the drills and test sessions performed, the location of the vehicles and its status was used to assign an ambulance to a victim in need of transportation to a medical service / hospital.

Figure 21 – Example of the Vehicles and First Responders location from SUMMA 112 drill

Vehicles and ambulances assigned to specific tasks and location were tracked through the GLOBAL_COP, displaying their position and historical route, and the victims' position and route also tracked.

Figure 22 – Example of the Vehicles tracking / location from tests performed

By tracking the position of vehicles enabled the estimation of the time to destination (ETA – Estimated Time of Arrival) used by the hospitals to timely prepare the medical response to the arriving victims.

The results of having the vehicles and victims’ position and location were that it enabled a faster assignment and decision making by the incident manager, and hospitals are better prepared at time the victims arrived.

During the test all the features were validated, and any issues or limitation found were improved and corrected in the following sequence of tests and drills.

11.2.1.2. UC1 Results

TEST - 01	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP4-15-T01- Location of Nearest Vehicles	The system MUST be able to generate an updated vehicles position picture that support the Operational Command to make better time dependent victims evacuation decisions	KPI 1: Information available	Yes (vehicles position was received at the GLOBAL_COP) => Success
		KPI 2: Updated position of vehicles	Updated vehicles Position at SIGRUN: average < 1 minute => Success
		KPI 3: time elapses	Time to display the information of vehicle position: average < 1 minute. => Success

Table 5 – UC1 results for CO.WP4.15

11.2.2. CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges

Several tests and verifications were performed prior to the UC1 related to the WP4 opportunity. They were carried out to verify the integration and check the consistency of the data prior to integration. UC and have been documented in “Annex E. WP4 Results”. All of them were performed remotely except for the global previous demo that was performed in Madrid mentioned above.

Id	Start	End	Event	Mission	Agency	Task	Vehicle	Agency	Vehicle	Agency	Vehicle		
4	09:40	09:40	Incidente de Fuego Portugal	N/A									
5	09:45	09:50		Misión 1	AMPHIACION	AMPHIACION INFOEX	N/A	INFOEX	VEHICULO 1	VEHICULO 2	CGIF		
6	09:45	09:55		Misión 3	Medical Support	Preventivo Sanitario	Task A	Cruz Roja	AMB SIM1	AMB SIM 2	AMB1	AMB2	
7	10:00	10:00		Misión 4	Control	Activación PMA 112	N/A	112	CAMION				
8	10:05	10:05		Misión 5	Control	Activación de la UME y motobomba al lugar del incendio	N/A	UME	PMA	LEON101	AUTOBOMBA	AUTOBOMR	AUTOBOMBA3
9	10:05	10:05		Misión 6	Scouting Miscal	Incendio	Task D	UME	PICKUPSIM	AUTOBOMBA SIM1			
10	10:20	10:20	Accidente de tráfico	18°21'2.11"N 7°18'22.16"W									
11	10:20	10:25		Misión 1	Medical Support	Activación SLS/Task B	Task B	SLS	AMB SIM4	AMB SIM5	AMB6		
12	10:20	10:30		Misión 2	Traffic out	Corte carretera real	Task E	Guardia Civil	VEHICULO 1	VEHICULO 2			
13	10:41	10:46	CREACION DEL PSA	Misión 3	Medical Support	ambulancias	N/A	Cruz Roja	AMB6	AMB7	AMB8	AMB9	
14	10:50	10:50		Misión 4	Traffic out	Corte simulado	Task F	Guardia Civil	VEHICULO 3	VEHICULO4	VIR1	VIR2	
15	10:50	10:50		Misión 5	Medical Support	Envío de ambulancia al hospital	Task C	Cruz Roja	AMB1				

Table 6 – List of events, missions and agencies in UC1

In the table we see the entire list of events, missions and agencies that were the basis for the execution of the scenario for UC1. The table was used during the previous tests and during the demonstration as an execution guide.

11.2.2.1. UC1 Results

The following is a summary of the test results related to the opportunity to reduce voice communication. These tests were performed with the API/URL and UC1 data:[BM15]

TEST - 01	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP4-42-D02- Reduce Voice Communication	First responders' device/wearables must can communicate with SIGRUN by using HTTPs requests	KPI 1: Adequacy: 100% messages are encrypted.	The result of this test is the verification that the trace obtained during the demonstration is indeed encrypted and the time is less than 10ms.
		KPI 2: Penalties in execution time: less than 10ms	

Table 7 – Results for CO-WP4-42-D02 test 01

TEST - 02	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP4-42-D03- Reduce Voice Communication	SIGRUN uses token for authorisation, therefore, the HTTPs requests sent must have a valid token on the header.	KPI 1: Adequacy: 100% requests are authenticated by a valid token.	The result obtained is that the device without an authentication token was unable to communicate with SIGRUN as it did not have a token and was not allowed access, while the other device was allowed access.
		KPI 2: Data security: All data will be logged encrypted in a secure blockchain network.	

Table 8 – Results for CO-WP4-42-D03 test 02

TEST - 03	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP4-42-D04-Reduce Voice Communication	Each application would have to map their internal roles into the SIGRUN roles of the architecture	KPI 1: Adequacy: 100%.	[BM16]The result of this test is that several roles have been found, including administered, user and data entry device among others.

Table 9 – Results for CO-WP4-42-D04 test 03

TEST - 04	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP4-42-D05-Reduce Voice Communication	The SIGRUN platform must be capable of acquiring multidomain data, such as, first responses in different countries, and integrate it the same platform. Moreover, the information interchanged in the communication must be encrypted.	KPI 1: Adequacy: 100% messages.	[BM17]The result of this test is that SIGRUN is capable of handling multidomain data, and the time is less than 10ms. In the database of SIGRUN, it has been found data from different countries and information from different domains, e.g., fire, locations, triage of victims, etc.
		KPI 2: Penalties in execution time: less than 10ms	

Table 10 – Results for CO-WP4-42-D05 test 04

Final results sheets with all the results are included in Annex F.

TEST	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP4-42-T03-Reduce Voice Communication	The test consists of verifying that the information update from SIGRUN is updated in real time in the Platform and the information is updated according to the central Database.	KPI 1: Time elapsed (since Incident is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database)	37,442 s
		KPI 2: Time elapsed (since task is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database)	0,313 s
		KPI 3: Time elapsed (since asset is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database)	4,843 s

Table 11 – Results for CO-WP4-42-T03

The general criteria for the KPI is as follows

- < 60 sec | 100% success
- Between 60 and 90 sec | 50% success

- Between 90 to 120 sec | 25% success
- > 120 sec | 0% success

As we can see the results for CO-WP4-42-T03 are very positive for this initial UC and the centralisation and digitisation of the data with the SIGRUN platform provides information in real time with a standard communications environment.

Final results sheets with all the results are included in “Annex E. WP4 Results”

11.2.3. CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms

11.2.3.1. Preliminary tests results

The historical data analysis from the missions and platform opportunity is based on the collection of information from UC1 between Spain and Portugal, in particular, this use case is characterised by the generation of real data and simulated data. The real data have been added as the simulation took place, i.e. when a triage was carried out, for example. The simulated data was added automatically as the exercise progressed, i.e. the generation of vehicles and some of their locations and the spread of the fire throughout the territory, since it did not exist. The types of data collected by this simulation are quite diverse, thus generating a large amount of data to create the dataset. The dataset of the chaos of use 1 is composed of 15437 samples between real and simulated, these are composed of triages, vehicles, transfers of people, incidents and others. The dataset obtained represents very well how the simulation went from the beginning to the end. Thanks to it, it has been possible to carry out various analyses and create models that can be analysed in more detail in deliverable D7.2.

11.2.3.2. UC1 Results

TEST - 01	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP4-21-01- Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	SIGRUN must be capable of integrating data from multiples sources, such as, specific data for each first responder during an emergency, allowing to analyse the data to create a trained model.	KPI 1: Adequacy: 90%	<i>Different data processing techniques have been applied to obtain the most important features, and then three Machine Learning models have been generated. The first one consists of predicting the second triage based on the data obtained in the first one. The second model predicts the patient's death after the first triage. The last model predicts the patient's worsening after the first triage. All information about the processing techniques and the generated models can be found in D.7.2.</i>
		KPI 2: Penalties in execution time: 5000 ms	

Table 12 – Results for CO-WP4-21 in UC1

Final results sheets with all the results are included in Annex F.

11.3. WP5 Results

See full results in Annex G – WP5 Result sheets opportunities

11.3.1. Preliminary tests results

The preliminary tests are designed and performed prior to the Project demonstrators (UCs) to evaluate and verify that the enablers proposed by VALKYRIES are working as designed and, in the expert's opinion,

are adequate to advance the opportunity to which each of them relates. This allows deviations or errors to be identified and corrected, and performance to be improved.

All the harmonisation opportunities identified in VALKYRIES' WP5 have been verified by preliminary tests. Details of the methodology and design of the preliminary tests carried out can be found in Deliverable D7.3.

This deliverable D7.5 (Use case report 1: Spain-Portugal) also includes the results of the preliminary tests carried out before the UC1.

11.3.1.1. CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

CO-WP5-1-T01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: PRELIMINARY TEST			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
1. Importance	Low / High	KPI 1: Identify at least 5 problems/areas for improvement (P/AI) rated as low or high importance.	Functional test
2. Frequency	Low / High	KPI 2: More than 65% of the detected P/AI rated as LOW frequency.	Functional test
3. Persistence	Low / High	KPI 3: More than 65% of detected P/AI rated as LOW persistence.	Functional test
Verification action #1	Date and location	Madrid and Segovia (Spain), March 2023	
	Participants	TASSICA researchers involved in the VALKYRIES project	
	Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI 1: Importance: detected 9 problems/areas of improvement (P/AI) (5 rated as HIGH importance and 4 as LOW importance) (ACHIEVED) KPI 2: Frequency: 77,8% of the detected P/AI rated as LOW frequency (ACHIEVED) KPI 3: Persistence: 100% of detected P/AI rated as LOW persistence (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A, maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs).	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	

Table 13 – Results sheet CO.WP5-1-T01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

Annex G – WP5 Result sheets opportunities

 11.3.1.2. *CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans*

CO-WP5-2-T01 - EU structured repository of emergency response plans: TEST			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
1. Importance	Low / High	KPI 1: Identify at least 5 problems/areas for improvement (P/AI) rated as low or high importance.	Functional test
2. Frequency	Low / High	KPI 2: More than 65% of the detected P/AI rated as LOW frequency.	Functional test
3. Persistence	Low / High	KPI 3: More than 65% of detected P/AI rated as LOW persistence.	Functional test
Verification action #1	Date and location	Madrid and Segovia (Spain), March 2023	
	Participants	TASSICA researchers involved in the VALKYRIES project	
	Analysis	<p>The following is a compilation of usability problem scenarios indicating location, description and estimation detected after a cognitive walkthrough:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1.1 Create a new plan: When creating a plan, some items such as ON SCENE LIAISON COMMAND or ON SCENE COMMUNICATIONS AND MEDIA COMMAND do not appear in the plan as such at the scene level, but at the general or management level. As well as PLAN TRAINING or PLAN REVIEW. They are retained because they may appear in some plan., Frequency: Low; Importance: Low; Persistence: Low 1.1.2 Create a new plan: When creating a plan, the item "ON SCENE UNIFIED COMMAND" raises questions. It can be understood to refer to the same thing as "UNIFIED ADVANCED COMMAND POST", since the ACP designates the agency and the person in command of the ACP., Frequency: Low; Importance: Low; Persistence: High 1.1.3 Create a new plan: Some designations do not conform to the glossary, Frequency: Low; Importance: High; Persistence: High 1.3.1 Assigning agencies involved in an existing scheme: Agencies must already be created in order to be assigned, it may be necessary to indicate a direct access link to the creation of agencies., Frequency: Low; Importance: Low; Persistence: Low 1.2.1 Create a new agency: It may be necessary for the user to be able to create agencies, and not just the administrator., Frequency: Low; Importance: High; Persistence: Low 	

CO-WP5-2-T01 - EU structured repository of emergency response plans: TEST		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1.6.1 Duplicate a plan item: When identifying the duplicate item from the original, doubts may arise. It may be necessary to mark the duplicate with (Copy) or similar., Frequency: Low; Importance: Low; Persistence: Low
	Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI 1: Importance: detected 6 problems/areas of improvement (P/AI) (all of them rated as LOW importance) (ACHIEVED) KPI 2: Frequency: 66,7% of the detected P/AI rated as LOW frequency (ACHIEVED) KPI 3: Persistence: 66,7% of detected P/AI rated as LOW persistence (ACHIEVED)
	Quality	A, maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs).
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 14 – Results sheet CO.WP5-2-T01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex G – WP5 Result sheets opportunities

11.3.1.3. CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

CO.WP5-7-1 Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level

CO.WP5-7-T01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: PRELIMINARY TEST			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Relevance: Degree of importance attached to the use of a common classification and coding of victim priorities in a MCI.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Functional test
Stakeholder coding agreement: The level of agreement among first responders on the proposed MCI triage categories.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Functional test

CO.WP5-7-T01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: PRELIMINARY TEST			
Stakeholder tagging agreement: The level of agreement among first responders on the proposed MCI colour tagging code for victims in MCI and disasters.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Functional test
Cross-border cooperation improvement : The perceived improvement in cross-border cooperation between EMS when using a standardised classification and coding system.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 4: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Functional test
Verification action #1	Date and location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instituto Superior de Estudios Profesionales (ISEP) CEU. Castellón (Spain). 27 to 29 March 2023. • Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE). Madrid (Spain). 28 March 2023. 	
	Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students of the ISEP CEU's Ciclo Formativo de Grado Medio Técnico en Emergencias Sanitarias. • Doctors, Nurses and Emergency Medical Technicians of the Servicio de Urgencias Médicas SUMMA 112 of Madrid (Spain). 	
	Analysis and results	<p>a) FIRST RESPONDERS WITH EXPERTISE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Relevance: 95,24% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Stakeholder coding agreement: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Stakeholder tagging agreement: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Cross-border cooperation improvement: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) <p>b) FIRST RESPONDERS IN TRAINING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Relevance: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) 	

CO.WP5-7-T01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: PRELIMINARY TEST		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 2: Stakeholder coding agreement: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Stakeholder tagging agreement: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Cross-border cooperation improvement: 100,00% (ACHIEVED)
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 15 – Results sheet CO.WP5-7-1-T01

Evidence of implementation and compliance

See Annex G – WP5 Result sheets opportunities

CO.WP5-7-2 TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims’ information register and traceability in MCI and disasters

CO-WP5-7-2-T01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Inter-rater reliability: The consistency in triage decisions among different first responders using the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Decision-making confidence: improvement in healthcare staff confidence in making triage decisions using the TASSICA triage card, as measured by self-reported score.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Traceability: the extent to	Score from 1 (VERY	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception	<i>Functional test</i>

CO-WP5-7-2-T01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST

which the card helps to improve the traceability of victims throughout the chain of care at the scene of an MCI.	LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	of at least 80% by stakeholders.	
Victim information completeness and accuracy: degree of ease of recording complete and accurate victim information using the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 4: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
First responder wellbeing: The degree to which the card helps the first responder in their care tasks and reduces their stress during operations.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 5: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Task execution efficiency: The reduction in time taken to perform tasks in an MCI compared to using other options, as perceived by	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 6: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>

CO-WP5-7-2-T01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST			
first responders.			
Collaboration efficiency: The improvement in cross-border EMS collaboration, to coordinate and perform joint tasks using the TASSICA triage card, as perceived by first responders	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 7: Collaboration efficiency: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Overall satisfaction: The overall satisfaction of first responders with the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 8: Overall satisfaction with the TASSICA 3 triage card enabler. A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Verification action #1	Data and location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instituto Superior de Estudios Profesionales (ISEP) CEU. Castellón (Spain). 27 to 29 March 2023. • Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE). Madrid (Spain). 28 March 2023. 	
	Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students of the ISEP CEU's Ciclo Formativo de Grado Medio Técnico en Emergencias Sanitarias. • Doctors, Nurses and Emergency Medical Technicians of the Servicio de Urgencias Médicas SUMMA 112 of Madrid (Spain). 	
	Analysis and results	<p>a) FIRST RESPONDERS WITH EXPERTISE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Inter-rater reliability: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Decision-making confidence: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Traceability: 90,48% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Victim information completeness and accuracy:95,24% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 5: First responder wellbeing: 90,48% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Task execution efficiency: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Victim information completeness and accuracy: 95,24% (ACHIEVED) 	

CO-WP5-7-2-T01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 8: First responder wellbeing: 90,48% (ACHIEVED) <p>b) FIRST RESPONDERS IN TRAINING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Inter-rater reliability: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Decision-making confidence: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Traceability: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Victim information completeness and accuracy: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 5: First responder wellbeing: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Task execution efficiency: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Task execution efficiency: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Task execution efficiency: 100,00% (ACHIEVED)
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 16 – Results sheet CO.WP5-7-2-T01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex G – WP5 Result sheets opportunities

11.3.1.4. *CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response*

CO-WP5-12-T01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Data relevance: The perceived relevance of the data exchanged during the trial for proper management of casualties by EMS in an MCI or disaster.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders	<i>Functional test</i>
Data usefulness: The perceived usefulness of the exchanged	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY	A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders	<i>Functional test</i>

CO-WP5-12-T01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST			
data in the performance of care tasks by first responders.	HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).		
Verification action #1	Date and location	Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE). Madrid (Spain). 28 March 2023.	
	Participants	Doctors, Nurses and Emergency Medical Technicians of the Servicio de Urgencias Médicas (SUMMA 112) of Madrid (Spain), and researchers from the VALKYRIES Consortium.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Data usefulness: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	

Table 17 – Results sheet CO.WP5-12-T01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex G – WP5 Result sheets opportunities

11.3.1.5. CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

CO.WP5-13-T01 - SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Information exchange facilitation: The perceived improvement in information exchange between services using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Task execution efficiency: The perceived improvement in the efficiency of task execution in an MCI using SIGRUN	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>

CO.WP5-13-T01 - SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST			
compared to the current situation.			
Integration and cooperation: The perceived improvement in integration and cooperation with other services and/or procedures in responding to an MCI using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Implementation ease: The perceived ease and simplicity of implementing SIGRUN by first responders in an MCI.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 4: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
First responder well-being: The perceived improvement in the well-being of first responders during their operational tasks in an MCI using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 5: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Added value in cross-border MCI management: The perceived added value of using	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH /	KPI 6: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>

CO.WP5-13-T01 - SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST			
SIGRUN for managing and responding to an MCI affecting several communities or countries.	TOTALLY AGREED).		
Satisfaction with information content: The overall satisfaction with the content of the information exchanged using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 7: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Satisfaction with the operational procedure: The degree of satisfaction with the operational procedure implemented and based on the capabilities offered by SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 8: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Verification action #1	Date and location	Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE). Madrid (Spain). 28 March 2023.	
	Participants	Doctors, Nurses and Emergency Medical Technicians of the Servicio de Urgencias Médicas (SUMMA 112) of Madrid (Spain), and researchers from the VALKYRIES Consortium.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Information exchange facilitation: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Task execution efficiency: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Integration and cooperation: 96,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Implementation ease: 96,00% (ACHIEVED) 	

CO.WP5-13-T01 - SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 5: First responder well-being: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Added value in cross-border MCI management: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Satisfaction with information content: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Satisfaction with the operational procedure: 100,00% (ACHIEVED)
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 18 – Results sheet CO.WP5-13-T01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex G – WP5 Result sheets opportunities

11.3.1.6. *CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response*

CO.WP5-3-T01 Adoption of the METHANE model for sharing the essential incident data between emergency services in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Data relevance: Perceived importance of the data exchanged in the initial alert of a MCI or disaster to facilitate an efficient and effective emergency response.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: Data relevance: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Data usefulness: The perceived usefulness of the data exchanged during the drill in the initial alert to facilitate an efficient and effective emergency response.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: Data relevance: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>

CO.WP5-3-T01 Adoption of the METHANE model for sharing the essential incident data between emergency services in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST		
Verification action #1	Date and location	Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE). Madrid (Spain). 28 March 2023.
	Participants	Doctors, Nurses and Emergency Medical Technicians of the Servicio de Urgencias Médicas (SUMMA 112) of Madrid (Spain), and researchers from the VALKYRIES Consortium.
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: 100,00% • KPI 2: Data usefulness: 100,00%
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 19 – Results sheet CO.WP5-3-T01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex G – WP5 Result sheets opportunities

11.3.2. Demonstration results

11.3.2.1. CO-WP5-2-D01 - EU structured repository of emergency response plans: DEMONSTRATION

CO-WP5-2-D01 - EU structured repository of emergency response plans: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Availability	YES/NO (compliance = success).	KPI 1: Availability: A link to access the EU-ERP is shown in the global COP, along with basic information on the incident	Demonstration (functional validation)
Adequacy	YES/NO (compliance = success).	KPI 2: Adequacy: The emergency plans accessed are those specific to the territory and the type of risk concerned.	Demonstration (functional validation)
Operability	YES/NO (compliance = success).	KPI 3: By accessing the EU-ERP via the link in the global COP, the contents of the Emergency Response Plan related to the	Demonstration (functional validation)

CO-WP5-2-D01 - EU structured repository of emergency response plans: DEMONSTRATION			
		incident can be consulted in real time.	
Verification action #1	Date and location	Spanish-Portuguese border area between Valencia de Alcántara (Cáceres, Spain) and Marvão (Portugal). 4 May 2023.	
	Participants	PARTICLE SUMMARY (Portugal), TASSICA Spain)	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Availability: YES (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Adequacy: YES (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Operability: YES (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	

Table 20 – Results sheet CO.WP5-2-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex G – WP5 Result sheets opportunities

11.3.2.2. CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

CO.WP5-7-2 TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in MCI and disasters

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Time to triage: The average time taken to assign triage priorities using the TASSICA triage card.	Time (in seconds) from the victim first approach to the determination of triage priority and immediate actions.	KPI 9: A maximum acceptable average time to assign primary triage priorities: 1,5 min (90 sec).	Demonstration (functional validation)
Triage accuracy rate: The percentage of correct triage decisions made using the TASSICA triage card.	% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly triaged casualties by the total number of triaged casualties,	KPI 10: Minimum 80% of correctly triaged casualties made using the TASSICA triage card.	Demonstration (functional validation)

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION			
	expressed as a percentage).		
Verification action #1	Date and location	Hospital do Espírito Santo. Évora (Portugal). 4 May 2023.	
	Participants	Hospital emergency department staff.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 9: TASSICA 3 Time to triage threshold: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Primary triage average: 27 sec (ACHIEVED) ○ Secondary triage average: 42 sec (ACHIEVED) • KPI 10: TASSICA 3 Triage accuracy rate: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Primary triage accuracy: 95% (ACHIEVED) ○ Secondary triage accuracy: 90% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	

Table 21 – Results sheet CO.WP5-7-2-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex G – WP5 Result sheets opportunities

11.3.2.3. CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Time to triage: The average time taken to assign triage priorities using the TASSICA triage card.	Time (in seconds) from the victim first approach to the determination of triage priority and immediate actions.	KPI 10: A maximum acceptable average time to assign primary triage priorities: 1,5 min (90 sec).	Demonstration (functional validation)
Triage accuracy: The percentage of correct triage decisions made using the TASSICA triage card.	% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly triaged casualties by the total number of triaged	KPI 11: Minimum 80% of correctly triaged casualties made during the MCI drill using SIGRUN.	Demonstration (functional validation)

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
	casualties, expressed as a percentage).		
Verification action #1	Date and location	Spanish-Portuguese border area between Valencia de Alcántara (Cáceres, Spain) and Marvão (Portugal). 4 May 2023.	
	Participants	Summa 112 (Madrid, Spain), EMS SES (Extremadura, Spain), 112 EXTREMADURA (Spain), Unidad Militar de Emergencias (UME, Spain), EMS INEM (Portugal), Autoridade Nacional de Emergência e Proteção Civil (Portugal), Hospital do Espírito Santo (Évora, Portugal).	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 10: Time to triage average (SIGRUN): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Primary triage average: 44 sec (ACHIEVED) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prehospital EMS: 75 sec ▪ Hospital: 12 sec ○ Secondary triage average: 58 sec (ACHIEVED) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prehospital EMS: 48 sec ▪ Hospital: 67 sec • KPI 11: Triage accuracy (SIGRUN): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Primary triage accuracy: 95% (ACHIEVED) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prehospital EMS: 90% ▪ Hospital: 100% ○ Secondary triage accuracy: 90% (ACHIEVED) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prehospital EMS: 90% ▪ Hospital: 90% 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	
Result	Successful verification: YES		

Table 22 – Results sheet CO.WP5-13-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex G – WP5 Result sheets opportunities

11.4. WP6 Results**11.4.1. CO.WP6.2 Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data****11.4.1.1. Preliminary tests results**

Details on the methodology and design of the demonstrations carried out can be found in Deliverable D7.3.

11.4.1.2. UC1 Results

TEST - 01	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP6-1-T01- Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data	Verify that the data stored in the SIGRUN platform is correctly stored, applying cryptographic mechanisms to ensure that only authorized access can access it. Also, the data transmitted over the network is secure.	KPI 1: Information available: Yes / No (Available = success)	<i>The results obtained are that the information is 100% available and that the data is exchanged encrypted over the network thanks to https. On the other hand, for the simulations, the option of encrypting the data in the database has been highlighted in order to speed up its operation, but this option can be activated at any time.</i>
		KPI 2: data transfer protocol configured to use encrypted communications: encryption setting	
		KPI 3: data is stored with in an encrypted format: encryption setting	

Table 23 – Results sheet CO.WP6.2

11.5. Summary of stakeholders' feedback for the VALKYRIES solution and use case implementation

Two stakeholder questionnaires were carried out: a generic one on the development of the simulation, and another on the usability and utility of the technologies tested by the Valkyries project.

11.5.1. Simulation General Assessment Survey

For the general assessment of the simulation, an anonymous survey was conducted addressed to all the services that had participated in it. A mail group was created with the list of all the participants and an email was sent with the link of the survey to be filled in anonymously after the simulation.

The survey consisted of a web form that could be filled out from the computer, mobile phone or tablet-pc, with 36 questions with a gradation level of 1 to 10 according to the level of satisfaction of the participant with each of the aspects exposed. Additionally, the email of the participant was collected to corroborate his participation in the simulation (which was not used for the analysis), his role (the function he performed in the simulation) and an open question to write comments about the participation in the simulation of the interested party. It was agreed that the language would be in Spanish and Portuguese.

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Plantilla de Evaluacion de Simulacros por Organizacion Mundial de la Salud (OMS)

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* Indica que la pregunta es obligatoria

Correo *

Tu dirección de correo electrónico

ROLE *

Elige

RESPUESTA AL EVENTO:
Busqueda y rescate.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

DEFICIENTE ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ EXCELENTE

Figure 23 – General assessment survey

This questionnaire was extracted and adapted from the recommendations of the World Health Organization for the performance of simulation exercises(1).

A total of 31 responses were collected. Half of the participants belonged to emergency services and the rest were other participants and about 1% of authorities. The quantitative variables were expressed as mean, standard deviation (SD), standard error of the mean (SE), coefficient of variation (CV), asymmetry and percentiles (0%, 25%, 50% or median, 75% and 100%). The qualitative ones through absolute and relative proportions.

Table 25 summarizes the statistics for each of the questions (Annex D).

Question 37 (SIGRUN's overall satisfaction level) has a mean of 8.69 (1.40) with a median of 9 (IQR: 7.75-10).

Figure 24 – Satisfaction level of SIGRUN

Most of the questions show a mean between 6-7 with a median of 5-6. None has a value less than 2 and all have a maximum value of 10. We interpret that the realization of the simulation has had a fairly good general evaluation, while the evaluation of each of the specific aspects has obtained an evaluation in the middle of the satisfaction scale. In general terms, it is an acceptable evaluation, although there is clearly room for improvement. As points for improvement, it is worth mentioning the low adherence of the first respondents to the task of answering the surveys. Less than 10% of the first responders who took part in the surveys. On the one hand, low adherence to evaluation surveys is common among emergency medical services, especially when they include a large number of questions with lots of options. On the other hand, it is true that greater dissemination could have been done in different time periods to improve adherence to this task. Also, the way in which the survey is conducted could have been made more user-friendly.

11.5.2. Usability and usefulness of Valkyries tools survey

To assess the usability and usefulness of SIGRUN, we conducted an anonymous survey among the services involved. In the building where the first debriefing took place, a QR code inviting the completion of a short survey was placed in crowded places (such as doors and bulletin boards).

Figure 25 – Debriefing session after UC1 execution

This survey was elaborated electronically through a web form, which allowed its completion both on mobile phones, as in Tablet-pc, as well as on computers. To prevent it from being filled in multiple times by the same person, the email identity was recorded, but this information was not used for analysis.

The survey consisted of 21 questions with a score associated with whether the respondent agreed or disagreed with the corresponding statement. The service to which the respondent belongs, their role in the simulation and the type of tool used during it were also recorded. It took approximately 5 to 15 minutes to complete each survey, with button or multiple choice responses. By agreement of the parties, the languages used were Spanish and Portuguese.

Por favor, señale de entre las siguientes soluciones federadas en SIGRUN que se han ensayado en el simulacro, aquellas que usted haya podido evaluar:

- iSafety de INDRA
- GLOBAL COP de PARTICLE SUMMARY
- Digital TRIAGE
- TASSICA 3 Triage card

Nivel de satisfacción general de SIGRUN *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

NADA SASTIFECHO ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ MUJ SASTIFECHO

HORIZON 2020

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Figure 26 – VALKYRIES tools survey

A total of 17 responses were collected. The participants belonged mainly to Emergency Services and authorities. And more than half of the SUMMA 112 and the Hospital do Espírito Santo de Évora. After the database was purged, a descriptive study was carried out. Each of the quantitative variables was expressed in mean and standard deviation, and the qualitative variables in the form of absolute and relative frequencies.

Figure 27 – Distribution of responders

Table 26 summarizes the statistical parameters of the evaluations of each of the questions (Annex D).

Question 22 (SIGRUN's overall satisfaction level) has a mean of 9.2 (0.92) with a median of 9.5 (IQR: 8.25-10).

Nivel de satisfacción general de SIGRUN
10 respuestas

Figure 28 – General satisfaction level of SIGRUN

Most questions show a median of 7 to 8, with a non-Gaussian bimodal distribution. This makes us interpret that the level of satisfaction with all aspects of "Quality of working life" and "Perceived utility" is very good, with very few cases with a rating below 5. Overall it is a better evaluation than the overall drill survey. The exceptions are question 19, "Whenever I make a mistake when using SIGRUN, I recover easily and quickly" which shows a lower score (below 5) and question 20, "Information (such as online help, on-screen messages, and other documentation) provided with SIGRUN." Both refer to the difficulty that operators have in managing failures or that the information provided may be insufficient. On the other hand, question 22 is a general question of the level of satisfaction with SIGRUN, with a very high score, and in no case less than 8, so the implementation has been a clear benefit for the participants in the drill. As in the previous survey, the adherence of first responders to this activity was very low (less than 5%),

so the conclusions should be taken with great caution. The points for improvement are the same: to increase the dissemination of the surveys among first responders, to make them more user-friendly and to summarize the number of questions and the duration of the survey as much as possible.

11.6. Summary of the debriefing, recommendations and lessons learned

After the simulation exercise, a "hot" meeting exercise called debriefing "hot wash" which is a facilitated process often conducted by the lead evaluator. A key element of this learning method is debriefing, which has been defined as a conversation between several people to review a real or simulated event, in which the participants analyse their actions and reflect on the role of thought processes, psychomotor skills, and emotional states to improve or maintain future performance.

The focus of this first debrief is to allow everybody to decompress and to give participants the opportunity to provide their initial feedback on the exercise. It does not include evaluation of exercise outcomes, nor does it go into the level of detail planned for the main exercise debrief on the following day.

The following day, another "cold" meeting took place to analyse in more detail what had happened and identify areas for improvement.

During these meetings, first responders were requested to provide reports on their actions during the simulation. These reports were crucial in understanding the strengths and weaknesses of the response plan and identifying potential areas for improvement.

It is important to highlight that these meetings were crucial for learning and continuous improvement of the response team, demonstrating a commitment to safety and effectiveness in emergency situations.

Among the aspects of the content of the debriefing carried out, it is worth highlighting:

Regarding the most general aspects pointed out by almost all the participants, there was much praise regarding the success of the drill, motivated by the high number of participants, as well as the excellent predisposition to carry it out, as well as the motivation in carrying out the assigned tasks.

Given the problems of communication by radio and especially by telephone, many participants consider the enormous benefits of having information in real time by entering data/patients into the digital system at each step of the care circuit, as well as the possibility of coordination between different countries, teams and places.

The application for digitalizing the triage process enabled traceability of each patient from the beginning to the end of the entire exercise. This was not the case in the analogue triage group, where 10 green casualties were not correctly recorded and their traceability, injuries, etc. were completely lost.

Specifically, the health emergency services highlighted the good intervention and collaboration between different actors, such as security teams, police, DYA, Red Cross, Firefighters from different services and also wanted to highlight the exceptional work of the UME medical lieutenant, highlighting his better preparation, due to knowing how to function in the environment and carry out training and drills frequently.

The objective was to highlight the need for greater training and preparedness to face disaster situations, as well as improvements in the supply of material.

The need to identify the actors has been pointed out, such as with identification vests, to know the roles of each one.

In summary, it is worth highlighting the satisfaction shown by the success of the simulation in all participants and the great reception of the Valkyries solutions in terms of comments, on the availability of information, situation of resources and monitoring in all phases of care for victims.

12. Conclusions

Use case 1 has successfully demonstrated that the digitization of care processes in a multi-victim incident reduces not only the time spent on voice communications, but also the time spent on the entire care and evacuation of the injured. In addition, digitization has improved the accuracy of communication between each of the first responders involved, reducing errors and mismatches. The digital triage and assistance proposed by Valkyries project has been better than the traditional (analogue) triage and assistance commonly used by first responders. Finally, the impact it has had on Command and Control has allowed for accurate and near real-time information that has aided decision making by first responders.

The VALKYRIES project is aimed to enhance the effectiveness and interoperability of emergency response teams in cross-border and cross-sector emergency situations. It analyzed, improved, and developed infrastructures, protocols, and prompt data exchange standardization and harmonization tactics to achieve this goal.

In UC1, a full-scale exercise (as defined by the WHO) multi-victim incident simulation was conducted on the Spain-Portugal border. It involved a forest fire, a traffic accident, and first responders from both countries. We have been able to implement in a simulation not designed "ex profeso" as a project demonstrator, that by using observers, timekeepers and various surveys filled in by the first responders, we can successfully test the requirements set by the project.

By designing and carrying out preliminary tests and small-scale simulations in the Project's demonstrators, we have been able to evaluate and verify that the enablers proposed by VALKYRIES work as designed and, in the opinion of the experts, are suitable for testing and verifying the opportunity to which each of them refers.

The most relevant aspects we have been able to demonstrate are the following:

- The digital tool used has made it possible to decongest telecommunications and optimise the management of the chain of command in a multi-victim incident in cross-border countries.
- This has made it possible to integrate and improve the immediate response to multi-casualty emergencies involving two neighbouring countries.
- It has also allowed the recording, distribution, integration and sharing of all essential basic information, the minimum set of data, to optimise the management of the multi-casualty incident.

In addition, regarding the coordination process, the Valkyries solutions and the tools used have been able to demonstrate the following:

- Reception of initial information, with Methane Method
- Allocation of resources, mobilization and monitoring thereof
- Information on the injured, after initial triage and evacuation triage
- Assignment of evacuation resources
- Transfer of information to hospitals receiving injured people (hospital alert)
- Completion of the information process upon arrival at the hospital

The current use of voice communications in emergency medical services (via radios and mobile phones) and triage systems based on paper cards has a considerable cost in terms of time and errors. The Valkyries solution has developed a software tool that integrates and distributes all essential and basic information to the chain of command and control and develops the "Minimum Data Set" (MDS) to manage the Multi

Casualty Incident. This research within the exercise aimed to assess the impact of a digital tool on telecommunications relief and management optimisation in MCI. It included primary and secondary triage severity colour, age, gender, haemodynamic stability, type of pathology, assigned resources and destination hospital. The Valkyries project concluded that the digitisation of information in the MCI compared to the traditional analogue system had the potential to provide essential information available in real time, optimising the management of the chain of command and control by reducing communication congestion and overall incident management time. The difference achieved in primary triage depends more on the severity of the injuries (serious and minor cases with red and green triage cards) than on the participant.

In addition, digitalization allows information to be shared, made available to different care providers for multiple victims, to help decision-making, for better knowledge of the situation, as well as to anticipate subsequent phases of care, such as arrival and treatment to hospital. Hospital preparation can be improved by knowing the number and characteristics of patients in advance.

There are certain areas for improvement and difficulties that have been identified in this demonstrator:

- Although the first responders' assessments of the usability of the tested tools have been very positive, we have not been able to motivate everyone to complete the necessary surveys for the demonstrator. The proportion of first responders who completed both surveys was very low.
- The digital tool has required significant effort to improve its simplicity and user-friendliness for use with few gestures. It is necessary to invest significant effort to ensure that ease of use is not compromised by the security and registration processes that are essential due to established requirements. Also, one way to reduce interpersonal variability in triage and care colour assignment is to incorporate certain triage and care suggestions into the application based on the vital signs data entered.
- The data collection process for the demonstrator has not been straightforward. An effort has been required during small-scale prior simulations to refine and improve the timing process and observation by the evaluators. The digitization process and SIGRUN platform could also help the collection of data and times in emergency situations.
- During the analogue triage process, 10 patients in green (less severe) were not correctly recorded. Manoeuvres should be undertaken to improve the recording of the less serious patients and their location. This was a strength of the digital triage process, where no losses occurred.

13. References and bibliography

1. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable "D4.3 Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters"
2. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable "D2.8 Architecture Design Document"
3. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable "D7.3 System Validation and Evaluation"
4. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable "D7.4 Reference Integration and Lesson Learned Report"
5. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable "D7.1 Test Bed and Evaluation Methodology"

14. Annex A – Glossary

Acronym	Description
112	EU emergency phone number
ACC	Supplementary Traffic Authorization
ACP	Advance Command Post
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANEPC	Autoridade Nacional de Emergência e Proteção Civil
ANPC	Portuguese National Authority for Civil Protection
API	Application Programming Interface
API	Application Programming Interface
ASP	Advanced Sanitary Post
AT	Assistencial Triage
C&C	Command and Control
C2	Command and Control
CCON	National Operational Coordination Centre (Portugal)
CECOM	Command Cell
CECOP	Operative Control Centre
CELAC	Command Support Logistics Cell
CEPLO	Planning and Operations Cell
CEROP	Operational Response Cell
CERTEC	Technological Resources Cell
CMD	Cooperative Multichannel Emergency Message Dissemination Protocol
COP	Conference Of the Parties
CPEI	Consortium for the Prevention and Extinction of Fires
CV	coefficient of variation
DYA	Basic life support ambulances
DYA	Roadside Assistance Association (Asociación de Ayuda en Carretera)
ECC	Emergencies Coordinating Centre
EP	Evacuation Post
ERP	Emergency Response Plans
ET	Evacuation Triage
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
EUR-ERP	Structured Repository of EU Emergency Response Plans
FR	Funding Requirement
FR	First Responder

Acronym	Description
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSM	Global System for Mobile communication
H2020	Horizon 2020
HDB	Hospital de Burgos
HDG	Hospital de Getafe
HDM	Hospital de Mérida
HLT	Hybrid Twin Labs
HQ	Head Quarter
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
HUB	Hospital Universitario de Badajoz
HUC	Hospital Universitario de Cáceres
ICU	Intensive Care Unit
IFISE	Emergency Training Centre of the Community of Madrid
IMHT	Incident Management Health Team
INEM	Emergency medical services in Portugal (Instituto Nacional de Emergência Médica de Portugal)
INFOEX	Forest Fire Prevention and Extinguishing Service
IQR	Interquartile range
ISEP	Instituto Superior de Estudos Profesionales
IT	Information Technology.
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MCI	Multi-victim incidents
MCI	Multi Casualty Incident
MCP	Medical Command Post
MDS	Minimum Data Set
MEs	Mission success measures)
MVP	Multiple Victim Plan (Extremadura Civil Protection Plan)
P/AI	Problems/areas for improvement
PCDis	District Command Post
PCMun	Municipal Command Posts
PCNac	Plano nacional de Emergência de Proteção Civil
QR	Quick response
SD	Standard deviation
SE	Standard error of the mean

Acronym	Description
SEPEI (CEPEI)	Provincial Fire Prevention and Extinction Service of Cáceres.
SES	Regional Health System
SES	Extremadura health service
SVA	Advanced life support
SVB	Basic life support
TP	Triage Post
UC	Use Case
UME	Military Emergency Unit
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WHO	World Health Organization

Table 24 - Glossary

15. Annex B - Feedback questionnaire for first responders

15.1. Annex B1 - Simulation General Assessment Survey

The questions were as follows (identified numerically for correlation with the tables and graphs):

1. "RESPONSE TO THE EVENT: Search and rescue."
2. "RESPONSE TO THE EVENT: Firefighting."
3. "RESPONSE TO THE EVENT: First aid."
4. "RESPONSE TO THE EVENT: Mass casualty care."
5. "RESPONSE TIME: Search and rescue."
6. "ORGANIZATION OF RESPONSE: Leadership"
7. "ORGANIZATION OF RESPONSE: Internal coordination."
8. "ORGANIZATION OF THE RESPONSE: Coordination extrena."
9. "ORGANIZATION OF RESPONSE: Distribution of responsibilities."
10. "ORGANIZATION OF RESPONSE: Functioning as a team."
11. "ORGANIZATION OF RESPONSE: Discipline"
12. "DEVELOPMENT OF OPERATIONS: Application of plans, protocol"
13. "SECURITY MEASURES: Intervention technique applied."
14. "SECURITY MEASURES: Setting priorities."
15. "SECURITY MEASURES: Solution of unforeseen events."
16. "SECURITY MEASURES: Proper use of equipment, supplies and tools."
17. "HOSPITAL COMPONENT: Emergency Service Preparedness"
18. "HOSPITAL COMPONENT: Hospital triage system."
19. "HOSPITAL COMPONENT: Stabilization of patients."
20. "HOSPITAL COMPONENT: Surgical and medical care of injuries."
21. "HOSPITAL COMPONENT: Support service for care as diagnosis and therapy."
22. "HOSPITAL COMPONENT: Communication and internal and external coordination."
23. "HOSPITAL COMPONENT: Coordination and activation of the emergency plan."
24. "HOSPITAL COMPONENT: Availability and dissemination of the emergency plan"
25. "HOSPITAL COMPONENT: Personnel available and with knowledge of their tasks."
26. "HOSPITAL COMPONENT: Availability of supply."
27. "RESOURCE MANAGEMENT: Transportation."
28. "RESOURCE MANAGEMENT: Personnel."
29. "RESOURCE MANAGEMENT: Finance."
30. "RESOURCE MANAGEMENT: Facilities."
31. "RESOURCE MANAGEMENT: Other."
32. "RESOURCE MANAGEMENT: Closing of operations."
33. "RESOURCE MANAGEMENT: Evaluation of situation control."
34. "RESOURCE MANAGEMENT: Application of protocol for closing operations."
35. "RESOURCE MANAGEMENT: Alert deactivation or controlled scene indication."
36. Feedback on your participation.
37. SIGRUN's overall satisfaction level

15.2. Annex B2 - Usability and usefulness of Valkyries tools survey

The questions asked were the following (identified numerically for correlation with the tables and graphs):

1. "Quality of working life: I think SIGRUN has been a very useful tool for my work."
2. "Quality of working life: I think SIGRUN has been a very useful tool for our organization."
3. "Quality of working life: SIGRUN is an important part of personal work tools."
4. "Perceived utility: Using SIGRUN makes it easier to manage IMVs"
5. "Perceived utility: Using SIGRUN allows me to quickly manage IMVs."
6. "Perceived utility: The use of SIGRUN makes it more likely that IMV management is correct."
7. "Perceived utility: The use of SIGRUN is useful to correctly manage IMVs."
8. "Perceived utility: I believe that SIGRUN presents a more equitable process to attend and manage IMVs."
9. "Perceived utility: I am satisfied with SIGRUN to attend and manage the IMVs."
10. "Perceived utility: Using SIGRUN makes it easier to manage IMVs"
11. "Perceived utility: The use of SIGRUN increases the quality of IMV management."
12. "Perceived utility: I can manage IMVs correctly every time I use SIGRUN."
13. "Perceived ease of use: I am comfortable with my SIGRUN capability"
14. "Perceived utility: Learning to operate SIGRUN is easy for me."
15. "Perceived Utility: It's easy for me to be skilled in using SIGRUN"
16. "Perceived Utility: Easy-to-use SIGRUN Encounter."
17. "Perceived usefulness: I can always remember how to log in and use SIGRUN"
18. "User control: SIGRUN gives error messages that clearly tell me how to troubleshoot."
19. "User Control: Whenever I make a mistake while using SIGRUN, I recover easily and quickly."
20. "User Control: Information (such as online help, on-screen messages, and other documentation) provided with SIGRUN"
21. Please point out among the following federated solutions in SIGRUN that have been tested in the simulation, those that you have been able to evaluate
22. SIGRUN's overall satisfaction level

16. Annex D – Results from the analysis of the questionnaire data (Frequency tables)

16.1. Annex D1 - Simulation General Assessment Survey

The following table shows the results for the simulation general assessment survey.

	mean	sd	se(mean)	CV	skewness	0%	25%	50%	75%	100%
						Quartile				
Question 01	6,21	2,37	0,44	0,38	0,52	3	4	5	8	10
Question 02	6,48	2,28	0,46	0,35	0,32	3	5	5	8	10
Question 03	6,33	2,45	0,45	0,39	0,34	2	4	5	8	10
Question 04	6,23	2,30	0,42	0,37	0,48	3	4	5	8	10
Question 05	6,47	2,33	0,43	0,36	0,47	4	5	5	8	10
Question 06	5,93	2,50	0,46	0,42	0,21	2	4	5	8	10
Question 07	6,23	2,42	0,44	0,39	0,26	3	4,25	5	8	10
Question 08	6,16	2,31	0,42	0,38	0,43	3	4	5	8	10
Question 09	6,13	2,47	0,45	0,40	0,25	2	4	5	8	10
Question 10	6,50	2,38	0,42	0,37	0,08	2	5	5	9	10
Question 11	6,19	2,48	0,45	0,40	0,36	2	4	5	8	10
Question 12	6,13	2,29	0,41	0,37	0,40	3	4	5	8	10
Question 13	6,34	2,41	0,45	0,38	0,39	4	4	5	8	10
Question 14	6,55	2,50	0,46	0,38	0,35	4	4	5	9	10
Question 15	6,10	2,09	0,39	0,34	0,63	3	5	5	8	10
Question 16	6,38	2,31	0,43	0,36	0,57	4	5	5	9	10
Question 17	6,57	2,35	0,44	0,36	0,30	3	5	5,5	8	10
Question 18	6,55	2,38	0,44	0,36	0,36	3	5	5	9	10
Question 19	6,56	2,36	0,45	0,36	0,39	4	5	5	9	10
Question 20	6,64	2,46	0,49	0,37	0,29	4	4	5	9	10

	mean	sd	se(mean)	CV	skewness	0%	25%	50%	75%	100%
Question 21	6,13	2,25	0,40	0,37	0,54	3	4	5	8	10
Question 22	6,35	2,33	0,46	0,37	0,28	3	4	5	8	10
Question 23	6,62	2,42	0,47	0,37	0,23	3	5	5,5	9	10
Question 24	6,24	2,60	0,52	0,42	0,30	3	4	5	8	10
Question 25	6,33	2,34	0,45	0,37	0,34	3	4	5	8	10
Question 26	6,42	2,44	0,48	0,38	0,43	4	4	5	8,75	10
Question 27	6,00	2,30	0,41	0,38	0,54	2	4	5	8	10
Question 28	6,17	2,61	0,48	0,42	0,36	2	4	5	8,75	10
Question 29	6,21	2,19	0,45	0,35	0,83	4	5	5	8	10
Question 30	6,48	2,35	0,42	0,36	0,43	3	5	5	8	10
Question 31	6,19	2,55	0,45	0,41	0,36	3	4	5	8,25	10
Question 32	6,48	2,34	0,43	0,36	0,30	4	4	5	8	10
Question 33	6,42	2,41	0,43	0,37	0,33	3	4,5	5	8	10
Question 34	6,56	2,33	0,45	0,35	0,43	4	5	5	8	10
Question 35	6,30	2,30	0,44	0,37	0,57	4	4	5	8	10
Question 37	8,69	1,40	0,35	0,16	-0,52	6	7,75	9	10	10

Table 25 – Results of simulation general assessment survey

16.2. Annex D2 - Usability and usefulness of VALKYRIES tools survey

The following table shows the results for the survey concerning the usability and usefulness of VALKYRIES tools.

	mean	sd	se(mean)	cv	skewness	0%	25%	50%	75%	100%
Question 01	7,00	2,32	0,56	0,33	0,10	4	5	8	9	10
Question 02	7,00	2,35	0,57	0,34	0,00	3	5	8	9	10
Question 03	6,88	2,34	0,57	0,34	0,13	4	5	8	8	10
Question 04	7,12	2,55	0,62	0,36	-0,10	3	5	8	10	10

	mean	sd	se(mean)	cv	skewness	0%	25%	50%	75%	100%
Question 05	7,06	2,61	0,63	0,37	-0,10	3	5	8	10	10
Question 06	7,00	2,57	0,62	0,37	-0,05	3	5	8	10	10
Question 07	7,00	2,69	0,65	0,38	-0,15	3	5	8	10	10
Question 08	6,65	2,89	0,70	0,44	-0,14	2	4	8	10	10
Question 09	7,00	2,57	0,62	0,37	-0,05	3	5	8	10	10
Question 10	6,88	2,64	0,64	0,38	-0,04	3	5	7	10	10
Question 11	6,76	2,70	0,66	0,40	-0,13	2	5	7	10	10
Question 12	6,71	2,76	0,67	0,41	-0,10	2	5	7	10	10
Question 13	7,06	2,61	0,63	0,37	-0,22	3	5	8	9	10
Question 14	7,24	2,36	0,57	0,33	-0,03	4	5	8	9	10
Question 15	7,12	2,39	0,58	0,34	0,00	4	5	8	9	10
Question 16	7,06	2,36	0,57	0,33	-0,11	3	5	8	9	10
Question 17	6,59	2,69	0,65	0,41	-0,07	3	4	7	9	10
Question 18	6,29	2,44	0,59	0,39	0,14	3	4	7	8	10
Question 19	3,88	0,86	0,21	0,22	-0,43	2	3	4	4	5
Question 20	6,29	2,44	0,59	0,39	0,02	2	5	6	8	10
Question 22	9,20	0,92	0,29	0,10	-0,47	8	8,25	9,5	10	10

Table 26 – Results for the survey concerning the usability and usefulness of VALKYRIES tools

17. Annex E – Evidence

17.1. Screenshots of the Applications for UC1

iSafety application is performed as an emergency tool ready to execute and provide response for the victims. UC1 mission is join cross-frontier first aid response against major fire disaster. The 112-emergency coordinator centre (CCU) in Badajoz, Spain, receives multiple calls alerting for fires in areas near the border between Spain and Portugal. Note in the following picture there is a Mission created at 04/05/2023 10:22. Ticket has been created for Agency 112 and mission is IN/0000220[1]. Status of the Mission is: On the way. It means the assets may be deployed in aim to provide assistance to the incident. Several elements are assigned to the mission and has their own status.

Figure 29 – iSafety screenshot

During the course of action, more missions will be aggregate to the incident. New mission: IN/0000220[2] has been added up. Beyond to the first mission the second one has deployed new resources such as Guardia Civil and Pick Up and their status are: On the way. Consider the first mission IN/0000220[1] has became to Status: Active.

Figure 30 – iSafety Mission window

In order to generate a new Event related to the Mission fill the field on the application. Date, Type of Incident, Status, Location, Information, etc. New staff and vehicles will be held the mission as Medical Support or Traffic out.

Figure 31 – iSafety Event window

Likewise iSafety brace the application with GIS tool. GIS Digital tools aims to enhance the decision-making process. Starting identifying options to evaluation the information in the map until select and implement your decision. In the map two main incidents has been created (IN 0000221 & IN 0000220). Improving visual perception through icons for each incident well referenced.

Figure 32 – iSafety GIS tool

All the actives (assets) deployed in the field will be upload in real-time on the map. Operator can get a global view regarding emergency vehicles performance assessment.

Figure 33 – iSafety GIS tool with assets

The following tool is called GLOBAL COP and is strictly synchronized with SIGRUN. It is the application in charge for the incident visualization. The entire dataset gathered on SIGRUN will be analysed and treated over this panel. The user will manage any data regarding Geolocation, Vehicle deployment (Assets) and Medical Support. Due to the incident it is categorized as CBRN the resources deployed will be aligned to response and provide as many assets as need it.

Figure 34 – GLOBAL_COP: UC1 global view of the assets (Vehicles) in the field

Staff / Asset	Type	Status	Location	Organisation	Unit	Destination	ETA
SUMMA Triage Staff EMS 411	Advanced Emergency Medical Technician	Available	LatLon (40.5287, -3.6880)	SJMMA	SUMMA - TRIAGE CENTRE (TRI)		
SUMMA Triage Staff EMS 410	Advanced Emergency Medical Technician	Available	LatLonAlt (39.3819, -7.3304, 672)	SJMMA	SUMMA - TRIAGE CENTRE (TRI)		
SUMMA Triage Chief EMS Nurse 404	Registered Nurse	Available	LatLon (40.5288, -3.6883)	SJMMA	SUMMA - TRIAGE CENTRE (TRI)		
SUMMA Triage Staff EMS Technician 403	Advanced Emergency Medical Technician	Available	LatLon (40.5230, -3.6884)	SJMMA	SUMMA - TRIAGE CENTRE (TRI)		
SUMMA Triage Staff EMS Technician 402	Advanced Emergency Medical Technician	Available	LatLonAlt (40.5284, -3.9705, 861)	SJMMA	SUMMA - TRIAGE CENTRE (TRI)		
SUMMA Triage Staff EMS Technician 401	Advanced Emergency Medical Technician	Available	LatLon (40.5289, -3.6885)	SJMMA	SUMMA - TRIAGE CENTRE (TRI)		
SUMMA Incident Control Team EGI SCU 311	EMS Physician	Available	LatLon (40.5287, -3.6881)	SJMMA	SUMMA - CENTRO DE COORDINACIÓN (CCO)		
SUMMA Ambulance Staff AMBULANCE 310	Advanced Emergency Medical Technician	Available	LatLon (40.5285, -3.6885)	SJMMA	SUMMA - CENTRO DE COORDINACIÓN (CCO)		

Figure 35 – GLOBAL_COP: view of the UC1 assets list status, entity and locations

17.2. Images from UC1 execution

Figure 38 – Two actors participating in the simulation as injured people inside the bus. They wear a pendant with vital signs and findings that cannot be simulated

Figure 39 – Close-up of one of the crashed vehicles with first responders

Figure 40 – Casualty evacuation lifeline set up between the crashed bus and the advanced medical post

Figure 41 – Arrival of the wounded at the two outposts

Figure 42 – Advanced command and control post

18. Annex F – WP4 Result sheets Opportunities

18.1. CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles

18.1.1. CO-WP4-15-T01- Location of Nearest vehicles

CO-WP4-15-T01- Location of Nearest vehicles			
Description	The system MUST be able to generate an updated vehicles position picture that support the Operational Command to make better time dependent victims evacuation decisions.		
Location/Participants	Location: Border Portugal / Spain + Evora Hospital + route connecting both. Participants: PARTICLE, ANEPC, SUMMA112.		
Requirements	REQ_BASE_T4.1_2, REQ_COM_T4.3_7, REQ_COM_T4.5_2, REQ_COM_T4.5_9, REQ_COM_T4.5_10, REQ_COM_T4.5_11, REQ_COM_T4.5_15		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Vehicles position elapsed time between the real position and the information updated in the command centre: < 2 minute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vehicles position know at the command centre - Vehicles position updates within a gape time bellow 2 minutes - Vehicles destination capable of estimating a vehicle ETA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - KPI 1: Information available - KPI 2: Updated position of vehicles - KPI 3: time elapsed 	Demo
	Description	Information confidentiality	
	Participants	PARTICLE / Fire brigade / Hospital Evora	
	Location	Border PT / Spain + Evora city	
	Execution	To verify the vehicles and actors' position, correctly reported and presented and GLOBAL COP.	
	Analysis and results	The result of this test is the verification that the vehicles' location is correctly reported and updated within an acceptable time and disseminated to the User within an acceptable elapsed time.	
	History of corrective measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinate reference system between lat / log and decimal was not homogeneous. Correction on the coordinates system usage was required. - ETA depends in the route and conditions. Routes definition algorithms may need to improve to a more reliable result. 	
	Lessons learned	As the number of positional dynamic elements increases, particular attention must be taken to the network speed to support the continuous updating of vehicles, victims and assets position.	
	Quality	A	

CO-WP4-15-T01- Location of Nearest vehicles		
	End-user feedback	(See enquiry from UC1)
	Result	YES

Table 27 – Results sheet CO-WP4-15-T01

18.2. CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges

18.2.1. CO-WP4-42- T01- Reduce Voice Communication

CO-WP4-42- T01- Reduce Voice Communication			
Description	<i>Integration test related to Incident Creation, Task Creation and assets creation and update and information access from several devices for UC1</i>		
Location/Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Testing Sessions remotely: 24th February 10th March 17th March, 24th March (Indra, Tassica, Particle)</i> • <i>Intermediate Testing: 27th March (Madrid, Indra, Tassica, Particle, SUMMA)</i> • <i>Pre-Demo Testing: 28th March (IFISE Madrid, Indra, Tassica, Particle, SUMMA)</i> • <i>Demo Testing: 3rd May (Valencia Alcantara, Indra, Tassica, Particle, SUMMA)</i> • <i>Final Demo: 4th May (Valencia Alcántara, SUMMA, INDRA, Particle, Tassica, 112 Extremadura, Salud Extremadura, Hese, Proteçao Civil Portugal)</i> 		
Requirements	REQ_COM-T4.3.2, REQ_COM-T4.3.10, REQ_COM-T4.3.19, REQ_COM-T4.3.22		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
<p><u>1.</u> Incident Reported in SIGRUN</p> <p><u>2.</u> Task Reported in SIGRUN</p> <p><u>3.</u> Asset assignment to task in incident is reported in SIGRUN</p> <p>4. Asset status is reported in SIGRUN</p> <p>5. Asset location is reported in SIGRUN</p> <p>6. GLOBAL COP information accessible through different devices</p>	<p>iSafety application updates data in SIGRUN</p> <p>GLOBAL COP visualizes the information in several devices (laptops, tablets)</p>	<p>KPI 1: Information about the incident available in SIGRUN: YES/NO (Available = success)</p> <p>KPI 2: information about the task available in SIGRUN: YES/NO (Available = success)</p> <p>KPI 3: Information about assets localization available in SIGRUN: YES/NO (Available = success)</p> <p>KPI 4: Information about assets associated to tasks available in SIGRUN. YES/NO (Available = success)</p>	Test

		<p><i>KPI 5. Information related to Incident/tasks/assets in GLOBAL COP is available through different devices. YES/NO (Available = success)</i></p>	
Verification Step#1	Description	Incident Creation	
	Participants	PARTICLE, INDRA	
	Location	Remotely/Onsite	
	Execution	<p>An operator using iSafety, creates a new incident (Fire), specifying type of the incident, location and a short description. When operator click on Save Button to create the incident in iSafety, this information is sent to Sigrun.</p> <p>Then, this incident is created in SIGRUN, and this information is showed on Global COP web portal, and system applications can read this incident information from SIGRUN</p>	
	Analysis and results	The information is available on SIGRUN (GLOBAL_COP) and iSafety	
	History of corrective measures	Access errors appeared if the URL or API was not correct and If connectivity was not guaranteed. The incident type must match between both systems.	
	Lessons learned	Check Communications. Check URL and API from iSafety access before. Check incident catalogue between the systems. Several intermediate tests must be performed before executing the whole test.	
	Quality	A	
	End-user feedback	No end user feedback.	
	Result	YES	
Verification Step#2	Description	Missions/Tasks Creation	
	Participants	PARTICLE, INDRA	
	Location	Remotely/OnSite	
	Execution	<p>An emergency service operator, using iSafety, creates a new mission (SCOUTING MISSION) associated to the incident, specifying type of the mission and a short description. When operator click on Save Button to create the task in iSafety, this information is sent to Sigrun.</p>	

Verification Step#3	Analysis and results	The information is available on iSafety and GLOBAL COP.
	History of corrective measures	Access errors appeared if the URL or API was not correct and If connectivity was not guaranteed. The tasks/missions must be checked before.
	Lessons learned	The catalogue of tasks has to match (isafety/SIGRUN). Several tests need to be performed to ensure integration.
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	No end user feedback.
	Result	YES
	Description	Assets assignment to tasks and update
	Participants	PARTICLE, INDRA
	Location	Remotely
	Execution	On a third step, Emergency service operator, using iSafety, assign several assets to Scouting Mission (PICKUP1, PICKUP2) and several assets to the same mission. Then operator changes the status of the assets when they are “on the way”. The simulation begins from this TASK.
	Analysis and results	The information is available on ISafety and GLOBAL-COP. Isafety is accessing the routes of the vehicles provided by HTL (Hybrid Twin Labs)
	History of corrective measures	The same that previous verifications but also the assets catalogue must be the same between SIGRUN and iSafety (previous check). Several tests need to be performed with all the scenarios. Tasks and Assets must match for simulation integration.
	Lessons learned	The asset catalogue has to match (ISafety/SIGRUN). The biggest complexity has been modelling the units and assets with the SIGRUN data model for the UC1. We tried to homogenise the missions and tasks between the agencies to better understand the operational vision but each agency has its own type of mission and should be adjusted in more detail for real use. We create previous a structure of assets and Agencies that changed during the drill (more assets) and this was quite difficult to change.
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	No end user feedback.
	Result	YES

Table 28 – Results sheet CO-WP4-42-T01

Below is a more detailed test with the complete exercise for UC1. The verification steps are repeated depending on the missions, tasks and resources that are managed from command and control on several testing days. Evidence are reported on the UC screenshots .

TEST-ID	CO-WP4-42- T01- Reduce Voice Communication				
Date and Location	Testing Sessions (remotely): 24th February 10th March 17th March,24th March (Indra, Tassica, Particle) Intermediate Testing (remotely): 27th March (Madrid, Indra, Tassica, Particle, SUMMA) Pre-Demo Testing: 28th March (IFISE Madrid, Indra, Tassica, Particle, SUMMA) Demo Testing: 3rd May (Valencia Alcantara, Indra, Tassica, Particle, SUMMA) Final Demo: 4th May (Valencia Alcántara, SUMMA, INDRA, Particle, Tassica, 112 Extremadura, Salud Extremadura, Hese, Proteção Civil Portugal)				
Participants	SUMMA, INDRA, Particle, Tassica, 112 Extremadura, Salud Extremadura, Hese, Proteção Civil Portugal				
ACTION		TYPE (Isafety)		Description	Results
Incident Creation	Incident 1	FIRE		Incident Creation 09:30h (SPAIN)	OK
Incident Creation	Incident 2	FIRE		Incident Creation 09:40h (PORTUGAL)	OK
Incident Creation	Incident 3	TRAFFIC ACCIDENT		Incident Creation 10:20h	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 1	SCOUTING	Incident 1	Scouting 09:35h Kick off INFOEX	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	PICKUP 3	"ON THE WAY"	Pickup 3 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	AUTOPUMP 5	"ON THE WAY"	Autopump 5 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	AUTOPUMP 6	"ON THE WAY"	Autopump 6 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	PICKUP 3	"ON SITE"	Pickup 3 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	AUTOPUMP 5	"ON SITE"	Autopump 5 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	AUTOPUMP 6	"ON SITE"	Autopump 6 on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 2	CONTROL	Incident 1	Control Task 09:40h Kick off Police	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	GC1	"ON THE WAY"	Guardia Civil' GC1 Patrol on the way	OK

ACTION		TYPE (Isafety)		Description	Results
Asset Update	Mission 2	GC2	"ON THE WAY"	Guardia Civil' GC2 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	GC1	"ON SITE"	Guardia Civil' GC1 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	GC2	"ON SITE"	Guardia Civil' GC2 on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 1	AMPLIATION	Incident 2	Ampliation Resources 09:45	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	VEHICLE Nº1	"ON THE WAY"	Vehicle Nº1 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	VEHICLE Nº2	"ON THE WAY"	Vehicle Nº2 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	CGIF	"ON THE WAY"	CGIF on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	VEHICLE Nº1	"ON SITE"	Vehicle Nº1 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	VEHICLE Nº2	"ON SITE"	Vehicle Nº2 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	CGIF	"ON SITE"	CGIF on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 3	MEDICAL SUPPORT	Incident 2	Medical Support task 09:45h	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMBULANCE	"ON THE WAY"	AMB SIM1 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMBULANCE	"ON THE WAY"	AMB SIM2 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMBULANCE	"ON THE WAY"	AMB 1 SVB1 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMBULANCE	"ON THE WAY"	AMB 2 SVB2 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMBULANCE	"ON SITE"	AMB SIM1 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMBULANCE	"ON SITE"	AMB SIM2 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMBULANCE	"ON SITE"	AMB SVB1 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMBULANCE	"ON SITE"	AMB 2 SVB2 on the way	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 4	CONTROL	Incident 2	PMA 112 Activation 10:00h	OK
Asset Update	Mission 4	TRUCK	"ON THE WAY"	112 Truck vehicle on the way	OK

ACTION		TYPE (Isafety)		Description	Results
Asset Update	Mission 4	TRUCK	"ON SITE"	112 Truck vehicle on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 5	CONTROL	Incident 2	UME Activation 10:05h	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	UME	"ON THE WAY"	UME on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	PMA	"ON THE WAY"	PMA on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	LEON101	"ON THE WAY"	LEON101 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	AUTOBOMBA1	"ON THE WAY"	AUTOBOMBA1 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	AUTOBOMBA2	"ON THE WAY"	AUTOBOMBA2 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	AUTOBOMBA3	"ON THE WAY"	AUTOBOMBA3 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	PICKUP1	"ON THE WAY"	PICKUP1 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	UME	"ON SITE"	UME on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	PMA	"ON SITE"	PMA on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	LEON101	"ON SITE"	LEON101 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	AUTOBOMBA1	"ON SITE"	AUTOBOMBA1 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	AUTOBOMBA2	"ON SITE"	AUTOBOMBA2 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	AUTOBOMBA3	"ON SITE"	AUTOBOMBA3 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	PICKUP1	"ON SITE"	PICKUP1 on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 6	CONTROL	Incident 2	Kick off Drill 10:45h - Pickup and autobomba	OK
Asset Update	Mission 6	PICKUPSIM	"ON THE WAY"	PICKUPSIM on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 6	AUTOBOMBA SIM1	"ON THE WAY"	AUTOBOMBA SIM1 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 6	PICKUPSIM	"ON SITE"	PICKUPSIM on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 6	AUTOBOMBA SIM1	"ON SITE"	AUTOBOMBA SIM1 on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 1	MEDICAL SUPPORT	Incident 3	Medical Support task 10:20h	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	AMB SIM4	"ON THE WAY"	Ambulance SIM4 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	AMB SIM5	"ON THE WAY"	Ambulance SIM5 on the way	OK

ACTION		TYPE (Isafety)		Description	Results
Asset Update	Mission 1	AMB5	"ON THE WAY"	SVB on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	AMB SIM4	"ON SITE"	Ambulance SIM4 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	AMB SIM5	"ON SITE"	Ambulance SIM5 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	AMB5	"ON SITE"	SVB on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 2	TRAFFIC OUT	Incident 3	Roadblock 10:20	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	VEHICLE N°1	"ON THE WAY"	Police car 1 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	VEHICLE N°2	"ON THE WAY"	Police car 2 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	VEHICLE N°1	"ON SITE"	Police car 1 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	VEHICLE N°2	"ON SITE"	Police car 2 on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 3	MEDICAL SUPPORT	Incident 3	Medical Support task 10:41h	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMB6	"ON THE WAY"	Ambulance AMB6 SVB on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMB7	"ON THE WAY"	Ambulance AMB7 SVB on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMB8	"ON THE WAY"	Ambulance AMB8 VIR1 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMB9	"ON THE WAY"	Ambulance AMB9 VIR2 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMB10	"ON THE WAY"	Ambulance AMB10 VIR3 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMB6	"ON SITE"	Ambulance AMB6 SVB on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMB7	"ON SITE"	Ambulance AMB7 SVB on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMB8	"ON SITE"	Ambulance AMB8 VIR1 on site	OK

ACTION		TYPE (Isafety)		Description	Results
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMB9	"ON SITE"	Ambulance AMB9 VIR2 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	AMB10	"ON SITE"	Ambulance AMB10 VIR3 on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 4	TRAFFIC OUT	Incident 3	Roadblock 10:50	OK
Asset Update	Mission 4	VEHICLE Nº3	"ON THE WAY"	Police car 3 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 4	VEHICLE Nº4	"ON THE WAY"	Police car 4 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 4	VEHICLE Nº3	"ON SITE"	Police car 3 on site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 4	VEHICLE Nº4	"ON SITE"	Police car 4 on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 6	MEDICAL SUPPORT	Incident 3	Medical Support task 10:41h	OK
Asset Update	Mission 6	AMB1	"ON THE WAY"	Ambulance AMB1 on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 6	AMB1	"ON SITE"	Ambulance AMB1 on site	OK
Incident close	Incident 1	FIRE		Close incident (FIRE) SPAIN	OK
Incident close	Incident 2	FIRE		Close incident (FIRE) PORTUGAL	OK
Incident close	Incident 3	TRAFFIC ACCIDENT		Close incident (TRAFFIC ACCIDENT)	OK

Table 29 – Detailed test CO-WP4-42-T01

18.2.2. CO-WP4-42-T02- Reduce Voice Communication

CO-WP4-42-T02- Reduce Voice Communication	
Description	<i>Integration Test related to Triage Information (UC1), the information should be the same in both countries and also different devices</i>
Date and Location and Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Testing Sessions remotely: 24th February 10th March 17th March, 24th March (Indra, Tassica, Particle)</i> • <i>Intermediate Testing: 27th March (Madrid, Indra, Tassica, Particle, SUMMA)</i> • <i>Pre-Demo Testing: 28th March (IFISE Madrid, Indra, Tassica, Particle, SUMMA)</i> • <i>Demo Testing: 3rd May (Valencia Alcantara, Indra, Tassica, Particle, SUMMA)</i>

CO-WP4-42-T02- Reduce Voice Communication

- Final Demo: 4th May (Valencia Alcántara, SUMMA, INDRA, Particle, Tassica, 112 Extremadura, Salud Extremadura, Hese, Proteçao Civil Portugal)

Requirements COM_T4.3_2, REQ_COM_T4.3_22, REQ_COM_T4.4_10, REQ_COM_T4.4_11, REQ_COM_T4.5.2.

ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
<p>1. Victims registration in SIGRUN</p> <p>2. Victims status time update in SIGRUN</p> <p>3. Victims triage data update in SIGRUN</p> <p>4. GLOBAL COP information accessible through different devices</p> <p>5. GLOBAL COP information accessible in different countries</p>	<p>System applications updates incident data in SIGRUN</p> <p>Command and control systems read data from SIGRUN</p> <p>GLOBAL COP visualizes the information in several devices (laptops, tablets)</p> <p>GLOBAL COP visualizes the information in both countries</p>	<p>KPI 1: Victim Registration available: YES/NO (Available = success)</p> <p>KPI 2: Victim status time update (Triage STATUS) available: YES/NO (Available = success)</p> <p>KPI 3: Victims triage data update (Triage STATUS) available: YES/NO (Available = success)</p> <p>KPI 4: Information related Triage Process in GLOBAL COP is available through different devices. YES/NO (Available = success)</p> <p>KPI 5: Information about Triage Process in GLOBAL COP is available in both countries. YES/NO (Available = success)</p>	<p>Test</p>
Verification action #1	Description	Victim Registration and Medical Information Registration Verification	
	Execution	<p>Incident (Fire) is created into SIGRUN Platform</p> <p>Victim Age/Gender is registered in the platform.</p> <p>Status Triage information is updated (AT,ET)</p> <p>Main Pathology is updated</p> <p>Triage Classification is updated</p> <p>Transport is updated</p> <p>Staff reporting information is available</p>	
	Analysis and results	The information is displayed in GLOBAL-COP	
	History of corrective measures	The terminals must be setup for staff information. Connectivity with URL and API must be configured and checked previously.	

CO-WP4-42-T02- Reduce Voice Communication		
	Lessons learned	<i>The communications and access to URL/API for terminals and applications deployed with GLOBAL COP must be checked before and the application for digitalizing triage process must be checked in every terminal before to avoid problems during the test</i>
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	<i>No feed Back from user</i>
	Result	YES
Verification action #2	Description	<i>GLOBAL COP Information visualized in TABLET and the same for both countries</i>
	Execution	<i>We check that the same information displayed in workstation is displayed in GLOBAL COP and the workstations from Command Post for each country</i>
	Analysis and results	<i>The information is displayed in a tablet GLOBAL-COP</i>
	History of corrective measures	<i>The terminals must be setup for staff information</i>
	Lessons learned	<i>The communications and access to API/URL must be checked before the test. The terminals must be checked before the test.</i>
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	<i>No feed Back from user</i>
	Result	YES

Table 30 – Results sheet CO-WP4-42-T02

18.2.3. CO-WP4-42_T03- Reduce Voice Communication

CO-WP4-42-T03- Reduce Voice Communication			
Description	<i>Test for Verification Real Time Update in SIGRUN Platform (UC2)</i>		
Date and Location and Participants	<i>Final Demo: 4th May (Valencia Alcántara, SUMMA, INDRA, Particle, Tassica, 112 Extremadura, Salud Extremadura, Hese, Proteção Civil Portugal)</i>		
Participants	<i>INDRA, TASSICA, PARTICLE</i>		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method

CO-WP4-42-T03- Reduce Voice Communication

<p>1. Incident reported in SGRUN (< than 60 s)</p> <p>-2.Task Registration in SGRUN (< than 60 s)</p> <p>-3.Assets registration in SGRUN (< than 60 s)</p> <p>- Assets update in SGRUN (< than 60 s)</p>	<p>System applications update data in SGRUN</p> <p>Command and control systems read data from SGRUN</p>	<p>KPI 1: Time elapsed (since Incident is created in iSafety and registered in SGRUN Database)</p> <p>< 60 sec 100% success</p> <p>Between 60 and 90 sec 50% success</p> <p>Between 90 to 120 sec 25% success</p> <p>> 120 sec 0% success</p> <p>KPI 2: Time elapsed (since task is created in iSafety and registered in SGRUN Database)</p> <p>< 60 sec 100% success</p> <p>Between 60 and 90 sec 50% success</p> <p>Between 90 to 120 sec 25% success</p> <p>> 120 sec 0% success</p> <p>KPI 3: Time elapsed (since asset is created in iSafety and registered in SGRUN Database)</p> <p>< 60 sec 100% success</p> <p>Between 60 and 90 sec 50% success</p> <p>Between 90 to 120 sec 25% success</p> <p>> 120 sec 0% success</p> <p>KPI 4: Information about Triage Process in GLOBAL COP is available in both countries. YES/NO (Available = success)</p>	<p>Test</p>
<p>Verification action #1</p>	<p>Description</p>	<p>Incident Creation in UC1</p>	
	<p>Execution</p>	<p>Incident (Fire) is created into SGRUN Platform by an operator</p>	
	<p>Analysis and results</p>	<p>The information is displayed in GLOBAL-COP. We verify that we have the isafety logs and that we have the information in the SGRUN database for subsequent analysis.</p>	

CO-WP4-42-T03- Reduce Voice Communication

	History of corrective measures	<i>The communications to API/URL must be checked before Execution. The catalogue with the type of incidents must have been previously configured and must match between SIGRUN and the Command and Control applications. Previous tests data must be deleted before the test to avoid confusion.</i>
	Lessons learned	<i>To ensure that everything works and can be tested, many pre-tests have to be carried out to check that the data between the two applications is correct.</i>
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	No feed Back from user
	Result	YES
Verification action #2	Description	<i>Task Creation</i>
	Execution	<i>A task (Scouting Mission) is created into the incident</i>
	Analysis and results	<i>The information is displayed in GLOBAL-COP</i>
	History of corrective measures	<i>The communications to API/URL must be checked before Execution. The catalogue with the type of tasks must have been previously configured and must match between SIGRUN and the Command-and-Control applications.</i>
	Lessons learned	<i>The same that previous tests.</i>
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	No feed Back from user
	Result	YES
Verification action #2	Description	<i>Asset assignment to a Task</i>
	Execution	<i>An asset is attached to the previous task created (Fire Unit)</i>
	Analysis and results	<i>The information is displayed in GLOBAL-COP. We ensure that we have the application logs locally and the data in the central DB for further analysis.</i>
	History of corrective measures	<i>To ensure that everything works and can be tested, many pre-tests have to be carried out to check that the data between the two applications is correct.</i>
	Lessons learned	<i>The environment is the same as the previous tests and we can extract the same lessons.</i>
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	No feed Back from user
	Result	YES

Table 31 – Results sheet CO-WP4-42-T03

18.2.4. CO-WP4-42- D03- Reduce Voice Communication

CO-WP4-42- D03- Reduce Voice Communication			
Description	SIGRUN uses token for authorisation, therefore, the HTTPs requests sent must have a valid token on the header.		
Location/Participants	Remotely/UMU [BM18]		
Requirements	REQ_COM_T4.2_8		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Requests are authenticated	Execution time: Should not affect Resource consumption: Should not affect	KPI 1: Adequacy: 100% requests are authenticated by a valid token. KPI 2: Data security: All data will be logged encrypted in a secure blockchain network.	<i>Demo</i>
	Description	Authentication mechanisms for network access	
	Participants	UMU	
	Location	Remotely	
	Execution	<i>What has been done in this demonstration is the attempt to access and exchange information by one device without the authentication token and another with the authentication token to demonstrate that it is necessary to carry the token in order to communicate with SIGRUN.</i>	
	Analysis and results	<i>The result obtained is that the device without an authentication token was unable to communicate with SIGRUN as it did not have a token and was not allowed access, while the other device was allowed access.</i>	
	History of corrective measures		
	Lessons learned	<i>If this requirement were not met, any device could communicate with SIGRUN and inject false information into the network.</i>	
	Quality	A	
	End-user feedback	<i>No end user feedback.</i>	
Result	YES		
Verification Action #2			

Table 32 – Results sheet CO-WP4-42-D03

18.2.5. CO-WP4-42- D04- Reduce Voice Communication

CO-WP4-42- D04- Reduce Voice Communication	
Description	Each application would have to map their internal roles into the SIGRUN roles of the architecture
Location/Participants	Remotely/UMU [BM19]

CO-WP4-42- D04- Reduce Voice Communication			
Requirements	REQ_COM_T4.2_9		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Roles are assigned to organization, giving them certain roles as described in D5.3 (Workflows and Risk Assessment Design Document)	Execution time: Should not affect Resource consumption: Should not affect	KPI 1: Adequacy: 100%.	<i>Demo</i>
	Description	Role-based authorisation	
	Participants	UMU	
	Location	Remotely	
	Execution	<i>For the demonstration of this requirement, the database has been checked to observe the roles that have been assigned to the different users and to be able to verify that not all users can perform the same actions.</i>	
	Analysis and results	<i>Several roles have been found, including administered, user and data entry device among others. This means that different roles are being assigned to different users.</i>	
	History of corrective measures		
	Lessons learned	<i>This requirement allows for a more detailed control of the tasks that can be performed by the different users of the platform.</i>	
	Quality	A	
	End-user feedback	<i>No end user feedback.</i>	
	Result	YES	
Verification Action #2			

Table 33 – Results sheet CO-WP4-42-D04

18.2.6. CO-WP4-42- D05- Reduce Voice Communication

CO-WP4-42- D05- Reduce Voice Communication			
Description	The SIGRUN platform must be capable of acquiring multidomain data, such as, first responses in different countries, and integrate it the same platform. Moreover, the information interchanged in the communication must be encrypted.		
Location/Participants	Remotely/UMU [BM20]		
Requirements	REQ_BASE_T6.1_2, REQ_BASE_T6.1_3, REQ_COM_T6.1_5		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method

CO-WP4-42- D05- Reduce Voice Communication			
SIGRUN handles multidomain data	Latency: less than 1000ms for every request.	<p>KPI 1: Adequacy: 100%.</p> <p>KPI 2: Penalties in execution time: less than 10ms</p>	Demo
	Description	Multidomain data	
	Participants	UMU	
	Location	Remotely	
	Execution	For the demonstration of this requirement, the database has been checked to observe if there are data from different domains.	
	Analysis and results	SIGRUN is capable of handling multidomain data. In checking the database, it has been found that SIGRUN contains data from different countries and information from different domains, e.g., fire, locations, triage of victims, etc. In addition, as the test CO-WP4-42-D03 is successfully, all the information interchanged are encrypted.	
	History of corrective measures		
	Lessons learned	This requirement allows handling multiple information from different domain in the same platform. This is important as decisions can be based on a more solid and complete information base containing information from different domains. This reduces uncertainty and risk when making important decisions in different domains.	
	Quality	A	
	End-user feedback	No end user feedback.	
Result	YES		
Verification Action #2			

Table 34 – Results sheet CO-WP4-42-D05

18.3. CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms

18.3.1. CO-WP4-21- A01- Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms

CO-WP4-21- A01- Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	
Description	SIGRUN must be capable of integrating data form multiples sources, such as, specific data for each first responder during an emergency, allowing to analyse the data to create a trained model.
Location/Participants	Remotely/UMU

CO-WP4-21- A01- Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms			
Requirements	REQ_COM_T7.2_1, REQ_COM_T7.2_2, REQ_COM_T7.2_3		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Creation of a model which can speed up tasks in an emergency response.	<p>Execution time: Time prediction – less than 1000ms.</p> <p>System resource consumption: Imperceptible</p>	<p>KPI 1: Adequacy: 90%.</p> <p>KPI 2: Penalties in execution time: less than 5000ms</p>	Demo
	Description	Data analysis	
	Participants	UMU	
	Location	Remotely	
	Execution	<i>To demonstrate this requirement, the database with the gathered data during use cases by different sources of different first responders has been checked to analyse the data generated and apply preprocessed techniques to the data and create trained models.</i>	
	Analysis and results	<i>Different data processing techniques have been applied to obtain the most important features, and then three Machine Learning models have been generated. The first one consists of predicting the second triage based on the data obtained in the first one. The second model predicts the patient's death after the first triage. The last model predicts the patient's worsening after the first triage. All information about the processing techniques and the generated models can be found in D.7.2.</i>	
	History of corrective measures		
	Lessons learned	<i>Analysing triage data generated in different use cases and creating predictive models is highly important for first responders to obtain patterns and trends that may go unnoticed.</i>	
	Quality	A	
	End-user feedback	No end user feedback.	
Result	YES		

Table 35 – Results sheet CO-WP4-21-A01

19. Annex G – WP5 Result sheets Opportunities

19.1. CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

19.1.1. CO-WP5-1-T01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: PRELIMINARY TEST

CO-WP5-1-T01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: PRELIMINARY TEST			
Description	<p>Standardized terminology in emergency and disaster planning at the EU level is essential for clear, consistent communication and increased efficiency. The VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and implementation (VALKYRIES GLOSSARY) is a web-based, multilingual database of technical terms related to emergencies, designed to improve planning, communication, and coordination among first responders. This glossary, developed within the VALKYRIES project, is a prototype, aligned with deliverable D5.4 guidelines, and serves as a limited-scope example to test its effectiveness. It seeks to provide a unified understanding of terms for VALKYRIES researchers. A Cognitive Walkthrough testing of the VALKYRIES GLOSSARY is performed as a structured approach to evaluating usability of the prototype prior to its use in the planning of the demonstrators (UCs), using the results obtained to further improve the proposal.</p> <p>(Wharton C, Rieman J, Lewis C, Polson P. The Cognitive Walkthrough: A practitioner’s guide. 1994. https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:53925427)</p>		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.4_1, REQ_COM_T5.4_2, REQ_COM_T5.4_3 Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
1. Importance	Low / High	KPI 1: Identify at least 5 problems/areas for improvement (P/AI) rated as low or high importance.	Functional test
2. Frequency	Low / High	KPI 2: More than 65% of the detected P/AI rated as LOW frequency.	Functional test
3. Persistence	Low / High	KPI 3: More than 65% of detected P/AI rated as LOW persistence.	Functional test

CO-WP5-1-T01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: PRELIMINARY TEST

Verification action #1	Date and location	Madrid and Segovia (Spain), March 2023
	Participants	TASSICA researchers involved in the VALKYRIES project
	Description	<p>A cognitive walkthrough of the application has been carried out with the aim of discovering the possible problems that a user may encounter when using it. Based on this cognitive walkthrough, problem hypotheses were compiled, and a heuristic estimation was made for each of the three aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance (whether it affects severely affects usability) • Frequency (whether it occurs many times or few times) • Persistence (whether it is present during the journey). <p>The estimation of those three aspects of each of the possible problems is evaluated with two possible levels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low • High
	Execution	<p>The test was conducted with technology experts from the VALKYRIES Consortium.</p> <p>The list of tasks to be carried out during the Cognitive Walkthrough test would be as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Register a new term with a username and password. • Editing an existing term • Consult information of a term • Create a new equivalence of an existing term and then delete it. • Create a new source of documentation for an existing term and then delete it • Delete a term
Analysis	<p>The following is a compilation of usability problem scenarios indicating location, description and estimation. The complete cognitive walkthrough is included as ANNEX CO-WP5-1-T01.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1.2.1 Edit an existing term: The system may not clearly indicate that approved terms cannot be edited., Frequency: Low; Importance: Low; Persistence: Low • 1.2.2 Edit an existing term: The system does not limit the inclusion of comments in already approved terms, and generates an unchecked permissions 	

CO-WP5-1-T01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: PRELIMINARY TEST

		<p>error., Frequency: Low; Importance: High; Persistence: Low</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1.4.1 Create a new equivalence of an existing term and then delete it: The system does not allow the deletion of a term equivalence., Frequency: Low; Importance: High; Persistence: Low • 1.4.2 Create a new equivalence of an existing term and then delete it: Some users may perceive it as an error that equivalences cannot be added to already approved terms., Frequency: Low; Importance: Low; Persistence: Low • 1.5.1 Create a new source of documentation for an existing term and then delete it: The system does not allow the deletion of a source of documentation for a term., Frequency: Low; Importance: High; Persistence: Low • 1.5.2 Create a new source of documentation for an existing term and then delete it: It is possible that some users may perceive it as an error that source documentation cannot be added to already approved terms., Frequency: Low; Importance: Low; Persistence: Low • 1.7.1 Delete a term: After deleting a term, the term remains and the delete option is no longer displayed. If it is a logical deletion, the system leads to confusion by continuing to display the term., Frequency: High; Importance: High; Persistence: Low • 1.8.1 General use: If you wish to return from the term display screen, the system takes you back to the initial list of terms. You have to search again for the term you were working with., Frequency: High; Importance: High; Persistence: Low • 1.8.2 General use: The option to close or exit the tool is not clearly displayed., Frequency: Low; Importance: Low; Persistence: Low
	Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Importance: detected 9 problems/areas of improvement (P/AI) (5 rated as HIGH importance and 4 as LOW importance) (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Frequency: 77,8% of the detected P/AI rated as LOW frequency (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Persistence: 100% of detected P/AI rated as LOW persistence (ACHIEVED)

CO-WP5-1-T01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: PRELIMINARY TEST		
	History of corrective measures	Revision of the tool and update of the glossary for project demonstrators (UC).
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A, maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs).
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 36 – Results sheet CO-WP4-21-A01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See section 17.10 UC1 WP5 Preliminary test and UC1 demonstration evidence (evidence 6)

19.2. CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans

19.2.1. CO-WP5-2-T01 - EU structured repository of emergency response plans: TEST

CO-WP5-2-T01 - EU structured repository of emergency response plans: TEST			
Description	For effective coordination in emergency response planning, information must be standardised, structured, securely shared and readily available when needed. The STRUCTURED REPOSITORY OF EU EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLANS (EUR-ERP) aims to provide decision-makers with the information needed to coordinate cross-border disaster responses within the European Union Civil Protection system. Within the VALKYRIES project, the EUR-ERP is a prototype, which follows the guidelines of deliverable D5.4. It aims to provide VALKYRIES use cases with the necessary information to coordinate emergency plans in the territories involved. The effectiveness of the prototype was evaluated through testing.		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_2, REQ_COM_T5.2_3, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_5, REQ_COM_T5.3_6, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_10, REQ_COM_T5.3_11, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_13, REQ_COM_T5.3_14, REQ_COM_T5.3_17, REQ_COM_T5.3_22, REQ_COM_T5.4_9, REQ_COM_T5.4_10, REQ_COM_T5.4_11, REQ_COM_T5.4_14, REQ_COM_T5.4_31 Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
1. Importance	Low / High	KPI 1: Identify at least 5 problems/areas for improvement (P/AI)	Functional test

CO-WP5-2-T01 - EU structured repository of emergency response plans: TEST			
		rated as low or high importance.	
2. Frequency	Low / High	KPI 2: More than 65% of the detected P/AI rated as LOW frequency.	Functional test
3. Persistence	Low / High	KPI 3: More than 65% of detected P/AI rated as LOW persistence.	Functional test
Verification action #1	Date and location	Madrid and Segovia (Spain), March 2023	
	Participants	TASSICA researchers involved in the VALKYRIES project	
	Description	<p>A cognitive walkthrough of the application has been carried out with the aim of discovering the possible problems that a user may encounter when using it. Based on this cognitive walkthrough, problem hypotheses were compiled and a heuristic estimation was made for each of the three aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance (whether it affects severely affects usability) • Frequency (whether it occurs many times or few times) • Persistence (whether it is present during for the journey). <p>The estimation of those three aspects of each of the possible problems is evaluated with two possible levels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low • High 	
	Execution	<p>The test was conducted with technology experts from the VALKYRIES Consortium.</p> <p>The list of tasks to be carried out during the Cognitive Walkthrough test would be as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a new Emergency Response Plan (ERP) • Assign agencies involved in an existing ERP • Consult the items of an existing ERP of your own • Edit an existing ERP item • Duplicate an ERP item 	
	Analysis	<p>The following is a compilation of usability problem scenarios indicating location, description and estimation. The complete cognitive walkthrough is included as ANNEX CO-WP5-2-T01</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1.1.1 Create a new plan: When creating a plan, some items such as ON SCENE LIAISON COMMAND 	

CO-WP5-2-T01 - EU structured repository of emergency response plans: TEST

		<p>or ON SCENE COMMUNICATIONS AND MEDIA COMMAND do not appear in the plan as such at the scene level, but at the general or management level. As well as PLAN TRAINING or PLAN REVIEW. They are retained because they may appear in some plan., Frequency: Low; Importance: Low; Persistence: Low</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1.1.2 Create a new plan: When creating a plan, the item "ON SCENE UNIFIED COMMAND" raises questions. It can be understood to refer to the same thing as "UNIFIED ADVANCED COMMAND POST", since the ACP designates the agency and the person in command of the ACP., Frequency: Low; Importance: Low; Persistence: High • 1.1.3 Create a new plan: Some designations do not conform to the glossary, Frequency: Low; Importance: High; Persistence: High • 1.3.1 Assigning agencies involved in an existing scheme: Agencies must already be created in order to be assigned, it may be necessary to indicate a direct access link to the creation of agencies., Frequency: Low; Importance: Low; Persistence: Low • 1.2.1 Create a new agency: It may be necessary for the user to be able to create agencies, and not just the administrator., Frequency: Low; Importance: High; Persistence: Low • 1.6.1 Duplicate a plan item: When identifying the duplicate item from the original, doubts may arise. It may be necessary to mark the duplicate with (Copy) or similar., Frequency: Low; Importance: Low; Persistence: Low
	Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Importance: detected 6 problems/areas of improvement (P/AI) (all of them rated as LOW importance) (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Frequency: 66,7% of the detected P/AI rated as LOW frequency (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Persistence: 66,7% of detected P/AI rated as LOW persistence (ACHIEVED)
	History of corrective measures	Review of the prototype
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A, maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs).

CO-WP5-2-T01 - EU structured repository of emergency response plans: TEST		
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 37 – Results sheet CO.WP5-2-T01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See section 17.10 UC1 WP5 Preliminary test and UC1 demonstration evidence (evidence 7)

19.2.2. CO-WP5-2-D01 - EU structured repository of emergency response plans: DEMONSTRATION

CO-WP5-2-D01 - EU structured repository of emergency response plans: DEMONSTRATION			
Description	To ensure effective coordination in emergency response planning, it's crucial that information is standardized, organized, shared securely, and easily accessible when required. The STRUCTURED REPOSITORY OF EU EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLANS (EUR-ERP) is designed to equip decision-makers with the vital information for orchestrating cross-border disaster interventions under the European Union Civil Protection framework. As part of the VALKYRIES initiative, the EUR-ERP operates as a prototype, adhering to the directives of deliverable D5.4. This prototype is intended to furnish the VALKYRIES use cases with the requisite details to synchronize emergency plans in the participating regions. The functionality of this prototype was evaluated in UC1		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_2, REQ_COM_T5.2_3, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_5, REQ_COM_T5.3_6, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_10, REQ_COM_T5.3_11, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_13, REQ_COM_T5.3_14, REQ_COM_T5.3_17, REQ_COM_T5.3_22, REQ_COM_T5.4_9, REQ_COM_T5.4_10, REQ_COM_T5.4_11, REQ_COM_T5.4_14, REQ_COM_T5.4_31 Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
EUR-ERP Availability	YES/NO (compliance = success).	KPI 1: A link to access the EUR-ERP is shown in the global COP, along with basic information on the incident	Demonstration
EUR-ERP Adequacy	YES/NO (compliance = success).	KPI 2: The emergency plans accessed are	Demonstration

CO-WP5-2-D01 - EU structured repository of emergency response plans: DEMONSTRATION			
		those specific to the territory and the type of risk concerned.	
EUR-ERP Operability	YES/NO (compliance = success).	KPI 3: The contents of the Emergency Response Plan related to the incident can be consulted in real time.	Demonstration
Verification action #1	Date and location	Spanish-Portuguese border area between Valencia de Alcántara (Cáceres, Spain) and Marvão (Portugal). 4 May 2023.	
	Participants	PARTICLE SUMMARY (Portugal), TASSICA Spain)	
	Description	<p>During UC1, the EUR-ERP prototype developed at VALKYRIES was tested in real time by the Project researchers involved in the planning and execution of the simulation.</p> <p>The demonstration was complemented in a harmonised way with the other VALKYRIES enablers, within the reference integration implementation provided by the SIGRUN platform.</p>	
	Execution	<p>A cross-border MCI drill was held with the collaboration of various emergency services, each playing distinct roles in the emergency response, including first responders, emergency managers, technologists, and more. Data regarding emergency response plans specific to the incident's type and location can be accessed through a link in the comprehensive COP, directing to the EU-ERP prototype. This ensures the plans are available during the entire response phase.</p> <p>For assessment within SIGRUN, a 4G connection between applications is essential. The link between the devices and the SIGRUN platform will be checked before the exercise begins, and devices will be pre-set with the appropriate user details.</p>	
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: YES (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: YES (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: YES (ACHIEVED) 	

CO-WP5-2-D01 - EU structured repository of emergency response plans: DEMONSTRATION		
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 38 – Results sheet CO.WP5-3-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See section 17.10 UC1 WP5 Preliminary test and UC1 demonstration evidence (evidence 8)

19.3. CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

19.3.1. CO.WP5-7-1-T01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level:

PRELIMINARY TEST

CO.WP5-7-1-T01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: PRELIMINARY TEST			
Description	<p>The VALKYRIES project proposes to establish an EU-wide standardised code to unify the coding and labelling of casualties in mass casualty incidents (MCI) and disasters, based primarily on NATO standards. It is proposed to implement a pentapolar triage coding with the following triage priorities and colours for casualty tagging:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PT 1 IMMEDIATE (Red) • PT2 DELAYED (Yellow) • PT3 MINIMAL (Green) • PT4 EXPECTANT (Blue) • D DECEASED (Black) <p>To validate this, a questionnaire has been answered by two target groups: one consisting of first responders in training and the other one consisting of first responders integrated in an EMS with professional experience.</p>		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_10, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3 • Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Relevance: Degree of importance attached to the use of a common	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80%	Functional test

CO.WP5-7-1-T01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: PRELIMINARY TEST			
classification and coding of victim priorities in a MCI.	HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	by stakeholders.	
Stakeholder coding agreement: The level of agreement among first responders on the proposed MCI triage categories.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Functional test
Stakeholder tagging agreement: The level of agreement among first responders on the proposed MCI colour tagging code for victims in MCI and disasters.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Functional test
Cross-border cooperation improvement : The perceived improvement in cross-border cooperation between EMS when using a standardised classification and coding system.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 4: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Functional test

CO.WP5-7-1-T01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: PRELIMINARY TEST		
Verification action #1	Date and location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instituto Superior de Estudios Profesionales (ISEP) CEU. Castellón (Spain). 27 to 29 March 2023. • Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE). Madrid (Spain). 28 March 2023.
	Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students of the ISEP CEU's Ciclo Formativo de Grado Medio Técnico en Emergencias Sanitarias. • Doctors, Nurses and Emergency Medical Technicians of the Servicio de Urgencias Médicas SUMMA 112 of Madrid (Spain).
	Description	<p>The questionnaire contains four questions (1,2, 3 and 4) that refer to the following aspects:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Importance of EMS using the same classification to designate triage priority in MCI and disasters. 2. Use of a specific name for triage priorities 3. Specific assignment of colours for different triage priorities. 4. Assessment of the use of the same classification and colour coding in the EU to facilitate EMS working together in cross-border MCI. <p>The questionnaires are anonymous. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p>
	Execution	<p>Two groups were selected for testing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students of the Emergency Medical Technician course from the ISEP CEU Institute (Castellón, Spain). • Experienced first responders (Doctors, Nurses and Emergency Medical Technicians) from the SUMMA112 service (Madrid, Spain). <p>For each of these groups, a briefing session was organised in which the proposal for standardising the priorities and coding of MCI and disaster victims was presented.</p> <p>Both groups were then given the questionnaire containing the aspects considered to be key to analysing the need for a uniform coding and labelling system for MCI and disaster victims.</p>
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>a) FIRST RESPONDERS WITH EXPERTISE:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Relevance: 95,24% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Stakeholder coding agreement: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Stakeholder tagging agreement: 100,00% (ACHIEVED)

CO.WP5-7-1-T01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: PRELIMINARY TEST		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 4: Cross-border cooperation improvement: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Stakeholder coding agreement:5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Stakeholder tagging agreement: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Cross-border cooperation improvement: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) <p>b) FIRST RESPONDERS IN TRAINING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Relevance: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Stakeholder coding agreement: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Stakeholder tagging agreement: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Cross-border cooperation improvement: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Stakeholder coding agreement:5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Stakeholder tagging agreement: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Cross-border cooperation improvement: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED)
	History of corrective measures	This classification and coding were applied throughout the design and development phases of SIGRUN, in the planning and execution of the VALKYRIES use cases and in the integration of the tools used to support the Project's demonstrators.
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 39 – Results sheet CO.WP5-7-1-T01

Evidence of implementation and compliance

See section 17.10 UC1 WP5 Preliminary test and UC1 demonstration evidence (evidence 1, 3 and 4, questions 1, 2, 3 and 4)

19.3.2. CO-WP5-7-2-T01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST

CO-WP5-7-2-T01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST			
Description	<p>There is no consensus on how to label the priority of the casualties in an MCI or disaster, nor on how to record the clinical information that needs to accompany each patient through the chain of care.</p> <p>Triage cards have been used for some time, but they vary widely between services and generally have very limited versatility.</p> <p>VALKYRIES Project proposes the TASSICA 3 triage card as a standardised triage card for emergency services that may be involved in a MCI in order to ensure interoperability between services (professional or volunteer, civil or military), equity in treatment prioritisation, recording of victim information and traceability in mass casualty incidents and disasters.</p> <p>Information was collected about the respondents' opinion on the use of the TASSICA 3 card once it has been used in a MCI trial. A questionnaire was developed that covers aspects considered key to analysing the advantages of using a standardised triage card.</p>		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_2, REQ_COM_T5.1_10, REQ_COM_T5.1_11, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_5 Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Inter-rater reliability: The consistency in triage decisions among different first responders using the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Decision-making confidence: improvement in healthcare staff confidence in making triage decisions using the	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>

CO-WP5-7-2-T01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST			
TASSICA triage card, as measured by self-reported score.			
Traceability: the extent to which the card helps to improve the traceability of victims throughout the chain of care at the scene of an MCI.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Victim information completeness and accuracy: degree of ease of recording complete and accurate victim information using the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 4: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
First responder wellbeing: The degree to which the card helps the first responder in their care tasks and reduces their stress during operations.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 5: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>

CO-WP5-7-2-T01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST			
Task execution efficiency: The reduction in time taken to perform tasks in an MCI compared to using other options, as perceived by first responders.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 6: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Collaboration efficiency: The improvement in cross-border EMS collaboration, to coordinate and perform joint tasks using the TASSICA triage card, as perceived by first responders.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 7: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Overall satisfaction: The overall satisfaction of first responders with the TASSICA triage card	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 8: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Verification action #1	Data and location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instituto Superior de Estudios Profesionales (ISEP) CEU. Castellón (Spain). 27 to 29 March 2023. • Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE). Madrid (Spain). 28 March 2023. 	

CO-WP5-7-2-T01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST		
	Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students of the ISEP CEU's Ciclo Formativo de Grado Medio Técnico en Emergencias Sanitarias. Doctors, Nurses and Emergency Medical Technicians of the Servicio de Urgencias Médicas SUMMA 112 of Madrid (Spain).
	Description	<p>The questionnaire contains questions (5 to 12) that refer to the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extent to which the triage card helps to homogenise triage priorities, decide on lifesaving gestures, ensure traceability of a victim, and facilitates the recording of health information. Measure in which its use reduces the stress of healthcare staff in decision making. Assessment of its use in facilitating joint EMS work in cross-border MCI. Rating on enabling more efficient execution of tasks in a MCI compared to other cards. Overall level of satisfaction
	Execution	<p>A questionnaire has been answered by two target groups: one consisting of first responders in training and the other one consisting of first responders integrated in an EMS with professional experience.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The first group consists of trainees: Students of the Emergency Medical Technician course from the ISEP CEU Institute (Castellón, Spain). After receiving basic training on health care in MCI and the use of the triage card, they carry out a MCI drill in which they have to use the card to triage fictitious victims. They then complete the questionnaire. The second group consists of EMS personnel with pre-hospital experience: Doctors, nurses and paramedics participants in MCI exercises for the preliminary testing of the VALKYRIES proposals, organised by SUMMA 112 at the Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE) in Madrid (Spain). These personnel act as first responders in an MCI drill, assuming the different roles in the victims care using the proposed triage card. Just after the exercise, they answer the questionnaire. <p>The questionnaires are anonymous. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p>
	Analysis and results	<p>The answers to the questionnaires were expressed on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being the most unfavourable result</p>

CO-WP5-7-2-T01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST

		<p>to the proposal (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) and 5 being the most favourable result (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED). After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>a) FIRST RESPONDERS WITH EXPERTISE:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Inter-rater reliability: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Decision-making confidence: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Traceability: 90,48% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Victim information completeness and accuracy: 95,24% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 5: First responder wellbeing: 90,48% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Task execution efficiency: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Collaboration efficiency: 95,24% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Overall satisfaction: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inter-rater reliability: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Decision-making confidence: 4 (QUITE AGREED) • Traceability: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Victim information completeness and accuracy: 4 (QUITE AGREED) • First responder wellbeing: 4 (QUITE AGREED) • Task execution efficiency: 4 (QUITE AGREED) • Collaboration efficiency: 4 (HIGH) • Overall satisfaction: 4 (HIGH) <p>b) FIRST RESPONDERS IN TRAINING:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Inter-rater reliability: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Decision-making confidence: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Traceability: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Victim information completeness and accuracy: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 5: First responder wellbeing: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Task execution efficiency: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Collaboration efficiency: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Overall satisfaction: 100,00% (ACHIEVED)
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CO-WP5-7-2-T01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST		
		<p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inter-rater reliability: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Decision-making confidence: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Traceability: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Victim information completeness and accuracy: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • First responder wellbeing: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Task execution efficiency: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Collaboration efficiency: 4 (VERY HIGH) • Overall satisfaction: 4 (VERY HIGH)
	History of corrective measures	No corrective actions were deemed necessary in the design of the proposed enabler (standardised triage card TASSICA 3) or in the design of its validation tests.
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 40 – Results sheet CO.WP5-7-2-T01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See section 17.10 UC1 WP5 Preliminary test and UC1 demonstration evidence (evidence 1, 3 and 4, questions 5 to 12)

19.3.3. CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION	
Description	<p>VALKYRIES proposes the use of a standardised triage card (TASSICA 3) in the EU for the recording of key casualty information by the different emergency services that may intervene in a MCI.</p> <p>UC1 assessed the validity of the TASSICA 3 triage card as a mean of supporting interoperability between services (professional or volunteer, civilian or military), fairness in prioritising treatment, recording casualty information and traceability in mass casualty and disaster situations.</p> <p>The assessment of the enabler in the UC1 demonstrator was focused on the KPIs that measured objective aspects (KPI9 and KPI10) as these had not been assessed in the preliminary tests, and it was carried out in UC1 from a hospital perspective (VERIFICATION ACTION #1).</p>
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_2, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_5

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION			
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Time to triage: The average time taken to assign triage priorities using the TASSICA triage card.	Time (in seconds) from the victim first approach to the determination of triage priority and immediate actions.	KPI 9: A maximum acceptable average time to assign primary triage priorities: 1,5 min (90 sec).	Demonstration
Triage accuracy rate: The percentage of correct triage decisions made using the TASSICA triage card.	% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly triaged casualties by the total number of triaged casualties, expressed as a percentage).	KPI 10: Minimum 80% of correctly triaged casualties made using the TASSICA triage card.	Demonstration
Verification action #1	Date and location	Hospital do Espírito Santo. Évora (Portugal). 4 May 2023.	
	Participants	Hospital emergency department staff.	
	Description	The objective validity of the TASSICA 3 triage card was assessed on the basis of the data recorded by VALKYRIES' evaluators during the conduct of UC1 drill. An Excel sheet was defined to manually collect the information needed to evaluate TASSICA 3 triage card during the UC execution.	
	Execution	In UC1, a cross-border MCI response exercise was carried out, with a first phase of pre-hospital care of casualties (carried out at the scene of the accident by first responders from different Spanish and Portuguese emergency services), followed by a second phase (hospital phase) of reception and medical care of those casualties at the Hospital do Espírito Santo (HESE) in Évora (Portugal). This second phase was carried out by the	

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

		<p>medical staff (doctors and nurses) who are normally responsible for responding to this type of emergency in the HESE hospital.</p> <p>It is in this hospital phase that the TASSICA 3 triage card was evaluated in UC1 as an enabler to ensure interoperability, equity, victims' information registry and traceability in MCI and disasters.</p> <p>At the HESE hospital, the reception, triage and assistance procedures for MCI victims were carried out in parallel in 3 different ways, each using a different operating procedure:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Procedure normally used in the institution (with the usual triage cards of the HESE Emergency department). 2. VALKYRIES procedure using TASSICA 3 triage cards. 3. VALKYRIES procedure using SIGRUN federated system. <p>Collection of the information necessary to evaluate the TASSICA 3 triage card was made manually by a network of VALKYRIES' evaluators. The number and location of those evaluators during the execution of the UC was defined in order to properly carry out the data collection for the evaluation of the proposed enabler.</p> <p>The identification data and pathology of the drill victims were fictitious.</p>
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained using the TASSICA 3 triage card:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 9: TASSICA 3 Time to triage threshold: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Primary triage average: 27 sec (ACHIEVED) o Secondary triage average: 42 sec (ACHIEVED) • KPI 10: TASSICA 3 Triage accuracy rate: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Primary triage accuracy: 95% (ACHIEVED) o Secondary triage accuracy: 90% (ACHIEVED) <p>The following results were obtained using the procedures in place before the VALKYRIES proposal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time to triage threshold (following the previous operating procedures): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Primary triage average: 40 sec o Secondary triage average: 48 sec • Triage accuracy rate (following the previous operating procedures): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Primary triage accuracy: 95% o Secondary triage accuracy: 90%

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION		
		The TASSICA 3 card reduces primary triage time more than 33% and secondary triage time more than 11%, compared to previous operating procedures. Regarding the accuracy of the triage, it should be noted that the results were identical in both cases (using the TASSICA 3 card and the usual HESE hospital procedure).
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 41 – Results sheet CO.WP5-7-2-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See section 17.10 UC1 WP5 Preliminary test and UC1 demonstration evidence (evidence 9 and 10)

19.4. CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response

19.4.1. CO-WP5-12-T01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST

CO-WP5-12-T01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST	
Description	<p>When responding to mass casualty incidents (MCI) or disasters, it's essential to exchange information between the various services to coordinate the response effectively. Yet, emergency services often gather data that isn't uniformly relevant or standardized, posing a challenge to smooth integration.</p> <p>Standardisation of information is a prerequisite for any exchange of information, regardless of whether it is data, voice or any other form. It is therefore necessary to move in this direction in order to facilitate the exchange of information between different first responders or civil protection authorities within a country or between countries in cross-border disasters.</p> <p>VALKYRIES proposes a Minimum Data Set (EMS MDS) for Emergency Medical Services to share during MCIs and disasters concerning victim care. This EMS MDS includes data such as victim identification, characteristics, contact details, location, injuries, clinical updates, and other vital information.</p> <p>Information was collected about the respondents' opinion on the data exchanged during the trial.</p>

CO-WP5-12-T01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST

Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_2, REQ_COM_T5.2_3, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_5, REQ_COM_T5.3_6, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_10, REQ_COM_T5.3_11, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_13, REQ_COM_T5.3_14, REQ_COM_T5.3_17, REQ_COM_T5.3_22, REQ_COM_T5.4_9, REQ_COM_T5.4_10, REQ_COM_T5.4_11, REQ_COM_T5.4_14, REQ_COM_T5.4_31 Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Data relevance: The perceived relevance of the data exchanged during the trial for proper management of casualties by EMS in an MCI or disaster.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders	<i>Functional test</i>
Data usefulness: The perceived usefulness of the exchanged data in the performance of care tasks by first responders.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders	<i>Functional test</i>
Verification action #1	Date and location	Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE). Madrid (Spain). 28 March 2023.	
	Participants	Doctors, Nurses and Emergency Medical Technicians of the Servicio de Urgencias Médicas (SUMMA 112) of Madrid (Spain), and researchers from the VALKYRIES Consortium.	
	Description	A questionnaire has been developed to collect respondents' opinions on the usefulness of the data	

CO-WP5-12-T01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST

		<p>exchanged in the management of an MCI. Some of its questions (1 and 2) are related to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opinion on whether the data transmitted in the test are appropriate for the proper management of casualties by an EMS in MCI or disasters. • Whether the data exchanged has been useful to complete their care tasks. <p>The questionnaires are anonymous. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p>
	Execution	<p>An MCI simulation was conducted involving EMS professionals experienced in out-of-hospital care, including doctors, nurses, and paramedics. This was organized by SUMMA 112 at the Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE) in Madrid, Spain. Throughout the drill, several crucial procedures for such incidents were practiced, encompassing incident declaration, area control, victim triage, stabilization, evacuation, and Command and Control (C2) measures. Specific roles were assigned for these procedures, each generating and sharing data during the process. Once the exercise concluded, the first responders anonymously completed the questionnaire.</p>
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Data usefulness: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data relevance: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Data usefulness: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED)
	History of corrective measures	<p>The EMS MDS was used as a reference for the development of SIGRUN and for the integration of the different software tools used in the project demonstrators by the emergency services involved in the use cases (UCs).</p>
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 42 – Results sheet CO.WP5-12-T01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See section 17.10 UC1 WP5 Preliminary test and UC1 demonstration evidence (evidence 2 and 4, questions 1 and 2)

19.5. CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

19.5.1. CO.WP5-13-T01 SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST

CO.WP5-13-T01 SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST	
Description	<p>In order to support adequate information sharing for an effective response to an MCI or disaster, a federated system of applications operated by different emergency services, as well as different external data sources, could provide a solid basis for harmonisation and standardisation of IT systems, workflows and other issues that have been identified as major barriers to system interoperability, whether within a single country or in major cross-border disasters.</p> <p>SIGRUN is the VALKYRIES common framework used to federate a set of interrelated technology solutions to support first responder C2, logistics, deployment and medical care procedures and improve shared situational awareness in response to a multi-casualty incident or disaster.</p> <p>Preliminary testing was carried out in MCI simulations, and feedback was then collected on responders' views of operational procedures related to logistics, deployment and care at the scene of an MCI, based on information sharing with SIGRUN.</p>
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_7, REQ_COM_T5.1_8, REQ_COM_T5.1_11, REQ_COM_T5.1_12, REQ_COM_T5.2_2, REQ_COM_T5.2_4, REQ_COM_T5.2_5, REQ_COM_T5.2_6, REQ_COM_T5.2_7, REQ_COM_T5.2_8, REQ_COM_T5.2_9, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_COM_T5.2_11, REQ_COM_T5.2_12, REQ_COM_T5.2_13, REQ_COM_T5.2_14, REQ_COM_T5.2_2, REQ_COM_T5.2_4, REQ_COM_T5.2_5, REQ_COM_T5.2_6, REQ_COM_T5.2_7, REQ_COM_T5.2_8, REQ_COM_T5.2_9, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_COM_T5.2_11, REQ_COM_T5.2_12, REQ_COM_T5.2_13, REQ_COM_T5.2_14, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_2, REQ_COM_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_4, REQ_COM_T5.3_6, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_14, REQ_COM_T5.3_15, REQ_COM_T5.3_16, REQ_COM_T5.3_17, REQ_COM_T5.3_18, REQ_COM_T5.3_19, REQ_COM_T5.3_20, REQ_COM_T5.3_21, REQ_COM_T5.3_22, REQ_BASE_T5.4_1, REQ_BASE_T5.4_2, REQ_BASE_T5.4_3, REQ_COM_T5.4_1, REQ_COM_T5.4_2, REQ_COM_T5.4_3, REQ_COM_T5.4_4, REQ_COM_T5.4_5, REQ_COM_T5.4_6,

CO.WP5-13-T01 SIGRUN as an integration [PG21][AM22] reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
		<p>REQ_COM_T5.4_8, REQ_COM_T5.4_9, REQ_COM_T5.4_10, REQ_COM_T5.4_11, REQ_COM_T5.4_12, REQ_COM_T5.4_13, REQ_COM_T5.4_14, REQ_COM_T5.4_15, REQ_COM_T5.4_16, REQ_COM_T5.4_17, REQ_COM_T5.4_18, REQ_COM_T5.4_19, REQ_COM_T5.4_28, REQ_COM_T5.4_29, REQ_COM_T5.4_30, REQ_COM_T5.4_31, REQ_COM_T5.4_32, REQ_COM_T5.4_33, REQ_COM_T5.4_34</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 	
Information exchange facilitation: The perceived improvement in information exchange between services using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Task execution efficiency: The perceived improvement in the efficiency of task execution in an MCI using SIGRUN compared to the current situation.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Integration and cooperation: The perceived improvement in integration and cooperation with other	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>

CO.WP5-13-T01 SIGRUN as an integration [PG21][AM22] reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST			
services and/or procedures in responding to an MCI using SIGRUN.			
Implementation ease: The perceived ease and simplicity of implementing SIGRUN by first responders in an MCI.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 4: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
First responder well-being: The perceived improvement in the well-being of first responders during their operational tasks in an MCI using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 5: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Added value in cross-border MCI management: The perceived added value of using SIGRUN for managing and responding to an MCI affecting several	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 6: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>

CO.WP5-13-T01 SIGRUN as an integrator [PG21][AM22] reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST			
communities or countries.			
Satisfaction with information content: The overall satisfaction with the content of the information exchanged using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 7: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Satisfaction with the operational procedure: The degree of satisfaction with the operational procedure implemented and based on the capabilities offered by SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 8: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Verification action #1	Date and location	Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE). Madrid (Spain). 28 March 2023.	
	Participants	Doctors, Nurses and Emergency Medical Technicians of the Servicio de Urgencias Médicas (SUMMA 112) of Madrid (Spain), and researchers from the VALKYRIES Consortium.	
	Description	<p>A questionnaire has been developed to gather the opinion of respondents on the usefulness of SIGRUN in improving procedures associated with logistics, deployment and health care by first responders in an MCI or disaster. The questionnaire contains questions (5 to 12) referring to the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extent to which SIGRUN could facilitate the exchange of information between services. 	

CO.WP5-13-T01 Sigrun as an integration [PG21][AM22] reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extent to which the tested procedure would allow a more efficient execution of assigned tasks in a MCI compared to the current situation. • Opinion on whether this system would facilitate integration and joint work with other services and/or procedures in the response to an MCI • Opinion on the ease and simplicity of implementation by a first responder in a MCI • Opinion on the improvement of the well-being of first responders during their operational tasks in a MCI • Added value to the management and response in a MCI affecting several communities or countries • Overall satisfaction with the content of the information exchanged. • Degree of satisfaction with the operational procedure implemented and based on the capabilities offered by Sigrun. <p>The questionnaires are anonymous. Only is known to the institution to which the author belongs.</p>
	Execution	<p>An MCI exercise was conducted with the participation of EMS personnel experienced in MCI and disasters response (doctors, nurses, and paramedics) organized by SUMMA 112 at the Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE) in Madrid, Spain. During the exercise, the various links necessary for the activation and implementation of a care procedure for this type of incident are used, such as: declaring the incident, triaging the victims, stabilising them and evacuating them. To this end, roles and operational procedures are defined to carry out the various care tasks, each of which generates data that is displayed and shared. Sigrun is used as the information exchange system. Software tools supporting responders (triage, COP, C2), all federated in Sigrun, were used for the trial.</p> <p>During the test, data is generated that needs to be updated in the system in real time.</p>
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Information exchange facilitation: 100,00% (ACHIEVED)

CO.WP5-13-T01 SIGRUN as an integration [PG21][AM22] reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 2: Task execution efficiency: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Integration and cooperation: 96,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Implementation ease: 96,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 5: First responder well-being: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Added value in cross-border MCI management: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7 Satisfaction with information content: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Satisfaction with the operational procedure: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information exchange facilitation: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Task execution efficiency: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Integration and cooperation: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Implementation ease: 4 (QUITE AGREED) • First responder well-being: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Added value in cross-border MCI management: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Satisfaction with information content: 4 (QUITE AGREED) • Satisfaction with the operational procedure: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED)
	History of corrective measures	Several improvement aspects identified were then applied to the design of the SIGRUN federated system and its integration into the operational procedures of responders (first responders, logisticians, C2 managers, etc.).
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“I have acted as coordinator and generally the level of management support is very high. The presentation of data for decision making could be improved.”</i> • <i>“Adding specific times to the account. Filtering of information.”</i>

CO.WP5-13-T01 SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“The introduction of digital services provides faster and more accurate access to information and improves the process of triage and victim support.”</i> • <i>“Only minor modifications are needed. Software for data exploitation.”</i>
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 43 – Results sheet CO.WP5-13-T01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See section 17.10 UC1 WP5 Preliminary test and UC1 demonstration evidence (evidence 2 and 4, questions 5 to 12).

19.5.2. CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION	
Description	<p>The VALKYRIES project proposes to use SIGRUN to federate a set of interlinked capabilities of different emergency services to support the response to a multi-casualty incident or disaster at different levels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing information about the incident and casualties between first responders at the scene, promoting interoperability and making their work more effective (deployment, logistics, search and rescue, triage, stabilisation, evacuation). • Sharing information between pre-hospital and hospital facilities to ensure continuity of medical care for victims. • Improving situational awareness and support C2 decision making through a common COP. <p>The VALKYRIES demonstrators have been used to prove that SIGRUN can significantly improve the operating procedures related to C2, logistics, deployment and provision of medical assistance by first responders, enabling a more effective response to MCIs or disasters.</p> <p>A set of technological solutions, federated through SIGRUN and integrated into the operating procedures of each of the emergency services involved in the UCs, has been used as a sample for the demonstration.</p> <p>The evaluation of this enabler on the UC1 demonstrator was carried out by collecting data from the VALKYRIES evaluators during the exercise (on a Excel sheet) and also from data stored in the federated SIGRUN system during the simulation (VERIFICATION ACTION #1). It was focused on the KPIs that measured objective aspects (KPI10 and KPI11) as these had not been assessed in the preliminary tests.</p>
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.2_4, REQ_COM_T5.2_5, REQ_COM_T5.2_6, REQ_COM_T5.2_7, REQ_COM_T5.2_8, REQ_COM_T5.2_9, REQ_COM_T5.2_10,

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
	<p>REQ_COM_T5.2_11, REQ_COM_T5.2_12, REQ_COM_T5.2_13, REQ_COM_T5.2_14, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_4, REQ_COM_T5.3_6, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_10, REQ_COM_T5.3_11, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_13, REQ_COM_T5.3_14, REQ_COM_T5.3_15, REQ_COM_T5.3_16, REQ_COM_T5.3_17, REQ_COM_T5.3_18, REQ_COM_T5.3_19, REQ_COM_T5.3_20, REQ_COM_T5.3_21, REQ_COM_T5.3_22</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
Time to triage: The average time taken to assign triage priorities using the TASSICA triage card.	Time (in seconds) from the victim first approach to the determination of triage priority and immediate actions.	KPI 9: A maximum acceptable average time to assign primary triage priorities: 1,5 min (90 sec).	Demonstration
Triage accuracy: The percentage of correct triage decisions made using the TASSICA triage card.	% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly triaged casualties by the total number of triaged casualties, expressed as a percentage).	KPI 10: Minimum 80% of correctly triaged casualties made during the MCI drill using SIGRUN.	Demonstration
Verification action #1	Date and location	Spanish-Portuguese border area between Valencia de Alcántara (Spain) and Marvão (Portugal). 4 May 2023.	
	Participants	Summa 112 (Madrid, Spain), EMS SES (Extremadura, Spain), 112 EXTREMADURA (Spain), Unidad Militar de Emergencias (UME, Spain), EMS INEM (Portugal), Autoridade Nacional de Emergência e Proteção Civil (Portugal), Hospital do Espírito Santo (Évora, Portugal).	

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

	Description	The objective KPIs relating to the triage time and accuracy using SIGRUN were assessed based on the data recorded in this federated platform during the conduct of the UC1 drill.
	Execution	<p>A cross-border MCI drill was carried out with the participation of different emergency services adopting the roles involved in the emergency response (first responders, disaster managers, technologists, etc.). Each of these roles generated data that were displayed and shared in real time. Rescuers from both countries (Portugal and Spain) were on site to rescue, triage, stabilise and evacuate the victims. At the site of the accident, all the services worked together, but in parallel, on 2 lines with different operating procedures:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Operating procedures normally used by each emergency service. 2. VALKYRIES operating procedure, using the federated SIGRUN system. <p>And at the HESE hospital, as previously mentioned, the reception, triage and assistance procedures for MCI victims were carried out in parallel in 3 different ways, each using a different operating procedure:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Procedure normally used in the institution. 2. VALKYRIES procedure using TASSICA 3 triage cards. 3. VALKYRIES procedure using SIGRUN federated system. <p>In order to establish homogeneous and consistent comparisons, the same number of victims (20) and identical characteristics (age, pathology, vital signs, etc.) were taken into account for the evaluation of this facilitator, both in the field phase and in the hospital phase.</p> <p>The demonstration was complemented in a harmonised way with the other VALKYRIES enablers, within the reference integration implementation provided by the SIGRUN platform. SIGRUN was used as the information exchange system federating various technological and software tools used to support responders as example. During the UC, relevant information will be gathered in order to carry out the proposed demonstrations.</p> <p>The identification data and pathology of the drill victims were fictitious.</p> <p>The terminals were previously configured with the associated users. The permissions and users required for the test within SIGRUN were enabled taking into account GRPD issues. Connectivity 4G between applications is required for the evaluation within SIGRUN. The connectivity between the</p>

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

		terminals and the SIGRUN platform was verified prior to the test.
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 9: Time to triage average (SIGRUN): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Primary triage average: 44 sec (ACHIEVED) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prehospital EMS: 75 sec ▪ Hospital: 12 sec o Secondary triage average: 58 sec (ACHIEVED) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prehospital EMS: 48 sec ▪ Hospital: 67 sec • KPI 10: Triage accuracy (SIGRUN): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Primary triage accuracy: 95% (ACHIEVED) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prehospital EMS: 90% ▪ Hospital: 100% o Secondary triage accuracy: 90% (ACHIEVED) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prehospital EMS: 90% ▪ Hospital: 90% <p>The following results were obtained using the procedures in place before the VALKYRIES proposal (NON SIGRUN):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time to triage average (NON SIGRUN): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Primary triage average: 36 sec <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prehospital EMS: 33 sec ▪ Hospital: 40 sec o Secondary triage average: 79 sec <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prehospital EMS: 111 sec ▪ Hospital: 48 sec • Triage accuracy (NON SIGRUN): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Primary triage accuracy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prehospital EMS: 50% ▪ Hospital: 95% o Secondary triage accuracy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prehospital EMS: 80% ▪ Hospital: 90% <p>A significant variability was observed between the triage times of first responders at the scene and those of hospital staff.</p> <p>The VALKYRIES researchers attributed this to specific aspects of the scene that are not present in the hospital emergency department environment and which make the work considerably more difficult: security, lighting, distances, etc.</p>

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION		
		They also attributed it to the reduced availability of means and materials at the scene of the accident for the stabilisation of the victims. Regarding the accuracy of triage, it should be noted that at the hospital level the results were identical in both cases (using the TASSICA 3 card and the usual HESE procedure). However, at the pre-hospital level, the triage accuracy rate was much better using the SIGRUN operational procedure.
	History of corrective measures	As VALKYRIES focuses on MCI or disaster response in the field, it was decided after UC1 that the subsequent use cases for this enabler would focus on the out-of-hospital environment in order to bring the results as close as possible to reality and to the intended goals of the project.
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 44 – Results sheet CO.WP5-13-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See section 17.10 UC1 WP5 Preliminary test and UC1 demonstration evidence (evidence 9 and 10)

19.6. CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

19.6.1. CO.WP5-3-T01 Adoption of the METHANE model for sharing the essential incident data between emergency services in the EU.

CO.WP5-3-T01 Adoption of the METHANE model for sharing the essential incident data between emergency services in the EU. PRELIMINARY TEST	
Description	<p>The initial shared information on the characteristics of the incident during an MCI or disaster is critical to initiating and maintaining an effective emergency response. By standardising early warning procedures for such incidents, stakeholders can be assured that they will receive consistent and understandable details about the situation or threat and the appropriate steps to address it.</p> <p>VALKYRIES researchers support the METHANE model (proposed in the UK by JESIP in its "Joint Doctrine: the interoperability framework") as incident-related Minimum Data Set (MDS) to provide a common structure for responders and their control centres to share incident information in a consistent, rapid and simple manner.</p> <p>Preliminary testing was carried out in MCI exercises, within the reference integration implementation provided by the SIGRUN platform in an</p>

CO.WP5-3-T01 Adoption of the METHANE model for sharing the essential incident data between emergency services in the EU. PRELIMINARY TEST

	<p>harmonized way. After the drill, information was collected about the respondents' opinion on the proposed enabler. M/ETHANE. Joint doctrine: the interoperability framework. Edition 2 July 2016. Pg 9. https://www.jesip.org.uk/uploads/resources/JESIP-Joint-Doctrine.pdf</p>		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.2_2, REQ_COM_T5.2_2, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_4, REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_BASE_T5.4_4, REQ_COM_T5.4_9, REQ_COM_T5.4_10, REQ_COM_T5.4_20, REQ_COM_T5.4_21, REQ_COM_T5.4_24, REQ_COM_T5.4_25 Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Data relevance: Perceived importance of the data exchanged in the initial alert of a MCI or disaster to facilitate an efficient and effective emergency response.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: Data relevance: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>
Data usefulness: The perceived usefulness of the data exchanged during the drill in the initial alert to facilitate an efficient and effective emergency response.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: Data relevance: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	<i>Functional test</i>

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Verification action #1	Date and location	Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE). Madrid (Spain). 28 March 2023.
	Participants	Doctors, Nurses and Emergency Medical Technicians of the Servicio de Urgencias Médicas (SUMMA 112) of Madrid (Spain), and researchers from the VALKYRIES Consortium.
	Description	<p>A questionnaire has been developed to collect information to assess whether the METHANE method is considered appropriate for the initial reporting of MCI. This questionnaire includes questions (3 and 4) on the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Criticality of the information transmitted in the initial declaration of an MCI or disaster. • Opinion on whether the information provided is appropriate to the needs of EMS in the early stages of an MCI or disaster. <p>The questionnaires are anonymous. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p>
	Execution	<p>A trial of MCI is carried out with the participation of EMS personnel with experience in pre-hospital care. During the drill, the different links necessary for the activation and implementation of an incident response procedure are deployed, starting with the declaration of the incident. The METHANE methodology is used for this purpose. The first responder collects the information contained in this method to declare the incident, and this data is included in the system so that it can be shared by the different agencies. During the course of the exercise, the incident data is updated if there is any change from the initial situation.</p> <p>At the end of the simulation, the first responders answer the questionnaire anonymously.</p>
	Analysis and results	<p>The answers to the questionnaires were expressed on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being the most unfavourable result to the proposal (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) and 5 being the most favourable result (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED). After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: 100,00% • KPI 2: Data usefulness: 100,00% <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data relevance: 5 (TOTALLY AGREED) • Data usefulness: 4 (QUITE IN AGREEMENT)

CO.WP5-3-T01 Adoption of the METHANE model for sharing the essential incident data between emergency services in the EU. PRELIMINARY TEST

History of corrective measures	The METHANE model was used as a reference for the development of SIGRUN and for the integration of the various related software tools used in the project demonstrators by the emergency services involved in the use cases (UCs).
Lessons learned	
Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
End-user feedback	
Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 45 – Results sheet CO.WP5-3-T01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See section 17.10 UC1 WP5 Preliminary test and UC1 demonstration evidence (evidence 2 and 4, questions 3 and 4)

19.7. UC1 WP5 Preliminary test and UC1 demonstration evidence

19.7.1. UC1 WP5 Preliminary test evidence

19.7.1.1. Evidence 1 PRE-TEST WP5: Survey 1

The image shows two pages of a survey form. The top of both pages features the VALKYRIES logo and the text 'COMPLETADO' (Completed). The first page is titled 'Prueba de validación' and contains questions 1 through 4. Each question has five radio button options: 'TOTALMENTE DE ACUERDO', 'BASTANTE DE ACUERDO', 'MODERADAMENTE DE ACUERDO', 'POCO DE ACUERDO', and 'NADA DE ACUERDO'. The second page contains questions 7 through 13, also with the same five radio button options. At the bottom of the second page, there is a section for 'COMENTARIOS, VALORACIONES, SUGERENCIAS' (Comments, ratings, suggestions) and a 'FECHA:' (Date) field with the handwritten date '28/02/2023'.

Figure 43 – WP5 UC1 Evidence 1 PRE-TEST WP5: Survey 1

19.7.1.2.

Evidence 2 PRE-TEST WP5: Survey 2

VALKYRIES

Prueba de validación

- E-WPS-E: Conjunto de datos mínimos de los servicios de emergencias médicas (SMES) para compartir información en IMV y catálogos.
- E-WPS-F: Entendimiento de la interoperabilidad técnica de alerta móvil para servicios de emergencia en IMV y relacionados en la Unión Europea.
- E-WPS-S: SEEM como referencia de integración para facilitar los casos de despliegue y respuesta de los servicios de emergencia en IMV a escala global en la Unión Europea.

CONSENTIMIENTO DE DATOS SMES (E-WPS-E)

3- ¿Cree que los datos que se han transmitido en el ensayo son los adecuados para la adecuada gestión de las alertas por un servicio de emergencia en IMV o demasiado?

TOTALMENTE DE ACUERDO	BAJAMENTE DE ACUERDO	MODERADAMENTE DE ACUERDO	POCO DE ACUERDO	NADA DE ACUERDO
-----------------------	----------------------	--------------------------	-----------------	-----------------

7- ¿Son datos indispensables los que se han transmitido para completar los datos solicitados?

TOTALMENTE DE ACUERDO	BAJAMENTE DE ACUERDO	MODERADAMENTE DE ACUERDO	POCO DE ACUERDO	NADA DE ACUERDO
-----------------------	----------------------	--------------------------	-----------------	-----------------

INTERCAMBIO DE DATOS (E-WPS-F)

8- ¿Cree que se utiliza la información transmitida en la declaración inicial de un SMES o debería para aumentar la eficacia de la respuesta sanitaria y participación al riesgo para las informaciones?

TOTALMENTE DE ACUERDO	BAJAMENTE DE ACUERDO	MODERADAMENTE DE ACUERDO	POCO DE ACUERDO	NADA DE ACUERDO
-----------------------	----------------------	--------------------------	-----------------	-----------------

4- ¿Cree que la información transmitida en el ensayo en la declaración inicial de IMV es suficiente para las necesidades de un servicio de emergencia en los próximos meses de un SMES o demasiado?

TOTALMENTE DE ACUERDO	BAJAMENTE DE ACUERDO	MODERADAMENTE DE ACUERDO	POCO DE ACUERDO	NADA DE ACUERDO
-----------------------	----------------------	--------------------------	-----------------	-----------------

PROCEDIMIENTO SIGMIS DE INTERCAMBIO DE INFORMACIÓN (E-WPS-G)

9- ¿En el momento en que la situación de alerta móvil facilita el intercambio de información entre los diferentes servicios sanitarios implicados en la respuesta a un SMV?

TOTALMENTE DE ACUERDO	BAJAMENTE DE ACUERDO	MODERADAMENTE DE ACUERDO	POCO DE ACUERDO	NADA DE ACUERDO
-----------------------	----------------------	--------------------------	-----------------	-----------------

6- ¿En qué medida piensa que el procedimiento ensayado le permitiría una ejecución más eficaz de sus tareas en un IMV en comparación con la situación actual?

TOTALMENTE DE ACUERDO	BAJAMENTE DE ACUERDO	MODERADAMENTE DE ACUERDO	POCO DE ACUERDO	NADA DE ACUERDO
-----------------------	----------------------	--------------------------	-----------------	-----------------

VALKYRIES

7- ¿Cree que el procedimiento ensayado facilitaría la integración y el trabajo conjunto con otros servicios y/o procedimientos en la respuesta a un SMV?

TOTALMENTE DE ACUERDO	BAJAMENTE DE ACUERDO	MODERADAMENTE DE ACUERDO	POCO DE ACUERDO	NADA DE ACUERDO
-----------------------	----------------------	--------------------------	-----------------	-----------------

8- ¿En qué medida cree que el procedimiento ensayado es fácil y sencillo de aplicar por un primer interviniente sanitario en un IMV?

TOTALMENTE DE ACUERDO	BAJAMENTE DE ACUERDO	MODERADAMENTE DE ACUERDO	POCO DE ACUERDO	NADA DE ACUERDO
-----------------------	----------------------	--------------------------	-----------------	-----------------

VALORACIÓN SIGMIS

9- ¿Cree que la solución propuesta mejora la significativamente el bienestar de los primeros intervinientes sanitarios durante sus tareas operativas en un IMV?

TOTALMENTE DE ACUERDO	BAJAMENTE DE ACUERDO	MODERADAMENTE DE ACUERDO	POCO DE ACUERDO	NADA DE ACUERDO
-----------------------	----------------------	--------------------------	-----------------	-----------------

10- ¿Cree que la solución propuesta puede aportar un valor añadido a la gestión y respuesta en IMV que afecte a varias comunidades o a varios países?

TOTALMENTE DE ACUERDO	BAJAMENTE DE ACUERDO	MODERADAMENTE DE ACUERDO	POCO DE ACUERDO	NADA DE ACUERDO
-----------------------	----------------------	--------------------------	-----------------	-----------------

11- ¿Cuál es su grado global de satisfacción con el CONTENIDO (DATOS) que se han intercambiado en el episodio ensayado de respuesta a IMV?

MUY ALTO	ALTO	MODERADO	BAJO	MUY BAJO
----------	------	----------	------	----------

12- ¿Cuál es su grado global de satisfacción con el PROCEDIMIENTO DE INTERCAMBIO DE INFORMACIÓN que se ha ensayado?

MUY ALTO	ALTO	MODERADO	BAJO	MUY BAJO
----------	------	----------	------	----------

COMENTARIOS, VALORACIONES, SUGERENCIAS:

INSTRUCCIÓN: *Subir a 812*
 FECHA: *28/03/2023*

Figure 44 – WP5 UC1 Evidence 2 PRE-TEST WP5: Survey 2

19.7.1.3.

Evidence 3, 4 and 5 PRE-TEST WP5: Data sheets

Figure 45 – WP5 UC1 Evidence 3, 4 and 5 PRE-TEST WP5: Data sheets

19.7.1.4. Evidence 6 PRE-TEST WP5: VALKYRIES GLOSSARY usability report

VALKYRIES GLOSSARY

Collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution

Report on the usability of the prototype

For this report, the following tasks enabled in the tool have been carried out:

Content

Report on the usability of the prototype	1
1. Register a new term	2
2. Add an existing term	4
3. View an existing term	4
4. Create a new equivalence of an existing term and then delete it	5
5. Create a new source of documentation for an existing term and then delete it	7
6. Approve a term	8
7. Delete a term	8
Completion of hypotheses of usability problems	12

1

1. Register a new term

On the home screen, and click on "Terms"

A green "New" button appears at the top right.

The fields that appear are filled in with the information of the term: definition, URL, source, and category as well as it is included.

The term is included in the glossary as pending approval.

2

Figure 46 – WP5 UC1 Evidence 6 PRE-TEST WP5: VALKYRIES Glossary usability report

19.7.1.5. Evidence 7 PRE-TEST WP5: EUR ERP usability report

EUR-ERP

EU structured repository of emergency response plans

Report on the usability of the prototype

For this report, the following tasks enabled in the tool have been carried out:

Contenido

Report on the usability of the prototype	1
1. Create a new plan	2
2. Setting up an agency	5
3. Assigning agencies involved in an existing scheme	4
4. Consult the items of an existing over plan	5
5. Edit an existing item	6
6. Duplicate a plan item	7
7. Delete an existing item	8
Completion of hypotheses of usability problems	9

1

1. Create a new plan

A green "New" icon appears in the top right-hand corner of the home screen.

When you click on "New" a screen appears to enter the details of the new plan. Click on "Submit" to upload the content.

In the list of plans, the newly introduced status plan is ready appears.

2

Figure 47 – WP5 UC1 Evidence 6 PRE-TEST WP5: EUR ERP usability report

19.7.1.6.

Images PRE-TEST WP5

Orden	Muestra	CATEG	SEXO	EDAD	PATOLOGIA	IMPUNDO	MADRID	MUESTRA	DESCRIP
1	0545	B	F	26	Quemadura / 100% 400	X	NO	M-950	16-500
2	0544	B	F	26	Quemadura / 100% 400	X	NO	M-951	16-500
3	0543	A	M	26	Quemadura / 100% 400	X	SI		
4	0546	A	M	26	Quemadura / 100% 400	X	SI		

Figure 48 – WP5 UC1 Images PRE-TEST WP5

19.7.2. WP5 UC1 evidences

19.7.2.1. Evidence 8 UC1 WP5: EUR-ERP

Figure 49 – WP5 UC1 evidence 8: EUR-ERP 1

Figure 50 – WP5 UC1 evidence 8: EUR-ERP 2

Emergency response plans

Territorial Civil Protection Plan of the Autonomous Community of Extremadura (PLATERCAEX) (Spain)

Official name: Plan Territorial de Protección Civil de la Comunidad Autónoma de Extremadura (PLATERCAEX)

Status: In force **Territorial Scope:** Regional

Agencies involved: Protección Civil Extremadura

[Show plan details](#)

Activation ▼

Categorization ▼

Overall C2 ▼

On scene C2 ▲

- **UNIFIED ADVANCED COMMAND POST**

Denomination	Responsible agency	Responsible post
Advanced Command Post	Civil Protection Department	Expert civil protection coordination staff designated by the Plan Director
- **ON SCENE PUBLIC ALERT & WARNING COMMAND**

Denomination	Responsible agency	Responsible post
Logistics group	Directorate-General responsible for emergencies and civil protection	Technical staff of the Directorate-General responsible for emergencies and civil defence
- **ON SCENE ASSESSMENT COMMAND**

Denomination	Responsible agency	Responsible post
Technical Support Group	Directorate-General responsible for civil protection and emergencies.	Technical staff of the Directorate-General responsible for civil protection and emergencies.
- **ON SCENE LOGISTICS COMMAND**

Denomination	Responsible agency	Responsible post
Logistics group	Directorate-General responsible for emergencies and civil protection	Technical staff of the Directorate-General responsible for emergencies and civil defence
- **ON SCENE OPERATIONS COMMAND**

Denomination	Responsible agency	Responsible post
Intervention Group	Fire and Rescue Service in the area affected by the emergency	Commander of the Fire and Rescue Service in the area affected by the emergency
- **ON SCENE HAZARD CONTROL & FIGHTING COMMAND**

Denomination	Responsible agency	Responsible post
Intervention Group	Fire and Rescue Service in the area affected by the emergency	Commander of the Fire and Rescue Service in the area affected by the emergency
- **ON SCENE SEARCH & RESCUE COMMAND**

Denomination	Responsible agency	Responsible post
Intervention Group	Fire and Rescue Service in the area affected by the emergency	Commander of the Fire and Rescue Service in the area affected by the emergency
- **ON SCENE MEDICAL CARE COMMAND**

Denomination	Responsible agency	Responsible post
Health group	Extremadura Health Service (EHS)	Head of the Extremadura Health Service designated by the Management of the corresponding Health Area or by the Management Directorate of the EHS.

Figure 51 – WP5 UC1 evidence 8: EUR-ERP 3

19.7.2.2.

Evidence 9 UC1 WP5: HESE hospital datasheet

04/05/2023 Hospital do Espírito Santo de Évora (Portugal)

Victim	Triage Time (TP: Primary Triage; TS: Secondary Triage)				HESE			
	Tassica paper	T App	TP	TS	TP	TS	TP	TS
529	0:00:33	0:00:53	0:00:14	0:01:28	0:00:47	0:01:13		
533	0:00:38	0:00:46	0:00:11	0:01:51	0:01:16	0:00:56		
530	0:00:34	0:00:43	0:00:16	0:01:47	0:00:40	0:00:50		
527	0:00:21	0:00:39	0:00:16	0:01:40	0:00:35	0:01:18		
526	0:00:44	0:00:52	0:00:13	0:00:50	0:00:53	0:00:57		
535	0:00:36	0:00:49	0:00:16	0:01:05	0:00:44	0:00:56		
531	0:00:35	0:00:42	0:00:09	0:01:20	0:00:31	0:00:53		
528	0:00:24	0:00:34	0:00:09	0:00:35	0:00:47	0:00:40		
544	0:00:19	0:00:31	0:00:10	0:01:10	0:00:25	0:00:35		
539	0:00:21	0:00:40	0:00:13	0:00:20	0:00:20	0:00:42		
537	0:00:21	0:00:41	0:00:05	0:01:58	0:00:51	0:00:25		
540	0:00:24	0:00:43	0:00:12	0:02:47	0:00:54	0:00:53		
538	0:00:17	0:00:44	0:00:10	0:00:36	0:00:50	0:00:32		
536	0:00:17	0:00:43	0:00:11	0:00:28	0:00:15	0:00:39		
543	0:00:17	0:00:43	0:00:11	0:00:23	0:00:22	0:00:39		
532	0:00:34	0:00:57	0:00:14	0:00:59	0:01:41	0:00:45		
541	0:00:23	0:00:41	0:00:15	0:00:30	0:00:13	0:00:44		
534	0:00:30	0:00:37	0:00:13	0:00:59	0:00:33	0:00:42		
545	0:00:21	0:00:31	0:00:09	0:01:03	0:00:24	0:00:54		
542	0:00:23	0:00:32	0:00:14	0:00:38	0:00:15	0:00:39		
Mean	0:00:27	0:00:42	0:00:12	0:01:07	0:00:40	0:00:48		
Median	0:00:23	0:00:42	0:00:12	0:01:01	0:00:37	0:00:44		

PRIMARY TRIAGE PRIORITY				SECONDARY TRIAGE PRIORITY			
TP Tassica	T App	TP HESE	BENCHMARK	TP Tassica	T App	TP HESE	BENCHMARK
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	1	1	1	3	1	3	1
2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1
2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2
2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2
2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	2	3	2
3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3

ACCURACY	
95,00%	100,00%
90,00%	90,00%

ACCURACY	
95,00%	95,00%
90,00%	90,00%

Figure 52 – WP5 UC1 evidence 9: HESE hospital datasheet

19.7.2.3. Evidence 10 UC1 WP5: On scene datasheet

04/05/2023 VALKYRIES WP5 UC1 Data sheet

PAX ID	1T ANALG (prior.)	1T VALK (prior.)	1T BENCHMARK	2T ANALG	2T VALK (prior.)	2T BENCHMARK	PAX ID	1T ANALG (sec.)	1T VALK (SEC.)	2T ANALG (SEC.)	2T VALK (SEC.)
501	1	1	1	1	1	1	501	52	37	273	42
502	1	1	1	1	1	1	502	60	20	52	67
503	1	1	1	1	1	1	503	60	9	90	10
504	2	1	1	1	1	1	504	50	70	65	42
505	1	3	2	2	3	2	505	60	89	190	29
506	2	1	2	2	1	1	506	36	95	361	41
507	3	1	2	1	1	2	507	36	44	150	10
508	2	2	2	1	2	2	508	45	36	150	54
509	2	1	2	2	2	2	509	34	43	480	58
510	2	1	2	1	1	2	510	20	20	564	55
511	3	3	3	3	3	3	511	30	32	50	25
512	2	3	3	3	3	3	512	45	23	45	9
513	3	3	3	3	3	3	513	35	23	60	31
514	3	3	3	3	3	3	514	30	22	50	31
515	2	2	3	2	2	2	515	35	69	808	3
516	3	3	3	3	3	3	516	20	44	55	27
517	3	3	3	3	3	3	517	25	34	65	19
518	2	2	3	2	2	3	518	30	38	146	13
519	3	3	3	3	3	3	519	30	22	50	22
520	3	3	3	3	3	3	520	45	28	60	15
526	1	1	1	2	1	1	526	33	90	184	35
527	2	1	1	1	1	1	527	34	7	85	32
528	1	1	1	1	1	1	528	41	14	138	131
529	2	1	1	2	1	1	529	52	27	295	145
530	2	2	2	2	2	2	530	30	117	200	12
531	2	1	2	1	1	1	531	33	88	92	20
532	2	2	2	3	2	2	532	35	49	77	10
533	2	3	2	2	3	2	533	59	102	213	35
534	2	2	2	3	3	2	534	31	66	70	59
535	2	2	2	2	2	2	535	28	49	89	31
536	2	3	3	3	3	3	536	30	47	138	4
537	2	3	3	3	3	3	537	34	64	60	56
538	2	3	3	3	3	3	538	33	58	80	29
539	2	3	3	3	3	3	539	23	38	65	78
540	2	3	3	3	2	2	540	29	21	115	64
541	3	3	3	3	3	3	541	26	181	60	48
542	2	3	3	3	3	3	542	43	91	60	49
543	2	3	3	3	3	3	543	25	55	88	59
544	3	3	3	3	3	3	544	23	262	45	27
545	2	3	3	3	3	3	545	20	70	65	46
CORRECT (N)	24	30		31	34		MEAN (sec)	33,1	74,8	110,95	48,5
INCORRECT (N)	16	10		9	6		MEDIAN (sec)	32	61	86,5	40,5
CORRECT (%)	60,00%	75,00%		77,50%	85,00%						

Figure 53 – WP5 UC1 evidence 9: on scene datasheet

19.7.2.4.

Images UC1 WP5

Figure 54 – WP5 UC1 Images

20. Annex H – WP6 Result sheets Opportunities

20.1. CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

20.1.1. CO-WP6-1-T01- Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

CO-WP6- [PG23]-T01- Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data			
Description	Verify that the data stored in the SIGRUN platform is correctly stored, applying cryptographic mechanisms to ensure that only authorized access can access it. Also, the data transmitted over the network is secure.		
Location/Participants	UMU		
Requirements	REQ_COM_T6.1_1		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Data stored in the SIGRUN platform is encrypted, as well as data transmitted over the network.	100% of data transferred and stored in the SIGRUN platform is encrypted, except for the cases defined in the premises and limitations	KPI 1: Information available: Yes / No (Available = success) KPI 2: data transfer protocol configured to use encrypted communications: encryption setting KPI 3: data is stored with in an encrypted format: encryption setting	Analysis
	Description	Data encrypted	
	Participants	UMU	
	Location	Remotely	
	Execution	To carry out this demonstration, SIGRUN has been configured to store encrypted data and to exchange encrypted data over the network, thus ensuring that the data is protected. SIGRUN works by default with https, which means that its exchanges are encrypted, and the database used by SIGRUN has the capacity to encrypt the data so that it remains confidential in the event of an information leak.	
	Analysis and results	<i>The results obtained are that the information is 100% available and that the data is exchanged encrypted over the network thanks to https. On the other hand, for the simulations, the option of encrypting the data in the database has been highlighted in order to speed up its operation, but this option can be activated at any time.</i>	
History of corrective measures			

CO-WP6- [PG23]-T01- Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data		
	Lessons learned	<i>We have learned that confidentiality of data is a highly important aspect, especially when dealing with medical issues, which is why data encryption mechanisms have been implemented.</i>
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	<i>No end user feedback.</i>
	Result	YES

Table 46 – Results sheet CO-WP6-1-T01